

Towards the Next Generation
Robotic Autonomy on the Edge:
Scalability, Resiliency, and Dynamic
Resource Allocation

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Robotics and AI

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To my family and friends

ABSTRACT

Motivated by the increasing need for advanced autonomy and in response to the computational limitations of onboard robotic systems, this thesis presents unified novel frameworks to enhance the autonomy of computationally resource-constrained aerial and ground robotic systems. The contributions span from designing novel robotic architectures through edge computing and edge/cloud technologies for robust and safe control system design. Furthermore, it contributes by developing resource-aware offloading strategies, scalable cloud/edge deployments, and resilient fallback mechanisms centered around control architectures.

A core focus centers in enabling real-time trajectory control for robotic platforms, primarily Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), by offloading computationally heavy control components to `Kubernetes` (k8s) edge clusters. The proposed edge architecture integrates edge-offloaded Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) with onboard sensing, which requires data transmission between the edge and the robots. A major challenge lies in addressing communication time delays, which are inherent in Networked Control Systems (NCS). By deploying network-aware switching strategies that enable seamless transition between offloaded NMPC and onboard fail-safe control, continuous and safe operation is ensured. By utilizing 5G communication channels and network Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), the system can reactively switch to a safe onboard Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) fallback controller when time delays or signal degradation jeopardize stability.

Building upon this, a series of novel architectures are proposed to explore predictive control under varying communication time delays. Position predictors are introduced to compensate for round-trip time (RTT) delays, enabling smooth UAV behavior. While the computational burden of NMPC is obvious in resource-constrained single-agent systems, it becomes even more critical in Multi-Agent Systems (MAS). Therefore, these control schemes are extended to centralized NMPC and offloaded to edge clusters. The proposed E-CNMPC (Edge-based Centralized NMPC) framework supports real-time swarm trajectory optimization with embedded collision avoidance by offloading the full control stack to the k8s edge cluster.

To address the scalability limitations of centralized NMPC in larger robotic MAS, this thesis introduces novel cloud-based and edge-based architectures that combine intelligent scheduling with dynamic resource modeling. First, dynamic resource allocation based on agent count and prediction horizon length is proposed, ensuring that edge resources are efficiently utilized. Then, a k8s-based scheduling mechanism configures centralized control parameters and dynamically deploys or reconfigures CNMPC pods (similar to E-CNMPC pods) across distributed worker nodes in edge or cloud clusters. The system solves a Mixed-Integer Linear Program (MILP) to optimize controller-to-agent assignment, prediction horizons, and node-level resource allocations, all while respecting hardware and time delay constraints.

In parallel, the framework ensures that closed-loop system stability requirements are met. A polynomial complexity model, derived offline, estimates the computational demand of each controller based on agent count and prediction horizon. This model feeds an online control law that adjusts Central Processing Unit (CPU) and memory requests in real time, ensuring that the total RTT delay remains within a stability-guaranteeing threshold. The result is a robust and responsive orchestration framework that maintains closed-loop performance under dynamic workloads and varying communication time delays, enables seamless controller scaling and migration, and maximizes resource efficiency.

A comprehensive comparison between edge computing architectures demonstrates the advantages of the proposed orchestrated systems in resilience, scalability, and fault recovery. K8s enables features like automated deployment, resource monitoring, and application redundancy, which are essential for mission-critical operations involving aerial robots.

The thesis also includes an evaluation of edge, fog, and cloud architectures designed for robotic systems. This justifies the presented contributions within broader infrastructure choices and offers guidelines for selecting appropriate platforms based on task complexity, time delay sensitivity, and resource constraints.

Overall, this work establishes a broad foundation for edge-enhanced robotic autonomy, providing novel architectural frameworks, implementation strategies, and theoretical models that bridge real-time control with large-scale deployment. By integrating advanced control methods with cloud-native orchestration tools, it demonstrates how edge and cloud infrastructures can be systematically used to overcome the computational and scalability limitations of traditional robotic systems, even in hazardous real-world environments such as underground mines.

The proposed frameworks enable not only reliable and optimized offloading of complex controllers but also adaptive resource management, mission-aware scheduling, and seamless system reconfiguration, which are critical for the future of autonomous robotics operating under dynamic conditions. The presented approaches have been validated through extensive experimentation on simulated agents, and real aerial and ground MAS platforms, confirming their performance in realistic scenarios involving varying number of agents, variable network conditions, and mission-critical timing constraints. The proposed frameworks have been validated through laboratory experiments and further demonstrated to be feasible in real-world deployment scenarios. Together, these contributions offer practical and generalizable insights for the next generation of distributed, resource-efficient, and resilient robotic systems, advancing the field toward robust autonomy at scale.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation & Vision

A defining trend of the modern era is the global shift toward smart cities and Industry 4.0, where intelligent systems, automation, and digital infrastructure are expected to reshape how people live, work, and interact with their environment. Robotics and autonomous vehicles are envisioned as integral parts in domains such as urban mobility, intelligent logistics, environmental monitoring, industrial automation, and emergency response.

Yet, as society moves steadily toward this vision, several foundational technologies remain underdeveloped or insufficiently integrated. Among the most critical enabling technologies are edge and cloud computing, which offer scalable, distributed computational capabilities essential for supporting large-scale, data-intensive, and time-sensitive robotic systems. While these paradigms have matured significantly in enterprise and consumer contexts, their seamless application to autonomous robotic systems remains an open research challenge.

To this end, the thesis unfolds the integration of edge computing technologies with robotic systems, progressively addressing the challenges and opportunities of offloading computation-intensive tasks such as high-level control to the edge. The narrative begins with Chapter 1, which lays the groundwork by introducing the terminology, notation, and theoretical concepts that form the basis for the subsequent developments.

Building on this foundation, Chapter 2 surveys the landscape of edge computing in robotics, identifying critical enablers, system requirements, and architectural trends. This analysis highlights time delay as a fundamental challenge in networked control systems, a challenge that is thoroughly addressed in Chapter 3 through the design of delay-aware control strategies and a resilient fallback mechanism to maintain stability under uncertain network conditions.

With the feasibility of offloading individual controllers to the edge established, Chapter 4 expands the scope to robotic Multi-Agent Systems (MAS), and exploring how edge computing can support scalable and reliable coordination. This includes a centralized control architecture for both ground and aerial robots, as well as a hybrid edge-assisted implementation of safety constraints.

However, the benefits of centralized multi-robot control at the edge come with increasing demands for computational efficiency and adaptability. Chapter 5, addresses this by introducing a dynamic resource allocation framework, providing a primary contribution. It integrates offline complexity modeling, an online control law for delay compensation, and an optimization-based deployment strategy to ensure scalable and real-time execution of edge-offloaded controllers.

Finally, Chapter 6 synthesizes the insights gained throughout the thesis, discusses limitations and lessons learned, and outlines ongoing research directions, ranging from real-time point cloud transmission and network-aware navigation to perceptual data offloading, paving the way for next-generation robotic autonomy in edge-enabled infrastructures.

In this context, the present thesis aims to bridge the gap between robotic autonomy and edge computing, offering a pathway toward deploying resilient, scalable, and computationally efficient robotic systems that can operate in dynamic and resource-constrained environments. Specifically, this work addresses the key challenges of deploying real-time control and coordination mechanisms across edge-enabled infrastructure. By tackling the core issues of time delay, dynamic resource allocation, and multi-robot coordination, the thesis contributes foundational architectural, algorithmic, and experimental advances that bring the vision of smart cities and Industry 4.0 closer to realization.

1.2 Terminology

Before introducing the notion of this work, it is essential to clearly define the terminology used throughout the thesis. The thesis begins by presenting the concepts of edge-based systems, followed by an overview of the time-delayed control, and a stability analysis of networked closed-loop systems, as well as the proposed solutions. The abbreviations and mathematical notations used throughout the thesis are defined in Tables 1.1-1.2 and Table 1.3. respectively.

These abbreviations and notations are used throughout the theoretical developments and algorithmic formulations presented in later chapters. Any additional symbols introduced within a chapter are defined in the corresponding chapter.

1.3 Edge Computing for Robotic Systems

Currently, the robotics community is pushing the autonomy levels of the next generation of applications with autonomous robots [1]. Among the typical examples, multi-session Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM) can be highlighted, with multiple robots performing exploration or map-based navigation missions that include collaborative online point cloud map merging while simultaneously estimating each robot's localization [2]. These tasks are computationally expensive and demand extensive processing capabilities. In response to these demands, edge computing offers high potential by offloading such tasks from onboard computers and enabling faster execution through real-time processing capabilities. Additionally, the integration of edge architectures with emerging 5G communication technologies, offering gigabit speeds and low latencies, can enable seamless communication between robots [3,4].

Table 1.1: Abbreviation table (A-M)

Abbreviation	Definition
AA	Aerial-Aerial
AGC	Aerial-Ground-Corresponding
AGO	Aerial-Ground-Other
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APhI	Aerial Physical Interaction
API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
BBU	Base Band Unit
BW	bandwidth
CBF	Control Barrier Function
CNI	Container Network Interface
CNMPC	Centralized Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRI	Container Runtime Interface
CRS	Container Runtime Systems
DCB	Decentralized Control Block
DL	Deep Learning downlink
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GG	Ground-Ground
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IoT	Internet-of-Things
IP	Internet Protocol
k8s	Kubernetes
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
L4S	Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LIO	LiDAR Inertial Odometry
LLC	Low-Level Control
LMIs	Linear Matrix Inequalities
LQR	Linear-Quadratic Regulator
LS	Least Squares
MAS	Multi-Agent Systems
MAV	Micro Aerial Vehicle
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Program
ML	Machine Learning

Table 1.2: Abbreviation table (M-Z)

Abbreviation	Definition
MoCap	Motion Capture System
MPC	Model Predictive Control
NCS	Networked Control System
NID	Near-Identity Diffeomorphism
NMPC	Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
NR	New Radio
OS	Operating System
PANOC	Proximal Averaged Newton-type method for Optimal Control
PnP	Perspective-n-Point
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
QoS	Quality of Service
QP	Quadratic Program
RAM	Random Access Memory
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RGB	Red-Green-Blue
RKE	Rancher Kubernetes Engine
RMS	Root Mean Square
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROS	Robot Operating System
RRUs	Remote Radio Unit
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indication
RTT	round-trip time
SA	Standalone
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization And Mapping
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TDD	Time Division Duplex
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UE	User Equipment
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UL	uplink
VM	Virtual Machine
YLLLO	You Look Less than Once
YOLO	You Only Look Once
WMSE	Weighted Mean Squared Error

Table 1.3: Notation table

Notation	Definition
$\tau_u \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	UL time delay
$\tau_d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	DL time delay
$\tau_p \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	Processing time delay
$\tau_{rtt} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	RTT delay
$\tau_{max} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	Maximum allowable time delay
$R_s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	MPC execution rate
$T_s \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$	Sampling time
$e_\tau \in \mathbb{R}$	Error between τ_{max} and τ_{rtt}
$e_{trj} \in \mathbb{R}$	Trajectory tracking error
$s \in \mathbb{R}$	SINR measurements
$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Estimated delay-induced error
$\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \vee \mathbb{R}^3$	Position vector
$\mathbf{p}^{ref} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \vee \mathbb{R}^3$	Reference position vector
$\mathbf{p}^{obs} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \vee \mathbb{R}^3$	Object position vector
$\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^3$	Orientation vector
$\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \vee \mathbb{R}^8$	State vector
$\mathbf{x}^{ref} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \vee \mathbb{R}^8$	Reference state vector
$\mathbf{x}^{obs} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \vee \mathbb{R}^6$	Object state vector
$\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \vee \mathbb{R}^3$	Control input vector
$n_a \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	Total number of agents
$n_c \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	Number of controllers
$\mathbf{n}_{apc} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{n_c}$	Number of agents per controller
$\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{n_c}$	Prediction horizon steps
$n_{max} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	Maximum allowable number of agents
$h_{max} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	Maximum allowable prediction horizon steps
$n_{k8s} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$	Number of k8s nodes
$c \in \mathbb{R}$	Model identification
$r_e \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Modelled resources
$r_c \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Time delay compensation resources
$r_{k8s} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	k8s available resources
$r_{req} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$	Requested resources
$\mathbf{r}_{opt} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n_{k8s}}$	Optimal resources
$\mathbf{r}_{alc} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^{n_{k8s}}$	CPU shares allocation
$\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}^3$	Deployment vector

A typical application that benefits from this integration is multi-robot SLAM, which is critical for risk-aware navigation in dynamically changing environments. Such missions require low latency, minimal lag in high-level command execution, efficient visual representation, and robust data security and privacy [5, 6].

To address these challenges, the development, and utilization of edge computing and 5G technologies is expected to significantly increase the autonomy of robotic systems and overcome existing onboard hardware limitations. Edge platforms, like onboard computers, can handle large amounts of data at high speeds and offer substantial computational capacity along with real-time data transmission. Compared to cloud computing, edge computing brings computation closer to the data source, enabling more efficient processing of locally generated data [7]. Moreover, edge-connected robots benefit from significantly lower latency due to their physical and network proximity to edge data centers.

This work analyzes different cloud-based architectures, with a particular focus on edge-based approaches in the context of robotic systems.

1.3.1 Edge Devices & Robotic Platforms

The growing demand for computational power and storage resources in robotic systems has led to the development of various computing architectures [8]. Researchers across disciplines such as Deep Learning (DL) [9], video analytics [10], and Industry 4.0 [11] are constantly exploring and extending these architectures to solve existing challenges and unlock new opportunities [12].

At their core, edge devices and robotic platforms are individual systems equipped with application-specific sensors, such as cameras and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors, for perception, navigation, and inspection tasks. These sensors can generate gigabytes of data, which must be processed, at least partially, onboard to enable autonomous capabilities. However, due to limited onboard computational resources, especially in resource-constrained platforms such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV)s, only lightweight tasks such as low-level control or single-robot SLAM can be reliably executed. In MAS or in more computationally demanding scenarios, the onboard computer may fail to execute tasks within required real-time bounds or may fail entirely.

1.3.2 Computing Paradigms in Robotics

To address such challenges and enable new functionalities [12], different computing paradigms have been adopted, as analyzed in our published work [13]. These paradigms are typically organized into four conceptual layers (edge devices, edge, fog, cloud), as illustrated in Figure 1.1, where the bottom layer is composed of the robotic devices themselves. These layers are characterized by different hardware specifications such as Graphics Processing Unit (GPU), Central Processing Unit (CPU), and memory, and are defined as follows:

1. **Edge Devices Layer** - Robots and data generation devices
 - (a) Data generation
 - (b) Lightweight onboard processing
 - (c) Low-Level Control (LLC)
 - (d) Other essential onboard operations

Figure 1.1: Computation processing and data storage layers.

2. **Edge Layer** – Offloads computational load from robots to nearby edge servers
 - (a) High-volume, real-time data processing
 - (b) On-premises data visualization
 - (c) High-level control execution
 - (d) Micro-scale data storage
3. **Fog Layer** – An extension of the edge layer, consisting of interconnected nodes
 - (a) Local networking
 - (b) Distributed control response
4. **Cloud Layer** – Offers scalable storage and compute power, but with higher latency
 - (a) Big data analytics
 - (b) Long-term storage

A closer look at each of these layers from a robotics perspective provides insights into the opportunities and constraints they introduce. This thesis focuses primarily on edge computing, and to a lesser extent, cloud computing.

In computationally intensive scenarios involving multiple robots, extending robot capabilities through edge or fog computing is often essential. These layers enable real-time processing of large data streams from robots connected over the network. One example is multi-session SLAM, where several robots explore the same environment and collaboratively merge map data [14, 15]. While the cloud layer provides greater storage and compute resources, it is physically and network distant from the device layer, leading to increased latency. Due to this latency, cloud computing alone cannot address the stringent timing requirements of next-generation robotic systems.

Edge computing emerges as a strong candidate for overcoming these challenges. It allows systems to operate with greater autonomy and longer uptime by reducing the computational burden on individual robots. In MAS, real-time communication and data sharing among robots is essential, particularly when decisions must be coordinated, based on shared environmental understanding [2], or allocate tasks among agents [16].

Using edge computing, sensor data can be transmitted to nearby nodes for intensive processing, and control commands can be returned to robots with minimal delay. Closing the control loop over such an architecture requires reliable, low-latency communication infrastructure, most notably, 5G. The combination of edge computing and 5G offers high bandwidth (BW), low latency, and the ability to offload heavy computation while maintaining responsiveness.

Still, in certain use cases, data may need to be sent to the cloud for long-term storage or advanced analytics [17]. Additionally, the fog computing paradigm provides an intermediate layer for distributed processing. A hybrid edge–fog–cloud architecture is therefore becoming increasingly relevant in robotic applications. While existing reviews, like [18], provide general insights into edge computing, this work specifically focuses on its application within robotics and time-critical, closed-loop systems.

1.4 Networked Control Systems

As this thesis focuses on edge robotics and closed-loop control, the work falls under the broader domain of Networked Control Systems (NCS). While NCS has been extensively studied, it presents persistent challenges, most notably time delays, that must be addressed to ensure safe and reliable control. This thesis acknowledges those challenges, integrates well-established solutions from classical control, and proposes novel architectures tailored to the constraints and opportunities of edge robotics.

In NCS as the one depicted in Figure 1.2, the state of the system is captured at a specific time and transmitted to a remote controller. The time it takes for this state to reach the controller is determined by the uplink (UL) communication channel. After computing the control action, the controller sends the command to the robot via the downlink (DL) channel. The total time elapsed from state capture to control action execution is referred to as the round-trip time (RTT). It is composed of UL and DL, as well as the controller’s processing time. Maintaining the RTT within a bounded threshold is critical for the stability of the closed-loop system.

Figure 1.2: Concept figure of an edge-based networked control system for robotic applications.

1.4.1 Real-Time Control Systems

Real-time control systems are characterized by the need to produce results within strict and predictable time constraints. These timing requirements ensure desired and safe operation of the physical process being controlled. However, physical systems are inherently subject to delays, especially processing and communication delays, that can compromise performance or even destabilize the system. Effectively managing these delays is therefore critical for maintaining both stability and responsiveness in closed-loop control applications.

In NCS, such delays are further amplified by the use of external computation platforms and wireless communication networks. It is therefore essential to recognize the real-time constraints and design appropriate control laws that explicitly account for these delays. In this thesis, control strategies are proposed that compensate for both processing and communication delays, ensuring stability and performance even in the presence of dynamic workloads and variable network conditions.

1.4.2 Communication Delays

Edge-controlled systems, like any NCS, are affected by communication delays. These can be separated into UL (τ_u) and DL (τ_d) delays. In cellular networks, UL and DL delays are often asymmetric, particularly in traditional DL-oriented configurations. This asymmetry comes from both limited processing capabilities in cellular modems and the use of DL-optimized Time Division Duplex (TDD) patterns, which allocate more resources to DL traffic to minimize DL latency relative to UL. As a result, ensuring balanced latency in both communication directions remains a critical challenge for achieving predictable end-to-end control performance.

However, robotic control systems offloaded to the edge require robust and low-latency communication in both directions. A bottleneck in either the UL or DL path can destabilize the system or lead to unsafe behavior. To mitigate this, several industrial deployments rely on 5G New Radio (NR) Standalone (SA) infrastructure, which provides improved latency symmetry, Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees, and higher reliability, making it suitable for edge-enabled robotic control [19]. These capabilities mark a significant step toward closing the loop between physical systems and distributed intelligence, enabling reliable real-time autonomy in complex networked environments.

1.4.3 Processing Delays

In addition to communication delays, the processing time of the controller (τ_p) also plays a crucial role in overall system performance. Processing delays are introduced by the computational effort required to solve optimization-based control laws, such as Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC). When control computation is offloaded to an edge server, these delays depend on the available compute resources, current system load, and algorithmic complexity. Insufficient resources or transient computational bottlenecks can increase solver times, leading to degraded responsiveness or even missed deadlines. To maintain real-time performance and closed-loop stability, it is therefore essential to monitor τ_p continuously and adapt resource allocation dynamically based on system conditions.

By leveraging the flexibility of edge computing, computational resources can be dynamically allocated to ensure that the processing delay remains bounded. For a networked closed-loop system to maintain stability, it is essential that the total RTT ($\tau_{\text{rtt}} = \tau_u + \tau_p + \tau_d$) remains below a maximum allowable threshold (τ_{max}). This thesis proposes resource allocation strategies to ensure that the system respects this timing constraint, even under variable workloads and dynamic mission conditions.

1.5 Infrastructure Enablers for Edge-Based Robotics

With the advent of cloud/edge computing and virtualization, many application domains, including robotics, are exploring how to optimally utilize these technologies. Although virtualization strategies are a well-established topic in both academia and industry, this section reviews the three most widely used virtualization approaches and discusses their characteristics, advantages, and limitations in the context of cloud and edge robotics.

1.5.1 Virtualization Technology

A Virtual Machine (VM) is a computing resource that utilizes software to emulate physical hardware, enabling the deployment of applications and execution of processes independently from the host machine [20]. VMs provide full emulation of hardware components such as CPU, disk, Random Access Memory (RAM), networking devices, and more. They can be configured to support diverse application topologies and offer a stable runtime environment by resolving dependency issues (e.g., Operating System (OS) compatibility, software library versions, etc.).

VMs also support configurable resource allocation, scaling, and redeployment across different host machines. They allow for application isolation and are commonly used in cloud and edge deployments for robotic applications. Furthermore, VMs typically include an entire OS and support features like Graphical User Interfaces (GUI)s, which make them suitable for interactive development environments. However, their full-stack emulation introduces overhead in terms of both memory and startup time.

1.5.2 Containerized Applications

Containers are software packages that encapsulate an application along with all its dependencies. Unlike VMs, containers do not emulate hardware, they emulate only the software environment, making them significantly more lightweight [21]. Containers include system libraries, external software packages, and runtime components necessary for execution, but they share the host OS' kernel. Such are provided as open source through our published work [22].

This lightweight nature enables faster startup times and easier scalability. Most Container Runtime Systems (CRS) like `DOCKER` also support extensive pre-built container repositories. In robotics, one common example is the use of pre-configured Robot Operating System (ROS) containers. Containers can also be stacked and layered to compose more complex software systems. These properties, modularity, portability, and ease of iteration, have contributed to the rise of container-based development and deployment in robotics and edge computing.

1.5.3 Container Orchestration

Orchestration technology has emerged as a reliable and handy solution when dealing with multiple containerized applications. As such, `Kubernetes` (k8s) is an open-source platform designed to orchestrate containerized applications across distributed, network-connected infrastructures [23]. Originally developed by `Google` to manage large-scale deployments of container applications, k8s has become a de facto standard for managing containers in both cloud and edge environments.

K8s provides essential features such as scalability, reliability, robustness, and security. It groups containers into units called pods, which are managed throughout their lifecycle. These pods can include applications such as SLAM systems, or controllers such as Model Predictive Control (MPC) for offloaded control in robotic systems.

K8s supports load balancing, fault tolerance, service discovery, and resource monitoring. It enables dynamic scheduling of workloads across a cluster, ensuring optimal resource utilization. These features make k8s particularly suitable for orchestrating real-time, resource-aware robotic applications in heterogeneous environments. As k8s continues to evolve, its capabilities increasingly support time-critical and mission-critical robotic systems deployed on the edge, therefore, this work focused on developing and utilizing k8s clusters for time-critical robotic applications.

1.6 Research Overview & Contributions

Robotics is increasingly viewed as a key enabler in the broader vision of smart cities and Industry 4.0, where intelligent agents perform critical infrastructure, logistics, and inspection tasks autonomously and cooperatively. Yet, most robotic platforms remain constrained by limited onboard computation, energy capacity, and unreliable wireless connectivity. These constraints limit the practical deployment of advanced algorithms, such as optimization-based control, real-time perception, and MAS coordination, that require high computational throughput and tight integration with low-latency feedback. Bridging this gap is essential to unlock the full potential of autonomous robotic systems in real-world, dynamic environments.

Edge computing, positioned between the robot and the traditional cloud, has emerged as a compelling solution to these limitations. By offering high-performance computing resources near the robot, edge infrastructures enable the offloading of time-critical tasks while reducing BW usage, end-to-end delay, and onboard processing burden. However, realizing edge-based robotic autonomy at scale introduces several system-level challenges. These include maintaining closed-loop stability in the presence of time-varying network delays, orchestrating multiple applications across shared infrastructure, and dynamically allocating computational resources as mission conditions and agent counts evolve. Furthermore, edge deployments must address the inherent variability in connectivity, computational demand, and mission objectives, necessitating adaptable architectures that can reconfigure themselves at runtime. This thesis tackles these open challenges through a unified investigation of edge-based control architectures, delay compensation strategies, and dynamic resource allocation frameworks for scalable, resilient robotic autonomy.

1.6.1 Research Questions

This thesis seeks to answer the following fundamental research questions (RQ):

- **RQ1:** How can the computational capabilities of resource-constrained robots be expanded without compromising real-time control performance?
- **RQ2:** Why is edge computing a suitable paradigm for robotics, and how can it be tailored to address robotics-specific challenges such as tight control loops, time delays, and dynamic environments?
- **RQ3:** How can scalable and resilient control frameworks be designed to maintain robustness and real-time operation as system complexity increases, due to a growing number of agents, environmental uncertainty, or dynamic network conditions?

To address these, the thesis delivers four primary research contributions, each spanning multiple chapters and papers, combining theory and systems design with extensive experimental validation.

1.6.2 Contributions

The research investigates both the control-theoretic and systems-level aspects of the problem, resulting in a set of integrated contributions that span architecture design, delay compensation, MAS coordination, and dynamic resource allocation. These contributions are presented below in four thematic categories, each unfolding across the corresponding chapters of the thesis.

Contributions 1

The first core contribution of this thesis addresses the challenge of enabling real-time advance robotic control on resource-constrained platforms by leveraging edge computing infrastructure. Specifically, it responds to both research questions RQ1 and RQ2 by proposing and validating full-stack system architectures that offload computationally intensive control logic, such as NMPC, from onboard processors to edge servers.

This contribution is primarily developed in Chapter 2 and has been disseminated through a series of publications, including conference papers and journals detailed in 1.6.3. In Papers 3 through 8, where the architecture was progressively refined from simulation (Papers 3–5), to laboratory experiments with integrated collision avoidance (Papers 6–7), and eventually to real-world deployment in a 5G-connected underground mine (Paper 8). Supporting groundwork was established in Papers 1 and 2, which helped scope the thesis through a survey of enabling technologies and the open-source release of key architectural components, and Paper 9 that validate the proposed architecture in different scenarios and missions. Together, these efforts mark one of the first end-to-end demonstrations of edge-offloaded NMPC for aerial robots operating under real-time and safety-critical conditions.

Contributions 2

The second major contribution of this thesis addresses the central challenge of maintaining closed-loop stability and safe operation in the presence of time-varying communication delays, a key aspect of RQ2. As edge-controlled robotic systems are inherently subject to network-induced latency, this contribution introduces a comprehensive delay-resilient control framework that combines real-time state prediction and a robust fallback mechanism.

This contribution is developed and evaluated in Chapter 3 and disseminated across multiple publications. These publications contribute in the conceptual design, architecture, and implementation of the delay prediction and switching framework, which are documented in Papers 10 and 11. These papers reflect the contributions in the core architecture and mathematical validation of the switching logic, as well as the integration of the delay-compensation approach to edge-controlled systems. These works advance the state-of-the-art in resilient edge robotics by demonstrating how edge-offloaded NMPC can operate safely under unpredictable network behavior, an essential capability for real-world deployment scenarios.

Contributions 3

The third contribution extends the architectural foundations established for single-agent systems to robotic MAS, addressing the scalability and coordination challenges raised in RQ3. Specifically, it proposes two edge-enabled control frameworks that support either centralized or hybrid MAS control, thereby enabling real-time trajectory coordination, constraint enforcement, and collision avoidance among teams of either homogeneous or heterogeneous robots.

These contributions are elaborated in Chapter 4, and disseminated through two journal articles. Paper 12 introduces the Edge-based Centralized Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (E-CNMPC) framework with experimental validation in lab environments using ground robots. In Paper 13, the contribution of this thesis is primarily the system architecture, that presents the hybrid (edge-onboard) architecture to a heterogeneous aerial-ground MAS, demonstrating scalability and safety in complex, shared task spaces. Together, these works represent two different scalable, experimentally validated frameworks for edge-assisted MAS coordination, providing a blueprint for future edge-based autonomy across diverse robot teams.

Contributions 4

The final and most significant contribution of this thesis lays on the development of a dynamic resource allocation framework for edge-offloaded centralized control, addressing the full scope of RQ3. While previous contributions focused on architectural feasibility and stability, this work tackles the critical issue of resource-awareness and autonomous orchestration, ensuring that the control system remains efficient, robust, and scalable as system demands evolve.

These results are developed in Chapter 5, which forms the thesis' theoretical and technical core. This work is disseminated through three papers. Paper 14 introduces the scheduling mechanism for scalable CNMPC deployment, while Paper 15 extends this with a delay-aware resource controller and resource modeling and Paper 16 integrates these into a full optimization-based framework.

Collectively, these contributions offer a novel and complete solution to the dynamic resource management problem for edge-based MAS, enabling robotic systems to operate efficiently under real-time constraints, fluctuating workloads, and communication variability. This work lays the foundation for future research in self-optimizing, resilient robotic systems at the intersection of control theory, edge computing, and distributed systems.

1.6.3 Summary of Published Works

The research presented in this thesis has been disseminated through a series of peer-reviewed conference proceedings, journal articles, and the licentiate thesis [24]. These publications cover a broad spectrum of the work, ranging from conceptual and theoretical developments to experimental evaluations that validate the core hypotheses of the thesis. The works listed below collectively form the foundation of this dissertation and reflect its evolution across different domains and application layers. The list includes both standalone contributions and collaborative efforts.

1. **A. S. Seisa**, G. Damigos, S. G. Satpute, A. Koval, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Edge Computing Architectures for Enabling the Realisation of the Next Generation Robotic Systems,” in 2022 30th Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED). IEEE, 2022, pp. 487–493, doi: 10.1109/MED54222.2022.9837289 [13].
2. **A. S. Seisa**, V. N. Sankaranarayanan, G. Damigos, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Cloud-Assisted Remote Control for Aerial Robots: From Theory to Proof-of-Concept Implementation,” in 2025 IEEE 25th International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Internet Computing Workshops (CCGridW), 2025, pp. 171–176, doi: 10.1109/CCGridW65158.2025.00032 [22].
3. **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, B. Lindqvist, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “An Edge Architecture Oriented Model Predictive Control Scheme for an Autonomous UAV Mission,” in 2022 IEEE 31st International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE). IEEE, 2022, pp. 1195–1201, doi: 10.1109/ISIE51582.2022.9831701 [25].
4. **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “A Kubernetes-Based Edge Architecture for Controlling the Trajectory of a Resource-Constrained Aerial Robot by Enabling Model Predictive Control,” in 2022 26th International Conference on Circuits, Systems, Communications and Computers (CSCC). IEEE, 2022, pp. 290–295, doi: 10.1109/CSCC55931.2022.00056 [26].
5. **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Comparison Between Docker and Kubernetes Based Edge Architectures for Enabling Remote Model Predictive Control for Aerial Robots,” in IECON 2022–48th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society. IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/IECON49645.2022.9968933 [27].
6. **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, B. Lindqvist, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “An Edge-Based Architecture for Offloading Model Predictive Control for UAVs,” *Robotics*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. 80, 2022, doi: 10.3390/robotics11040080 [28].

7. **A. S. Seisa**, B. Lindqvist, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “An Edge Architecture for Enabling Autonomous Aerial Navigation with Embedded Collision Avoidance Through Remote Nonlinear Model Predictive Control,” *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, p. 104849, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jpdc.2024.104849 [29].
8. **A. S. Seisa**, E. Pagliari, G. Damigos, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Real-World Deployment of a 5G-Connected Edge-Controlled Aerial Robot in Industrial Subterranean Mines,” 2025 [Accepted for presentation at IEEE/SICE International Symposium on System Integration (SII 2026)].
9. A. Berra, V. N. Sankaranarayanan, **A. S. Seisa**, J. Mellet, U. G. Gamage, S. G. Satpute, F. Ruggiero, V. Lippiello, S. Tolu, M. Fumagalli et al., “Assisted Physical Interaction: Autonomous Aerial Robots with Neural Network Detection, Navigation, and Safety Layers,” in 2024 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS). IEEE, 2024, pp. 1354–1361, doi: 10.1109/ICUAS60882.2024.10557050 [30].
10. V. N. Sankaranarayanan, G. Damigos, **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, T. Lindgren, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “PACED-5G: Predictive Autonomous Control Using Edge for Drones over 5G,” in 2023 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS). IEEE, 2023, pp. 1155–1161, doi: 10.1109/ICUAS57906.2023.10156241 [31].
11. G. Damigos, **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, T. Lindgren, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “A Resilient Framework for 5G-Edge-Connected UAVs Based on Switching Edge-MPC and Onboard-PID Control,” in 2023 IEEE 32nd International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE). IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–8, doi: 10.1109/ISIE51358.2023.10228114 [32].
12. **A. S. Seisa**, B. Lindqvist, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “E-CNMPC: Edge-Based Centralized Nonlinear Model Predictive Control for Multi-Agent Robotic Systems,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 121 590–121 601, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3223446 [33].
13. V. N. Sankaranarayanan, **A. S. Seisa**, A. Saradagi, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Barriers on the EDGE: A Scalable CBF Architecture over EDGE for Safe Aerial-Ground Multi-Agent Coordination,” 2025 [Submitted in journal based on [34]].
14. **A. S. Seisa**, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Cloud-Based Scheduling Mechanism for Scalable and Resource-Efficient Centralized Controllers,” in *IECON 2024 - 50th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, 2024, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/IECON55916.2024.10905254 [35].
15. **A. S. Seisa**, S. Kotpalliwar, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Dynamic Computational Resource Allocation for Ensuring Stability of Remote Edge-based Controlled Multi-Agent Systems,” in 2025 European Control Conference (ECC). IEEE, 2025, pp. 2907–2913, ,” 2025 European Control Conference (ECC), Thessaloniki, Greece, 2025, pp. 2907-2913, doi: 10.23919/ECC65951.2025.11187111 [36].

16. **A. S. Seisa**, S. Velhal, S. Kotpalliwar, S. G. Satpute, and G. Nikolakopoulos, “Optimization of Edge-Offloading for Centralized Controllers Through Dynamic Computational Resource Allocation,” 2025 [Minor revision of [37] submitted in the IEEE IoT Journal].

1.7 Thesis Chapters

The thesis is organized into multiple chapters, each of which builds upon the concepts and foundations established in the previous sections. A brief overview of the content and purpose of each chapter is provided below to guide the reader through the progression of ideas, contributions, and technical developments presented throughout the work, while the introduction establishes the main concepts and research scope of the thesis.

- **Chapter 2 – Edge-Offloading Architectures:** Presents the foundational system architectures that enable the offloading of computationally intensive control tasks from resource-constrained robots to edge computing infrastructure. The chapter introduces full-stack implementations using `DOCKER` and `k8s`, alongside 5G NR SA communication for low-latency data exchange. It also details real-time constraints for NMPC and provides extensive validation through simulated and real-world experiments, including UAV deployments in subterranean industrial environments.
- **Chapter 3 – Addressing Time Delay Impact:** Analyzes the effects of time-varying delays, both communication and processing, on the stability of edge-controlled robotic systems. This chapter introduces a state prediction mechanism to compensate for delayed feedback, and a Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)-driven switching strategy that enables fallback to onboard controllers when network quality degrades. Together, these contributions form a resilient edge control framework capable of maintaining safe operation under uncertain connectivity conditions.
- **Chapter 4 – Edge Architectures for Multi-Agent Systems:** Focuses on the extension of edge-offloaded control to MAS. It proposes a centralized edge-based control using CNMPC for cooperative ground robots and another approach that addresses safety constraints through decentralized onboard Control Barrier Functions (CBF)s. The chapter presents the E-CNMPC approach as well as a hybrid coordination architecture for heterogeneous MAS, and includes experimental evaluations demonstrating coordinated swarm behavior, obstacle-aware navigation under real-time constraints, and heterogeneous robot collaboration.
- **Chapter 5 – Dynamic Resource Allocation:** Develops the thesis’ core contribution, a dynamic resource allocation framework for edge-offloaded CNMPC control. This chapter introduces an offline modeling methodology using second-order polynomial regression to estimate the computational complexity of CNMPCs. A delay-aware control law is then proposed to ensure bounded RTT, and a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem is formulated to optimize controller deployment and resource usage. Real-world experiments validate the framework’s ability to dynamically adapt to varying agent counts, prediction horizons, and network conditions.

- **Chapter 6 – Conclusions:** Reflects on the research findings, synthesizes the main contributions, and discusses system-level implications for real-world robotic autonomy. It outlines limitations, lessons learned, and proposes future research directions, including dynamic perceptual offloading, network-aware navigation, and sub-map streaming for collaborative MAS mapping.

Edge-Offloading Architectures

2.1 Overview

Recent advancements in cloud computing and Internet-of-Things (IoT) have created new opportunities for resource-constrained robotic systems through computational offloading. While cloud computing offers scalable computing and storage resources [38, 39], its inherent latency makes it unsuitable for time-critical robotic applications such as real-time navigation with embedded collision avoidance [40–42]. Edge computing reduces transmission delays, enables responsive and real-time processing, by placing computation closer to the robot [43, 44].

Edge computing has the potential to extend the capabilities of autonomous robotic platforms by supporting advanced control methods, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and sensor fusion. These benefits are especially critical for lightweight platforms like Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAV)s, which lack the onboard processing power to run complex algorithms [45].

An extensive range of research has demonstrated the feasibility of offloading tasks such as object detection, SLAM, and trajectory planning to edge systems [46–50]. In these studies, robotic platforms transmit sensor data to nearby edge servers, where decisions are computed and returned with low latency. These architectures often leverage containerization and ROS-based messaging for modular deployment [51, 52]. However, most existing implementations focus on simulation environments or cloud-based orchestration, where latency constraints and real-world variability are less critical [53, 54].

This work builds on these insights and shifts the focus to edge-based architectures suitable for closed-loop, time-critical control applications deployed in dynamic and industrial environments, as illustrated in Figure 2.1. It explores how technologies such as `Docker` containers, `k8s`, and 5G NR SA infrastructure can be integrated to support offloading of high-performance control frameworks, particularly NMPC, from onboard systems to edge infrastructure. Unlike cloud-native deployments, the proposed edge frameworks are optimized for real-time control, mission-critical stability, and system responsiveness.

Figure 2.1: Concept figure of the edge-offloading architecture.

2.2 Contributions

This chapter contributes novel edge-based architectures for deploying computationally intensive, real-time control applications for resource-constrained aerial robots, with a main focus on NMPC. The system is designed to meet the latency, safety, and scalability demands of autonomous robotics operating under time-critical conditions.

The main contributions can be summarized as (i) the design of novel closed-loop system architectures for offloading NMPC-based controllers from UAVs’ onboard computers to edge servers using `Docker` containers and `k8s` orchestration, to support high-frequency control loops and long prediction horizons, while maintaining real-time bounds; (ii) the incorporation of 5G NR SA networks to ensure robust UL and DL performance for data transmission; (iii) the experimental validation in both laboratory conditions and real-world environments such as subterranean industrial sites, which demonstrate the feasibility of maintaining stable, closed-loop control despite limited onboard resources and dynamic network conditions, and (iv) the utilization of `k8s` which allows for rapid deployment, scaling, and monitoring of ROS-based applications, while enabling edge servers to dynamically manage control workloads and compensate for processing delays through container-based isolation and scheduling.

By addressing the gap between academic research and real-world deployments, this work moves the field closer to practical, robust edge robotic systems. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first implementation and experimental validation of a 5G-connected, edge-controlled closed-loop NMPC system for aerial robots in an active industrial environment. These frameworks lay the groundwork for extending edge offloading to more complex tasks such as perception, mapping, and collaborative control across heterogeneous MAS.

The next sections introduce the architectural system that underlies the key contributions of this thesis. It presents the proposed edge-based control frameworks, detailing how the integration of containerization, orchestration, real-time control, and network communication has been realized.

2.3 Edge-Controlled Architectures

Edge computing has become a key enabler for modern robotic systems by allowing the offloading of computationally intensive processes from resource-constrained platforms to nearby infrastructure. This section reviews prior architectures proposed in the literature and contextualizes the design choices of this work within the state-of-the-art by highlighting its structure, data flow, deployment methodology, and real-world implementation on UAVs. Specifically, it focuses on system-level designs for edge-based robotics, including containerized applications, and orchestration technologies.

In [51], a four-layer architecture was proposed for offloading the SLAM problem across robot, edge, fog, and cloud layers. This architecture enables collaborative mapping across multiple robots by offloading local maps to the edge and performing merging operations further up the hierarchy. Similarly, [55] introduced an edge-based system for SLAM map merging and real-time processing. These works illustrate the potential of multi-layer architectures but highlight a trade-off between compute scalability and latency, particularly when cloud servers are involved. In time-critical scenarios, edge-layer processing remains essential to meet time constraints.

Docker-based deployments have become widespread in robotic applications for modular and scalable system design. In [53], containerized robotic applications using Docker and k8s were deployed in a cloud cluster to facilitate task offloading and monitoring. The architecture integrated ROS-based communication and was evaluated in an industrial setting. However, real-time control tasks remained onboard due to latency and reliability concerns. In contrast, the work of this thesis offloads the controller itself to the edge cluster, achieving real-time performance through optimized container orchestration and dedicated network infrastructure.

Container orchestration using k8s has also been proposed for edge applications. In [54], a k8s-based deployment system for robotic containers was presented, enabling flexible application distribution between edge and cloud resources. Similarly, [56] implemented a remote controller using Docker containers hosted on a mobile edge server, demonstrating the feasibility of offloading control operations. [57] further expanded this idea by using stochastic optimization to schedule container deployments across fog, edge, and cloud environments, with k8s managing the lifecycle.

In [58], researchers introduced a low-latency edge service architecture to facilitate container interactions for robotic applications. This approach emphasized minimal network overhead and efficient resource use. Complementarily, [59] presented a distributed edge-cloud system using virtual clusters and open-source networks to manage robotic deployments. [60] surveyed container technologies and orchestration platforms, comparing them with traditional VM-based virtualization and highlighting their advantages in resource efficiency and deployment speed.

While most prior works demonstrate the feasibility of container-based offloading, they often focus on non-real-time applications or simulation environments. This thesis extends these contributions by demonstrating a real-time, closed-loop control system deployed entirely at the edge, supported by k8s and ROS integration. This design enables latency-sensitive tasks, such as NMPC execution, to be offloaded without violating real-time constraints.

The proposed architecture builds on the strengths of these earlier systems but emphasizes deployment in operational, non-laboratory environments and the offloading of time-critical control logic. It is tailored for aerial robotic platforms operating under strict timing constraints, and it represents, to the best of our knowledge, one of the first real-world demonstrations of edge-deployed NMPC controllers in autonomous UAV missions.

2.3.1 Architecture & Frameworks

The overall edge-based architecture consists of two sides: the robot (or robots) side and the k8s edge cluster side, and in some cases, a human which provides a reference input, as depicted in Figure 2.2. The robot start sending its state, i.e., position $\mathbf{p}(t)$, velocity $\mathbf{v}(t) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t)$, and orientation $\mathbf{q}(t)$. These state components form the state vector $\mathbf{x}(t)$. These signals are delayed as they travel from the robot to the edge k8s cluster. Thus, at the same time instance, the edge receives the information $\mathbf{x}(t - \tau_u(t))$, where $\tau_u(t)$ denotes the UL at time t . Simultaneously, when a human operator provides a reference signal $\mathbf{x}^{\text{ref}}(t)$, the signal received by the k8s cluster is also subject to UL channel delays, and therefore the received signal is denoted as $\mathbf{x}^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_u(t))$. The control algorithm processes these signals to generate control actions, represented as $\mathbf{u}(t)$, aiming to optimize the system's action. Consequently, these control actions are sent from the edge k8s cluster back to the robot. To describe this delay, the control actions received by the robot are referred to as $\mathbf{u}(t - \tau_d(t))$, where $\tau_d(t)$ is the DL introduced during data transmission from the edge to the robot. The main aim of this control strategy, is to guide the robot through a defined area while adhering to control limits, and preventing potential collisions.

Figure 2.2: Overview of the edge-offloaded control architecture.

The sequence of data streaming between the UAV and the edge, including the timing and structure of state and control signals, is further detailed in Section 2.3.2, which provides a comprehensive view of the information exchange underlying the closed-loop system.

2.3.2 Data Flow

The edge-based control system's data flow provides seamless communication between the robot and the k8s edge cluster. Operating on two levels, the system employs a proxy server with a User Datagram Protocol (UDP) tunnel to streamline robot-edge interactions, compared to Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) that prioritizes reliability over speed and low latency. Within the k8s cluster, the ROS networking mechanism is implemented.

Data Transmission Through a Proxy Server

To transfer ROS messages between the robot and the edge cluster, a proxy server that leverages a UDP tunnel with client and server nodes is implemented, to minimize data transmission overhead. One end of the tunnel is established at the robot to transmit and receive data, while the other is at the proxy server of the edge cluster. The robot sends its states, such as position, velocity, and orientation, to the edge via the proxy server's Internet Protocol (IP) address. Before transmission, ROS messages are converted into byte arrays to facilitate efficient data transfer. The proxy server, enabled by the k8s Node Port mechanism, decodes the byte arrays and forwards the data as ROS messages to nodes within the k8s pods. Data reaches the edge with an UL delay denoted by τ_u . Similarly, control commands, roll, pitch, yaw, and thrust, are converted into byte arrays and transmitted back to the robot through the client node of the proxy server with a DL delay τ_d .

To ensure efficient data exchange and eliminate data streaming conflicts, sockets are dynamically allocated, assigning unique ports for each message transfer. Since the controller is a stateful application, it is critical to share data across all nodes within the k8s cluster. The proxy server consolidates all necessary information and uses ROS for internal communication within the cluster, thereby resolving potential communication issues and enabling smooth transitions between the modules of the control application.

Robotic Operating System Networking

Within the k8s cluster, all pods share a common network environment, allowing ROS nodes to interact seamlessly through the ROS subscription and publication protocols. For effective communication, all ROS nodes register with a single ROS master. This master operates independently in its own k8s pod to minimize potential disruptions and ensure smooth operation during runtime.

ROS facilitates real-time communication between the edge-offloaded control modules and the UAV. State information is transmitted from the UAV through a UDP tunnel and received by the cluster's proxy server, where it is published to an odometry ROS topic. Similarly, reference trajectories are published to a reference topic. The NMPC module subscribes to both topics, computes the control actions, and publishes them to a command topic. These control commands are then streamed back to the UAV through the UDP tunnel, where they are received by the UAV's ROS node subscribed to the command topic. Delays introduced in publishing and subscribing are compensated using timestamping and time synchronization, ensuring a consistent and stable closed-loop operation.

Data Streaming

Figure 2.3 illustrates the data flow between the robot and edge. The system operates over a robust network (e.g., Wi-Fi or 5G), with time delays characterized by RTT communication time $\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)$ and edge-side computation time $\tau_p(t)$. By utilizing the computational capacity of edge computing, commands can be generated at up to 100 Hz, closely matching the UAV's state update rate R_s . High control rates improve agility but require sufficient computational resources. K8s provides mechanisms for dynamically allocating these resources to prevent congestion and ensure consistent performance.

Figure 2.3: Data-packet exchange flowchart between the robot and the edge.

State signals, generated at a fixed rate R_s by the UAV's onboard sensors, are continuously transmitted to the edge via the proxy server. Each state vector $\mathbf{x}(t)$ experiences an UL delay $\tau_u(t)$ before arriving at the edge cluster, where it is received as $\mathbf{x}(t + \tau_u(t))$. Upon receipt, the state is forwarded to the MPC application pod, which computes the corresponding control input after a processing delay $\tau_p(t)$.

The resulting control action, denoted as $\mathbf{u}(t + \tau_u(t) + \tau_p(t))$, is transmitted back to the UAV. This DL transmission introduces an additional delay $\tau_d(t)$, such that the control command, corresponding to the state $\mathbf{x}(t)$, is finally applied at the UAV as $\mathbf{u}(t + \tau_u(t) + \tau_p(t) + \tau_d(t))$.

This entire loop defines one RTT for the closed-loop control system, as expressed by (2.1). As discussed in later sections, maintaining the RTT within a bounded threshold is critical for preserving the stability and responsiveness of the system. The streaming and control process is repeated at every control cycle, maintaining synchronization with the state update frequency R_s .

$$\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) = \tau_p(t) + \tau_u(t) + \tau_d(t) \quad (2.1)$$

2.3.3 Containerization

All applications are containerized using `Docker` and multiple images are deployed. Mainly an NMPC image, including all ROS `Noetic` dependencies, optimization libraries, and the NMPC algorithm, and a ROS master image, hosting the `roscore` service for inter-node communication. Additional images were deployed to enable the proxy server and all other needed control modules. These lightweight containers ensure portability, ease of deployment, and environment consistency. They are stored in `Docker Hub` for reuse and integration with k8s.

2.3.4 Edge Cluster

Throughout the thesis, multiple different edge cluster configuration were utilized. Mostly, k8s is used as an orchestration layer to manage containerized workloads across edge nodes.

Typically, in most of the presented works, the edge system consists of a k8s cluster specifically configured to offload heavy computational tasks from robots. An on-premises cluster setup is implemented to guarantee low-latency interactions and substantial processing power essential for real-time control applications. It includes a master node, which is also capable of hosting applications, and two worker nodes. The hardware specifications of these nodes are listed in Table 2.1, while the k8s software environment is summarized in Table 2.2.

Table 2.1: Hardware specifications of edge k8s nodes

Specs	Node 1	Node 2	Node 3
CPU	i5@3.30GHz	i5@2.80GHz	i7@2.80GHz
CPU-cores	12	12	8
Memory [GB]	13	28	7
Storage [GB]	46	98	98

The cluster was developed within a k8s environment by employing three nodes, each operating with a `Linux`-based OS system, similarly to [61]. The Container Runtime Interface (CRI) was facilitated by `Docker`, and the `Calico` network plugin was employed for Container Network Interface (CNI).

By transferring tasks to the cluster, the robots can prioritize flight execution while offloading the complex computations, of control algorithms and predictive modeling, to the edge. This architecture improves the overall system performance, enhances scalability, and reduces the computational load on the robots, ensuring smooth operation.

K8s orchestrates the entire edge-side infrastructure. It handles pod scheduling, application scaling, health monitoring, and resource allocation. Key benefits include: (i) scalability and flexibility, as controllers for UAVs can be launched as individual pods with assigned CPU/memory limits; (ii) reliability, as rollbacks, self-healing, and replica management improve system robustness, and (iii) resource-awareness as k8s allows dynamic allocation of pods to edge nodes based on real-time workload.

Table 2.2: Software configuration of edge k8s cluster

Specs	Node 1	Node 2	Node 3
OS	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS (Focal Fossa)		
k8s-version	v1.28.11		
Kernel-version (5.4.0-X)	212-generic	200-generic	205-generic
Role	Control plane	Worker	Worker
Container runtime	Docker (docker://27.0.3)		
CNI	Calico		

Table 2.3: Sequence of operations for deploying the edge-controlled architecture

Step	Operation Description
1	Build Docker images and upload them to Docker Hub.
2	Create k8s services and deployments to pull and launch the pods.
3	Configure network to enable communication between UAV and edge.
4	Initialize the UAV system and activate edge-offloaded NMPC control.
5	Execute the flight operation, including take-off, trajectory tracking, and landing.

The k8s cluster includes a master node (with `kube-scheduler`, `kube-controller`, `kube-apiserver`, `etcd`) and worker nodes (with `kubelet` and `kube-proxy`). Multiple pods are deployed, including the NMPC pod that executes control modules, and the ROS master pod that manages communication between nodes, as described in our published work [26].

Figure 2.4 presents a complete block diagram of the architecture, illustrating the interactions between the UAV, edge pods, and k8s components, while Table 2.3 describes the operation sequence. For clarity, only the main control modules are highlighted. The edge side includes the NMPC controller, the ROS master, and the UDP tunnel that enables communication with the UAV, while the UAV side includes the corresponding end of the UDP tunnel, the onboard sensors used to generate state estimates, and the LLC, which actuates the UAV based on the control actions received from the offloaded NMPC module.

Figure 2.4: Block diagram of the edge architecture for the UAV-NMPC system.

2.4 Control Offloading Strategies

Offloading control logic from onboard robotic platforms to edge servers introduces both opportunities and challenges. While the computational burden is reduced on the robot, ensuring that the closed-loop system remains stable and responsive despite network-introduced delays is non-trivial. This section presents control offloading strategies and how they address timing, reliability, and system integration challenges.

In [56], the authors proposed a mobile edge server running a containerized controller for remote robot operation. This work showed the feasibility of running closed-loop control on an edge platform but did not provide detailed analysis on RTT guarantees or integration with orchestration frameworks like k8s.

A more comprehensive solution was introduced in [54], where a k8s-based deployment mechanism allowed robotic applications, including controllers, to be dynamically distributed between edge and cloud infrastructure. However, this architecture was primarily evaluated in terms of flexibility and deployment ease, with less emphasis on real-time performance metrics.

In [53], a monitoring architecture using `Docker` and k8s was applied to industrial mobile robots. Although the system enabled task offloading and management, control tasks remained local to the robots, primarily due to concerns over latency and control reliability.

2.4.1 Nonlinear Model Predictive Control Offloading

NMPC and MPC are inherently computationally intensive due to their reliance on online optimization. In systems with high-dimensional states or demanding timing requirements, onboard processors may struggle to execute NMPC within acceptable bounds. To address this, some researchers have explored distributed or assisted control strategies. For instance, [62] introduced a distributed MPC framework for autonomous vehicle platooning, deploying two MPCs to coordinate merging behaviors across parallel lanes.

In [63], a hybrid control architecture was evaluated using a simulated ball-and-beam setup, where a Linear-Quadratic Regulator (LQR) controller ran locally and MPC instances were offloaded to both edge and cloud nodes. The MPC acted as an auxiliary controller to enhance performance without compromising system robustness in the presence of connectivity loss. A similar setup was used in [64], which proposed a 5G-enabled, distributed edge-cloud architecture for mission-critical MPC execution. This system was evaluated primarily in terms of latency and resource utilization.

In [65], a UAV offloaded navigation support to a base station, which preloaded an environmental map to aid obstacle avoidance. While effective in static environments, this approach struggled with dynamic obstacles.

The proposed approach differs significantly by integrating dynamic obstacle consideration directly into the NMPC formulation, which stretches the criticality of maintaining time bounds of the NCS. The optimization problem adapts in real-time to the presence of moving obstacles, made feasible for resource-constrained platforms by offloading computation to a nearby edge cluster. Unlike [65], the proposed method is validated not only in simulation but through real-world experiments in uncontrolled environments.

The proposed framework incorporates a k8s-orchestrated, ROS-integrated control system where the NMPC solver runs entirely on the edge, ensuring bounded RTT delays and high control frequency. This enables resource-constrained UAVs to perform complex maneuvers safely and effectively, despite onboard limitations.

Table 2.4: Comparison of control offloading strategies in related work

Reference	Control Type	Offloading Target	Orchestration	Real-Time Capable	Evaluation
[56]	MPC	Edge	No	Partial	Real robots
[54]	Mixed	Edge/Cloud	Yes	No	Real robots
[53]	Monitoring	Cloud	Yes	No	Mobile robots
[63]	MPC (Assist)	Edge/Cloud	No	Yes	Simulation
[64]	MPC	Edge/Cloud	No	Yes	Simulation
[65]	Navigation assist	Edge/Base station	No	No	Simulation
This Work	NMPC	Edge	k8s	Yes	Real UAVs

This comparison highlights the distinct capabilities of this work’s architecture, particularly in addressing the challenges posed by dynamic obstacles, strict latency constraints, and operational deployment in real-world environments.

System Dynamics

This work utilizes the NMPC model proposed in [66], where the UAV is represented as a six Degrees-of-Freedom (DoF) system with a fixed body frame [67]. The body and world coordinate frames are denoted by \mathbb{B} and \mathbb{W} , respectively, as illustrated in Figure 2.5. The kinematic equations are described in Equation (2.2).

$$\ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) = \frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \mathbf{F}(t) + \mathbf{G} - \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \quad (2.2a)$$

$$\dot{q}_\phi(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_\phi} (K_\phi q_\phi^{\text{ref}}(t) - q_\phi(t)) \quad (2.2b)$$

$$\dot{q}_\theta(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_\theta} (K_\theta q_\theta^{\text{ref}}(t) - q_\theta(t)) \quad (2.2c)$$

The vector $\mathbf{p}(t) \triangleq [p_x(t) \ p_y(t) \ p_z(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ describes the position and the vector $\mathbf{q}(t) \triangleq [q_\phi(t) \ q_\theta(t) \ q_\psi(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ describes the orientation of the UAV. The parameter $m \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ represents the mass of the UAV. The matrices $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ are the rotation matrices relating to Euler angles, and $\mathbf{F}(t) \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ F_z(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^3$ represents the sum of thrust forces. These forces are dependent on the control inputs $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, which accounts for roll, pitch, and thrust, for the UAV. The vector $\mathbf{G} \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ -9.81]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes gravity, and $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ characterizes the drag coefficients. The desired reference inputs, $q_\phi^{\text{ref}}, q_\theta^{\text{ref}} \in [-\pi, \pi]$, are accompanied by time constants $\alpha_\phi, \alpha_\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ and proportional gains $K_\phi, K_\theta \in \mathbb{R}$.

The UAVs' controller employs a dual-loop structure: (i) the inner loop (LLC) governs attitude dynamics, while (ii) the outer loop regulates position dynamics. The inner loop must operate at a substantially higher frequency than the outer loop to generate the needed moments based on control inputs, so its control is executed on the onboard computer, minimizing processing and actuation latency. In contrast, due to its high computational demands, the outer loop control is offloaded to the edge k8s cluster. The outer loop controller's outputs include the thrust, T normalized for F_z , alongside the desired roll and pitch angles $q_\phi^{\text{ref}}, q_\theta^{\text{ref}}$. The UAVs' yaw (q_ψ) is consistently assumed to be zero, as the reference yaw input remains zero.

Figure 2.5: Crazyflie 2.0 on the coordinate frames, where \mathbb{W} and \mathbb{B} represent the global and body coordinate frames respectively.

Cost Function

The objective of the controllers is to formulate a function such that the control inputs \mathbf{u} ensure trajectories that avoid collisions and achieve the desired reference positions \mathbf{p}^{ref} . The state vector is defined as $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^\top \ \dot{\mathbf{p}}^\top \ q_\phi \ q_\theta]^\top$, and the control inputs are given by $\mathbf{u} \triangleq [q_\phi^{\text{ref}} \ q_\theta^{\text{ref}} \ T]^\top$, where $T \in [0, 1]$ denotes the thrust normalized by mass for the UAV. To discretize the system dynamics and extract the state evolution of the UAV, the forward Euler method is used with a sampling time T_s , as demonstrated in (2.3).

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \zeta(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \quad (2.3)$$

The controller evaluates the state evolution over a predetermined number of future time steps, represented by the prediction horizon (h), to optimize control inputs. The predicted state at the $(k+m)^{\text{th}}$ time step, computed at the k^{th} time step, is denoted by $\mathbf{x}_{k+m|k}$. Similarly, the control inputs are denoted as $\mathbf{u}_{k+m|k}$. The reference trajectory, \mathbf{x}^{ref} , is sampled throughout the prediction horizon to formulate the cost functions $J_c(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{u}_{k-1})$, for the controller as defined in (2.4).

$$\begin{aligned}
J_c = & \sum_{m=0}^h \left\{ \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{x}_{k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{x}_{k+m|k} \right)^\top \mathbf{Q}_x \left(\mathbf{x}_{k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{x}_{k+m|k} \right)}_{\text{State cost}} \right. \\
& + \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{u}_{k+m|k} - \mathbf{u}_{k+m-1|k} \right)^\top \mathbf{Q}_{\Delta u} \left(\mathbf{u}_{k+m|k} - \mathbf{u}_{k+m-1|k} \right)}_{\text{Smoothness cost}} \\
& \left. + \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{u}_{k+m|k} + \mathbf{G} \right)^\top \mathbf{Q}_u \left(\mathbf{u}_{k+m|k} + \mathbf{G} \right)}_{\text{Actuation cost}} \right\} \quad (2.4)
\end{aligned}$$

The cost function is designed to minimize state errors using the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{8 \times 8}$. Simultaneously, it ensures smooth control signals via the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_{\Delta u} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$, which helps in reducing fluctuations between successive control inputs. Furthermore, the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_u \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ keeps the control inputs near hovering mode. This function incorporates time delays and each robot's state in a centralized framework to generate collision-free paths, penalizing deviations from target positions.

The complexity of the control is determined by the prediction horizon (h), and the sampling time (T_s). Although the approach is robust, computational demands alters based on these parameters. However, this computational requirement is effectively managed by the monitored edge resources, facilitating controller execution and optimal solution generation.

Control Input Constraints

The optimization mechanism provides smooth and optimal control not only by the formulation of the cost function but also by applying input constraints. Thus, constraints are directly applied on the control inputs. Hard bounds on control inputs must be considered, as the thrust is limited by the motors and the attitude can only be stabilized within a certain range by the low-level attitude controller. Thus, bounds are defined on inputs as in Eq. 2.5.

$$\mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}_{k+m|k} \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max} \quad (2.5)$$

Furthermore, to ensure smooth system behavior and guarantee that the computed control inputs remain within desired bounds, control input constraints are implemented. These constraints ensure bounded values, as expressed in (2.6a)-(2.6d). In the following constraints, the function $[h_c]_+ = \max\{0, h_c\}$ is used to represent a constrained area. This formulation ensures that h_c takes on positive values when the constraint is violated and negative or zero when the constraint is satisfied.

$$\left[q_{\phi, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\phi, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\phi, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0 \quad (2.6a)$$

$$\left[q_{\phi, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\phi, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\phi, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0 \quad (2.6b)$$

$$\left[q_{\theta, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\theta, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\theta, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0 \quad (2.6c)$$

$$\left[q_{\theta, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\theta, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\theta, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0, \quad (2.6d)$$

where $\Delta q_{\phi, \text{max}}$ and $\Delta q_{\theta, \text{max}}$ denote the maximum permissible change in input per time step, and \mathbf{u}_{min} and \mathbf{u}_{max} represent the minimum and maximum allowable control input values constrained by the UAV's specifications.

Collision Avoidance Constraints

One critical constraint that is employed is obstacle avoidance, which is crucial for preventing collisions with environmental obstacles. To articulate this obstacle avoidance constraint more clearly, the constraint formulation used in [68, 69] to represent a set-exclusion constraint on the UAV position states, is applied, such that the constraint is satisfied if the UAV position lies outside a sphere centered on the obstacle position $\mathbf{p}^{\text{obs}} \triangleq [p_x^{\text{obs}} \ p_y^{\text{obs}} \ p_z^{\text{obs}}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ by (2.7).

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{sphere}}(\mathbf{p}_{k+m}, \mathbf{z}^{\text{obs}}) = & \left[(r_{\text{obs}} + r_{\text{safe}})^2 - (p_{x, k+m} - p_{x, k+m}^{\text{obs}})^2 \right. \\ & \left. - (p_{y, k+m} - p_{y, k+m}^{\text{obs}})^2 - (p_{z, k+m} - p_{z, k+m}^{\text{obs}})^2 \right]_+ = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where $\mathbf{z}^{\text{obs}} \triangleq [r_{\text{obs}} \ r_{\text{safe}} \ (\mathbf{p}^{\text{obs}})^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^5$. The obstacle positions \mathbf{p}^{obs} are the world-frame coordinates of the center of the sphere, at each time step k , and r_{obs} and r_{safe} are the radius of the obstacle, and an extra safety radius for the UAV, respectively. It is clear that if the constraint is satisfied, the evaluation of (2.7) is zero and can thus be stated as an equality constraint.

Incorporating the predictive aspect of NMPC, this constraint is extended to address $n_o \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ moving obstacles. To accomplish this, each future obstacle position $\mathbf{p}_{k+m}^{\text{obs}}$ is associated with a corresponding prediction model. In that approach, a projectile-motion model is employed, which allows forecasting the positions of obstacles based on initial measurements of their position \mathbf{p}^{obs} and velocity \mathbf{v}^{obs} states, represented as $\mathbf{x}^{\text{obs}} \triangleq [(\mathbf{p}^{\text{obs}})^\top \ (\dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}})^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^6$. The projectile-motion model, shown in equations (2.8), simulates the future states of the obstacle, assuming a constant gravitational acceleration $g = 9.81$.

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t) = \mathbf{v}^{\text{obs}}(t), \quad (2.8a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{v}}^{\text{obs}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -g \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.8b)$$

Each predicted obstacle position is associated with a corresponding predicted UAV state along the prediction horizon, effectively modeling the obstacle's motion with a projectile-motion assumption. This predictive approach enables the system to account for moving obstacles and adapt the UAV's trajectory to ensure collision avoidance.

Optimization

The NMPC problem is solved by the optimization engine and the Proximal Averaged Newton-type method for Optimal Control (PANOC) [68,70,71] algorithm, while an outer loop based on a penalty method is applied for the consideration of equality constraints [72]. The optimization engine solves general optimization problems subject to equality constraints as described in 2.9.

While considering real-time control or demanding computational demands, alternative optimization algorithms for efficiency in solving similar problems can be explored. In the proposed framework, the objective is to attain an optimized solution while meeting the requirement for a relatively real-time response. These two factors prompt a trade-off that should be considered when selecting and tuning an optimization method. Interior-point methods [73], sequential quadratic programming [74], or gradient-based approaches [75] may be suitable alternatives. The adaptability of the optimization algorithm underscores the versatility of the architecture, allowing it to be fine-tuned to the unique demands of different missions and UAV applications.

Furthermore, the advantage of the proposed architecture lies in its distinction and distribution of processes into pods and its optimization-agnostic behavior. Any optimization technique can be easily applied without the need for significant changes to the framework, provided that the time and computational criteria are respected. This flexibility empowers the architecture to employ a wide range of mission-specific requirements and allows for the integration of evolving optimization techniques without incurring substantial architectural modifications.

The resulting problem from the developed model, cost function, and constraints is expressed in (2.9).

$$\underset{\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{x}_k}{\text{Minimize}} J_c(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k; \mathbf{u}_{k-1|k}) \quad (2.9a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t.: } \mathbf{x}_{k+m+1|k} &= \zeta(\mathbf{x}_{k+m|k}, \mathbf{u}_{k+m|k}) \\ m &= 0, \dots, h-1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.9b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{\min} &\leq \mathbf{u}_{k+m|k} \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max} \\ m &= 0, \dots, h \end{aligned} \quad (2.9c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Constraints (2.6a) - (2.6d)} \\ m &= 0, \dots, h \end{aligned} \quad (2.9d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{sphere}}^o(\mathbf{p}_{k+m}, \mathbf{z}^{\text{obs}}) &= 0 \\ m &= 0, \dots, h, \quad o = 1, \dots, n_o \end{aligned} \quad (2.9e)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{k|k} = \mathbf{x}_k \quad (2.9f)$$

Stability Analysis

To ensure the system's stability a maximum allowable delay τ_{\max} must be defined, so that (2.10) holds. Regardless of controlling the trajectories of a single robot or MAS, it is essential to ensure that each robot meets the system's stability requirements, as discussed in our published work [29].

$$\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \leq \tau_{\max} \quad (2.10)$$

So, let's consider a single-robot (UAV) closed-loop system and analyzing its stability to determine τ_{\max} .

The first step involves linearizing the UAV model around its reference trajectory. To achieve this, a linear approximation of the system around an equilibrium point must be found, which represents the desired state where all time derivatives are zero. For simplicity, the UAV is assumed to follow the reference path defined in (2.11), that used in the experimental analysis.

$$\mathbf{p}^{\text{ref}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} r_{\text{trj}} \cos(\omega t) \\ r_{\text{trj}} \sin(\omega t) \\ h_{\text{trj}} \end{bmatrix} \quad \dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{ref}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -r_{\text{trj}} \sin(\omega t) \\ r_{\text{trj}} \cos(\omega t) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.11)$$

The reference path corresponds to a desired circular trajectory with a radius denoted by r_{trj} and an altitude of h_{trj} . The parameter ω represents the angular velocity of the circular trajectory.

For this circular trajectory, let's now assume that the UAV achieves an equilibrium point where it flies straight and level at a constant altitude, for small consecutive intervals, with fixed thrust and attitude commands, as expressed in (2.12).

$$\mathbf{p}^{\text{eq}} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{\text{trj}} \\ 0 \\ h_{\text{trj}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{eq}} = \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1},$$

$$q_{\phi}^{\text{eq}} = 0, \quad q_{\theta}^{\text{eq}} = 0 \quad (2.12)$$

At this equilibrium point, \mathbf{p}^{eq} represents the UAV's position at $t = 0$ on the circular trajectory, while $\dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{eq}}$ denotes the linear velocity, which is assumed to be zero due to the straight and level flight condition. The variables q_{ϕ}^{eq} and q_{θ}^{eq} represent the roll and pitch angles (with no angular velocities), and T^{eq} denotes the thrust at the equilibrium point.

Let's assume the linearized system with the state vector $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^{\top} \quad \dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\top} \quad q_{\phi} \quad q_{\theta}]^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^8$, and the control input vector is $\mathbf{u}_1 \triangleq [q_{\phi}^{\text{ref}} \quad q_{\theta}^{\text{ref}} \quad T]^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, so that the system expressed can be defined in the linearized states (2.13).

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_1(t) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) = \mathbf{x}_2(t) \quad (2.13a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_2(t) = \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \quad (2.13b)$$

$$\dot{x}_3(t) = \dot{q}_{\phi}(t) \quad (2.13c)$$

$$\dot{x}_4(t) = \dot{q}_{\theta}(t) \quad (2.13d)$$

To linearize the system and represent it in state-space form, the Jacobians of the state equations are defined, using the equilibrium values specified in (2.14), similarly to [67].

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta p} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta \dot{p}} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{I}^{3 \times 3}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\phi} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\theta} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta p} \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta \dot{p}} \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= -\mathbf{A}_{\text{diag}}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\phi} \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\phi), & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\theta} \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\theta), \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta u} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta u} \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) &= \mathbf{J}_{\ddot{\mathbf{p}}}(\mathbf{u}), \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta p} \dot{q}_\phi(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta \dot{p}} \dot{q}_\phi(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\phi} \dot{q}_\phi(t) &= -\frac{1}{\alpha_\phi}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\theta} \dot{q}_\phi(t) &= 0, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta p} \dot{q}_\theta(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3}, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta \dot{p}} \dot{q}_\theta(t) &= \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\phi} \dot{q}_\theta(t) &= 0, & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta q_\theta} \dot{q}_\theta(t) &= -\frac{1}{\alpha_\theta}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \delta u} \dot{q}_\phi(t) &= \mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\phi}(\mathbf{u}), & \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta u} \dot{q}_\theta(t) &= \mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\theta}(\mathbf{u}),
\end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

where $\mathbf{I}^{3 \times 3}$ stands for the identity matrix, and $\mathbf{A}_{\text{diag}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ denotes the diagonal matrix containing the damping constants A_x, A_y, A_z . The terms $\mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\phi) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ refer to the angular velocity Jacobians corresponding to the angles q_ϕ and q_θ . Lastly, $\mathbf{J}_{\ddot{\mathbf{p}}}(\mathbf{u}) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and $\mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\phi}(\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\theta}(\mathbf{u}) \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 3}$ represents the control input Jacobians.

The linearized system can be represented in the state-space form, as shown in (2.15). To analyze the stability of the time-delay system, the methodology presented in [76] is followed, which provides a comprehensive framework for delay-dependent and delay-independent stability analysis. In particular, the Lyapunov–Krasovskii functional approach is applied to establish sufficient conditions under which the linearized closed-loop system remains asymptotically stable despite the presence of delays introduced by the edge offloading architecture.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \\ \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \\ \dot{q}_\phi(t) \\ \dot{q}_\theta(t) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}(t) - \mathbf{p}^{eq} \\ \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) - \dot{\mathbf{p}}^{eq} \\ q_\phi(t) - q_\phi^{eq} \\ q_\theta(t) - q_\theta^{eq} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{B} \begin{bmatrix} q_\phi^{ref}(t) - q_\phi^{eq} \\ q_\theta^{ref}(t) - q_\theta^{eq} \\ T(t) - T^{eq} \end{bmatrix} \tag{2.15}$$

By combining the Jacobian matrices from (2.14) with the state-space model in (2.15), the \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , and \mathbf{C} state-space matrices are derived.

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{I}^{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1} & \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1} \\ \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3} & -\mathbf{A}_{\text{diag}} & \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\phi) & \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\theta) \\ \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & -\frac{1}{\alpha_\phi} & 0 \\ \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\alpha_\theta} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} g \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(q_\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -g \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(\mathbf{u}) \\ \mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\phi}(\mathbf{u}) \\ \mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\theta}(\mathbf{u}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(\mathbf{u}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\phi}(\mathbf{u}) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{K_\phi}{\alpha_\phi} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{J}_{\dot{q}_\theta}(\mathbf{u}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{K_\theta}{\alpha_\theta} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}^{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1} & \mathbf{0}^{3 \times 1} \\ \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & 0 & 0 \\ \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & \mathbf{0}^{1 \times 3} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Consequently, (2.15) can be expressed in state-space form as $\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(t)$ and $\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t)$, where the system output is defined as the UAV's position.

Given the transmission delays, the state signal \mathbf{x} is subject to a delay of τ_u (UL), while the control signal \mathbf{u} encounters a delay of τ_d (DL). In addition, the system experiences the inherited processing delays τ_p . As a result, ensuring the stability of the closed-loop system, from the networking perspective, is equal to addressing the stability concerns of a NCS. The control law from [77] is considered, and defined as $\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{K}\mathbf{y}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}})$, where $\mathbf{y}(t)$ denotes the system's output. The complete state-space representation of the closed-loop control system is given by (2.16).

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{K}\mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}) \quad (2.16a)$$

$$= \mathbf{A}_c\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{A}_d\mathbf{x}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}) \quad (2.16b)$$

To determine the upper maximum allowable delay, τ_{max} , it is necessary to solve the set of Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMIs) optimizations outlined in (2.17).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{11} & \mathbf{A}_{12} & \mathbf{A}_{13} \\ \mathbf{A}_{21} & \mathbf{A}_{22} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{31} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A}_{33} \end{bmatrix} < \mathbf{0}, \quad (2.17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{A}_{11} &= \mathbf{A}_{cd}\mathbf{Q}_1 + \mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{A}_{cd}^\top + \tau_{rtt}\mathbf{A}_d(\mathbf{Q}_2 + \mathbf{Q}_3)\mathbf{A}_d^\top \\
\mathbf{A}_{cd} &= \mathbf{A}_c + \mathbf{A}_d \\
\mathbf{A}_{12} &= \tau_{rtt}\mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{A}_c^\top \\
\mathbf{A}_{13} &= \tau_{rtt}\mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{A}_d^\top \\
\mathbf{A}_{21} &= \tau_{rtt}\mathbf{A}_c\mathbf{Q}_1 \\
\mathbf{A}_{22} &= -\tau_{rtt}\mathbf{Q}_2 \\
\mathbf{A}_{31} &= \tau_{rtt}\mathbf{A}_d\mathbf{Q}_1 \\
\mathbf{A}_{33} &= -\tau_{rtt}\mathbf{Q}_3 \\
\mathbf{Q}_i &> \mathbf{0}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3
\end{aligned}$$

Using the LMI in (2.17), the maximum permissible delay $\tau_{\max} \forall \mathbf{K}$ is determined within the range $[\mathbf{K}_{\min}, \mathbf{K}_{\max}]$ to ensure system stability, as illustrated in Fig. 2.6. This information defines the design of the control architecture. \mathbf{K}_{\min} and \mathbf{K}_{\max} have been extracted from the NMPC empirically, considering the control law 2.16, and NMPC as a black box.

Figure 2.6: Maximum allowable delay $\tau_{\max} \forall \mathbf{K} \in [\mathbf{K}_{\min}, \mathbf{K}_{\max}]$.

Execution Rate

The execution rate of the NMPC controller determines how frequently control commands are generated. A higher execution rate leads to faster command updates, which is essential for agile control, particularly in aerial robotic systems. In edge-controlled systems, this becomes even more critical due to the presence of RTT communication and processing delays.

The total RTT consists of two main components: the execution time of the NMPC at the edge, denoted by τ_p , and the communication delay between the UAV and the edge cluster, denoted by τ_u for the UL, and τ_d for the DL delays, respectively. These delays cause a temporal mismatch between the UAV's state used for computing the control input and the state at which the control input is executed. This mismatch can degrade trajectory tracking accuracy or, in extreme cases, destabilize the system.

Increasing the execution rate helps mitigate this issue by reducing the interval between command computations, thus reducing τ_p . However, a higher rate imposes a greater computational burden on the processing unit. While onboard UAV processors are often limited to rates around 20 Hz, the edge-based framework enables rates up to 100 Hz. This capability is explored and evaluated in Section 2.4.2.

Prediction Horizon

The prediction horizon defines the number of future time steps considered in the optimization problem. A longer prediction horizon allows the controller to better anticipate future system behavior, which can be particularly useful in dynamic or cluttered environments. However, extending the prediction horizon significantly increases the computational complexity of the optimization problem, as the number of decision variables and constraints grows.

While longer horizons generally lead to smoother and more accurate control trajectories, they also demand more computational resources. This poses a challenge for onboard control, especially on resource-constrained UAV platforms. By leveraging edge computing, the prediction horizon is able to increase without compromising the control rate or stability. The effects of different prediction horizon lengths are evaluated in Section 2.4.2.

Computational Processing

The ability to offload the computational burden of NMPC to the edge introduces significant flexibility in algorithm design. Traditionally, computational limits on embedded platforms constrained the use of complex control schemes, forcing developers to use short prediction horizons or low update rates. The flexibility in resource allocation, combined with the separation of control logic into containerized services, ensures that control loop timing remains stable even under varying system loads, as validated in our published work [25].

In the proposed architecture, the control computation is executed on a k8s-managed edge cluster, which allows for dynamically resource allocation such as CPU and memory to each control pod. This enables the system to handle heavier optimization loads while maintaining bounded execution times. Furthermore, the modularity of the architecture supports easy reconfiguration to adapt to varying mission needs or system constraints.

2.4.2 Evaluation & Results

A comprehensive evaluation of the proposed edge-offloaded NMPC framework is conducted through a combination of simulation-based and experimental tests. The objective is to assess the system’s performance in terms of trajectory tracking accuracy, latency characteristics, control frequency scalability, and computational resource utilization. The evaluation is divided into three parts: (i) the first part focuses on simulation-based validation; (ii) the second part presents experimental results from laboratory environments, and (iii) the third part demonstrates the proposed architecture in a real-world active industrial setup.

Simulation-Based Evaluation

To validate the proposed edge-offloaded NMPC framework, a comprehensive set of simulation tests is performed. These tests aimed to evaluate latency performance, trajectory tracking accuracy, and computational resource usage under varying control configurations, including different MPC prediction horizons and execution rates.

Simulation Setup: Simulations were conducted using the `Gazebo` environment, integrated with `ROS` for message passing and real-time control. The UAV model was either a custom quadrotor model or the `Hummingbird` platform from the `RotorS` simulator [78]. The NMPC controller ran on an edge cluster located in the edge of the network. Two edge orchestration approaches were used: one based on standalone `Docker` containers configuration and another based on a `k8s` cluster, as presented in our published work [27].

Control commands were generated at rates up to 100 Hz and communicated to the UAV over the UDP tunnel. Multiple flight scenarios were tested, including circular, vertically helical, and inverted conical spiral trajectories. System behavior was visualized in 3D and evaluated using `MATLAB` to extract and analyze time-series performance metrics.

Effect of Prediction Horizon and MPC Rate: To investigate the effects of control configuration parameters, the MPC prediction horizon is selected to vary from 20 to 100 steps and evaluated processing delays. Figure 2.7 and Table 2.5 illustrate the latency distributions across different horizon values while maintaining a fixed control rate of 40 Hz. Results indicate that although median latency remains stable, the variance increases with larger horizons due to computational complexity.

Table 2.5: Latency in milliseconds for varying horizon step values and fixed MPC rate value at 40 Hz

Horizon Steps	20	40	60	80	100
Minimum	21.518	14.583	10.647	12.691	12.362
Lower Adjacent	49.348	49.158	48.582	48.054	47.217
25 th Percentile	49.843	49.785	49.642	49.511	49.363
Median	50.002	49.998	50.008	50.010	50.033
75 th Percentile	50.175	50.208	50.349	50.492	50.796
Upper Adjacent	50.658	50.840	51.397	51.946	52.927
Maximum	86.705	83.665	82.910	86.629	82.007

Figure 2.7: Frequency distribution for different MPC horizon step values.

Similarly, Figure 2.8 and Table 2.6 show that increasing the MPC execution rate leads to significantly lower processing delay values. This demonstrates that offloading control to the edge enables faster controller execution without sacrificing responsiveness, which is essential for tasks such as collision avoidance.

Table 2.6: Latency in milliseconds for varying MPC rate values and fixed horizon step value of 20 steps

MPC Rates	20	40	60	80	100
Minimum	14.583	4.878	4.931	3.003	3.062
Lower Adjacent	49.158	24.071	15.847	11.933	9.463
25 th Percentile	49.785	24.768	16.465	12.359	9.869
Median	49.998	25.006	16.682	12.503	10.000
75 th Percentile	50.208	25.240	16.868	12.650	10.141
Upper Adjacent	50.840	25.939	17.464	13.080	10.545
Maximum	83.665	42.261	25.299	30.854	19.809

Figure 2.8: Frequency distribution for different MPC rate values.

Trajectory Tracking Performance: The tracking performance for the circular, vertically helical, and inverted conical spiral trajectories is shown in Figures 2.9 through 2.14. In all scenarios, the UAV model closely follows the reference path with Euclidean distance error $e_{\text{trj}}(t)$ consistently tracking a pre-defined threshold $e_{\text{trj}}^{\text{thr}}$, which is within the designed tolerance margin. The controller is designed to ensure that the error satisfies (2.18).

$$e_{\text{trj}}(t) \leq e_{\text{trj}}^{\text{thr}}, \quad (2.18)$$

where the error $e_{\text{trj}}(t)$ is defined as:

$$e_{\text{trj}}(t) = \sqrt{(p_x(t) - p_x^{\text{ref}}(t))^2 + (p_y(t) - p_y^{\text{ref}}(t))^2 + (p_z(t) - p_z^{\text{ref}}(t))^2},$$

and the $\mathbf{p}^{\text{ref}}(t)$ is updated by the controller every time the Euclidean distance error falls under the threshold $e_{\text{trj}}^{\text{thr}}$, given by (2.19).

$$e_{\text{trj}}^{\text{thr}} = \sqrt{(p_x^{\text{thr}})^2 + (p_y^{\text{thr}})^2 + (p_z^{\text{thr}})^2}, \quad (2.19)$$

where $\mathbf{p}^{\text{thr}} \triangleq [p_x^{\text{thr}} \quad p_y^{\text{thr}} \quad p_z^{\text{thr}}]$ are constant design parameters defining the axis-wise positional tolerances.

Figures 2.9–2.11 illustrate the 3D trajectory trackings, while Figures 2.12–2.14 provide the corresponding Euclidean distance error profiles over time.

Figure 2.9: Trajectory tracking by a simulated UAV for the circular path.

Figure 2.10: Trajectory tracking by a simulated UAV for the vertically helical path.

Figure 2.11: Trajectory tracking by a simulated UAV for the inverted conical spiral path.

Figure 2.12: Euclidean distance error for the circular path.

Figure 2.13: Euclidean distance error for the vertically helical path.

Typical processing delay profiles for the test missions are illustrated in Figure 2.15 as frequency distributions plotted on a logarithmic scale. The results demonstrate that the RTT remains consistent and bounded within the expected range, corresponding to the configured 20 Hz control rate and 20-step prediction horizon. This confirms that the system is capable of maintaining real-time responsiveness under these control parameters, which are representative of what is feasible on UAVs with moderate computational constraints.

Figure 2.14: Euclidean distance error for the inverted conical spiral path.

Figure 2.15: Processing delay profiles for the circular trajectory.

High-Frequency Control: In a separate test scenario, the control rate and horizon are increased to 100 Hz and 100 steps, respectively, ranges that could pose computational burden on UAV onboard processors, exploiting the computational capabilities of the edge cluster.

The UAV followed again circular, vertically helical, and inverted conical spiral trajectories. Figures 2.16–2.18 present a detailed breakdown of the delay components, including UL, processing, and DL delays, for the inverted conical spiral trajectory. The results demonstrate that the edge-based control framework consistently sustains real-time performance across all flight patterns, even under high-load settings. The outcome of these delay profiles confirms the robustness of the architecture in maintaining bounded RTT behavior, ensuring reliable closed-loop control.

Figure 2.16: UL delay profile τ_u for the inverted conical spiral trajectory.

Figure 2.17: Processing delay profile τ_p for the inverted conical spiral trajectory.

Figure 2.18: DL delay profile τ_d for the inverted conical spiral trajectory.

The average measured delays were 8.9 ms for UL, 14.1 ms for MPC execution, and 16.1 ms for DL. These values remain well within the control requirements, as the resulting RTT remains significantly below the maximum allowable delay defined in Section 2.4.1, even when considering the maximum observed values.

Resource Utilization: To evaluate the computational efficiency and orchestration performance of the edge-based deployment, simulations were conducted using both `Docker`-based and `k8s`-based architectures. In both configurations, CPU resource usage was monitored to assess the runtime demands of the NMPC controller. As shown in Figures 2.19 and 2.20, the average CPU utilization was approximately $\sim 10.0\%$ for the `Docker`-based setup and $\sim 24\%$ for the `k8s`-based setup.

While the `k8s` configuration introduces higher overhead due to its container orchestration, resource management, and continuous monitoring services, it also provides significantly enhanced fault tolerance, scalability, and deployment flexibility. These capabilities stem from `k8s`' native features such as automated pod rescheduling, load balancing across nodes, rolling updates with rollback capabilities, and dynamic resource allocation, which are utilized throughout this thesis. Therefore, despite its higher resource footprint, the `k8s`-based architecture is well-aligned with the demands of real-world autonomous systems where robustness, modularity, and scalability are essential.

Figures 2.19 and 2.20 present a detailed breakdown of CPU usage during the inverted conical spiral trajectories, executed under the two architectures. On average, for the `k8s` architecture, user-space utilization (us) measured at $\sim 19\%$, while kernel-space utilization (sy) laid at $\sim 5\%$. For the `Docker`-based architecture, us and sy averaged at $\sim 9\%$ and $\sim 1\%$, respectively. These values confirm that the edge cluster can accommodate the computational demands of high-rate NMPC execution without saturating system resources. Such performance would be infeasible on many UAV onboard processors, which lack the processing power to manage high-frequency optimization workloads alongside real-time communication and sensing.

Figure 2.19: Resource utilization for the Docker-based architecture.

Figure 2.20: Resource utilization for the k8s-based architecture.

In summary, the simulation results demonstrate that the proposed edge-offloaded NMPC framework achieves robust real-time control performance across a range of trajectories and control configurations. The edge infrastructure enables aggressive tuning of the control rate and prediction horizon while maintaining latency within allowable bounds and ensuring efficient resource use. These capabilities position the architecture as a strong candidate for time-critical UAV missions requiring high-performance model-based control.

Laboratory Experimental Evaluation

To complement the simulation-based analysis, a series of laboratory experiments were conducted using the *Crazyflie 2.0* MAV platform shown in Figure 2.21, and published in [28]. These experiments aimed to evaluate the real-world applicability of the proposed edge-offloaded NMPC architecture, including its ability to track trajectories with minimal latency and respond effectively to dynamic obstacles.

Experimental Setup: The *Crazyflie 2.0* MAV was selected due to its minimal on-board computational capabilities, making it an ideal platform for validating the necessity of offloading control to the edge. The MAV was operated within a *Vicon* Motion Capture System (MoCap) for precise localization, while control signals were generated on an edge-based k8s cluster hosted in Luleå, Sweden. Communication between the MAV and the edge occurred over a local Wi-Fi network.

Figure 2.21: *Crazyflie 2.0* along with the global and body coordinate frames, and the MAV motor rotation notations.

Trajectory Tracking with Variable MPC Parameters: A comprehensive analysis of NMPC configurations was tested, varying both the prediction horizon (20–100 steps) and the execution rate (20–100 Hz). Figure 2.22 show the 3D trajectory responses for various combinations of these parameters. The results indicate that increasing the prediction horizon reduces overshoot, particularly evident in the Z-axis, due to improved predictive behavior.

Tracking accuracy was evaluated through the Euclidean distance error between the reference trajectory and the MAV's actual position. As shown in Figure 2.23, the error per axis, consistently remained below the defined tolerance. This confirms the effectiveness of the off-loaded NMPC controller in achieving smooth and reliable tracking.

Figure 2.22: Trajectory responses for circular flights with varying number of prediction horizon and execution rate.

Figure 2.23: Distance error per axis for the test case of prediction horizon of 100 steps and execution rate of 20 Hz.

Processing delay measurements for each MPC rate were collected and are shown in Figure 2.24. As depicted, increasing the MPC execution rate systematically reduced the processing delay per control cycle. This behavior reflects the low-latency characteristics and high computational capacity of the local edge cluster, which effectively mitigates the additional overhead introduced by higher control frequencies. Such performance highlights the ability of the edge infrastructure to sustain real-time NMPC execution even under demanding parameter configurations.

Figure 2.24: Processing delay τ_p measurements for prediction horizon of 100 steps and for varying execution rate.

Obstacle Avoidance Evaluation: Additional experiments published in [29], involved obstacle avoidance, introducing dynamic objects into the MAV’s flight path, as illustrated in Figure 2.25. At low NMPC rates and horizons (20 Hz, 20 steps), the controller failed to react in time to avoid collisions, as visualized in Figures 2.26 and 2.27. Increasing the controller parameters improved responsiveness but also increased computational load.

Figure 2.25: MAV trajectory and collision avoidance concept based on edge-offloaded control.

Figure 2.26: Instance of MAV collision with a dynamic obstacle from three different angles. The selected value for the horizon is 20 steps, and for the execution rate is 20 Hz, and edge resources were utilized.

To investigate the effect of limited computational resources, a k8s pod was configured to emulate the Raspberry Pi Model B. Under this constraint, the system failed to generate control actions within desired time bounds, with collisions occurring at the 17th second, despite otherwise favorable control settings (100 Hz, 100 steps), as shown in Figures 2.28 and 2.29.

Figure 2.27: Euclidean distance between the MAV and the obstacle (green line) and between the MAV and the reference points (red line). Collision occurred at the 55th second, when 20 steps, and 20 Hz were selected for horizon and execution rate, respectively, and edge resources were utilized.

Figure 2.28: Instance of MAV collision with a dynamic obstacle from three different angles. The selected value for the horizon is 100 steps, and for the execution rate is 100 Hz, and Raspberry Pi Model B resources were utilized.

Table 2.7: Initialization times of the optimization problem for varying prediction horizon

Horizon	Files Size	Raspberry	Edge
20 steps	301 MB	16 s	10 s
40 steps	309 MB	143 s	17 s
60 steps	322 MB	177 s	28 s
80 steps	340 MB	476 s	46 s
100 steps	380 MB	1278 s	69 s

By contrast, when nominal edge resources were allocated, the MAV consistently avoided obstacles, deviating from the reference trajectory when necessary and returning afterward, as seen in Figures 2.30–2.31. Control signals remained bounded and smooth, satisfying system constraints (Figure 2.32).

Edge Resource Usage and Constraints: Table 2.7 provides initialization times for the optimization problem at various prediction horizons. Edge-based execution consistently outperforms low-resource hardware such as a Raspberry Pi, reinforcing the importance of hardware selection in edge-robotic systems.

Figure 2.29: Euclidean distance between the MAV and the obstacle (green line) and between the MAV and the reference points (red line). Collision occurred at the 17th second, when 100 steps, and 100 Hz were selected for horizon and execution rate, respectively, and Raspberry Pi Model B resources were utilized.

Figure 2.30: Instance of MAV collision avoidance with a dynamic obstacle from three different angles. The selected value for the horizon is 100 steps, and for the execution rate is 100 Hz, and edge resources were utilized.

Delay Analysis and Stability Assurance: UL, DL and processing time delays were analyzed across all trials. Figure 2.33 presents the aggregated RTT delay under maximum, mean, and minimum conditions. As summarized in Table 2.8, the maxim observed and the mean RTT which was approximately 38.6 ms, well below the allowable stability threshold $\tau_{\max} = 0.274$ s determined in Section 2.4.1 for gains $K \in [3, 20]$, which are the possible deviation gains of the MPC, based on the optimization output.

Table 2.8: Maximum, minimum and average observed RTT

Delays	Maximum	Average	Minimum
UL and DL delays ($\tau_u + \tau_d$)	258.3 ms	27.2 ms	9 ms
Processing delays (τ_p)	44.8 ms	11.4 ms	3.6 ms
RTT (τ_{rtt})	267.9 ms	38.6 ms	15.4 ms
Maximum allowable delay (τ_{\max})		274 ms	

Figure 2.31: Euclidean distance between the MAV and the obstacle (green line) and between the MAV and the reference points (red line) when 100 steps, and 100 Hz were selected for horizon and execution rate, respectively, and edge resources were utilized.

Figure 2.32: Control signals thrust (top left), roll (top right), pitch (bottom left), and yaw (bottom right) over the duration of a mission.

The laboratory experiments validate the edge-offloaded NMPC framework in laboratory conditions. The architecture enables real-time control of computationally limited UAVs, supports complex control policies like collision avoidance, and demonstrates resilience to timing variations and network-induced delays. These findings underscore the practical value of edge computing for enhancing robotic autonomy in constrained environments.

Figure 2.33: Observed maximum, minimum and average RTT.

Real-World Deployment in 5G-Connected Industrial Environment

To validate the real-time capabilities and robustness of the proposed edge-offloaded NMPC framework under real-world conditions, a series of field experiments were conducted in an active underground mining site in northern Sweden, shown in Figure 2.34. This deployment represented the final stage in a multi-phase evaluation process and incorporated an industrial-grade 5G NR SA infrastructure and on-site edge computing cluster.

Figure 2.34: Experimental setup including the edge cluster, the mining site and the 5G-connected aerial robot.

System Setup and Integration: The system consisted of three core components: (i) a private 5G NR SA cellular network deployed on-site to ensure low-latency, high-throughput communication; (ii) a multi-node k8s-based edge cluster deployed locally and managed via Rancher Kubernetes Engine (RKE), depicted in Figure 2.34, and (iii) a 5G-enabled UAV platform equipped with onboard sensing and computing capabilities.

The aerial platform (Figure 2.35) featured a custom-made multirotor UAV equipped with an Ouster LiDAR for onboard sensing and a Sierra Wireless 5G modem (EM9293) with multi-antenna support to ensure robust connectivity. A lightweight companion computer (Intel NUC running Ubuntu and ROS) was used for basic on-robot processing and for maintaining a persistent 5G link to the edge. Cellular modem connectivity and management are handled by the ModemManager package in Linux, while Access Point Name (APN) configuration and connection management are managed via the NetworkManager package.

Figure 2.35: Utilized aerial platform equipped with 5G setup.

On the infrastructure side, the 5G installation included macro and micro base stations operating in the 3.5 GHz band (n78), and 100 MHz BW, tailored for tunnel-like environments using high-directivity antennas and two-sector configurations to ensure coverage continuity. Edge servers were housed above ground and connected to underground Remote Radio Units (RRUs) via optical fiber, which in turn are linked to a centralized Base Band Unit (BBU), also located underground, ensuring minimal backbone latency.

Edge-Controlled Architecture and Deployment: The k8s edge cluster hosted the NMPC controller in containerized form, deployed in dedicated pods with pre-configured Node Ports and namespaces. The communication between the UAV and the edge controller was handled via UDP to minimize latency, and telemetry/control data was streamed in real time. The containerized nature of the system allowed for flexible resource allocation and fault isolation within the k8s cluster, ensuring operational reliability even in high-demand conditions.

The NMPC was executed within the containerized pod at rates and prediction horizons selected according to earlier simulation and lab-based findings. The control loop was closed through 5G NR SA communication, leveraging the dedicated low-latency slice provisioned for the robotic system. This configuration enabled reliable end-to-end control performance even in the challenging subterranean environment, demonstrating the robustness of the architecture under real-world industrial conditions.

Experimental Procedure and Results: During the experiments, a human operator connected to the edge system and defined a sequence of waypoints. These reference points were streamed to the controller, which computed control inputs onboard the edge and transmitted them back to the UAV in real-time. Figure 2.36 shows the UAV trajectory compared to the human-defined references, highlighting the accurate waypoint tracking behavior.

Figure 2.36: UAV's real trajectory and reference waypoints in the x , y , and z planes.

Table 2.9 summarizes the 5G radio parameters measured during operation, indicating acceptable Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) as well as Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) levels for robust control. UL and DL Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) values were recorded across four spatially distributed antennas to ensure 3D coverage.

Table 2.9: 5G network specifications & measurements

Parameter	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
Band	n78	
BW	100 MHz	
RSRP	-100 dBm	-83 dBm
SINR	12.5 dB	27.0 dB
EU TX Power	13.0 dBm	23.0 dBm
RSSI Ant 0	-72.3 dBm	-43.3 dBm
RSSI Ant 1	-71.9 dBm	-45.3 dBm
RSSI Ant 2	-73.8 dBm	-55.9 dBm
RSSI Ant 3	-69.1 dBm	-49.1 dBm

To assess network-level performance, passive monitoring tools (Qosium) were used to measure communication delay, jitter, and throughput. Figures 2.37–2.38 show the raw and drift-corrected network delay across both directions. UL delays ranged from 5 ms to 34 ms and DL delays from 3 ms to 27 ms, while the corrected average values were 9.5 ms (UL) and 6.5 ms (DL). These are well within the maximum allowable delay τ_{\max} for closed-loop stability, as established in Section 2.4.1.

Figure 2.37: Maximum network delay for DL (blue) and UL (green) channels.

Figure 2.38: Drift-corrected delay for DL (blue) and UL (green) channels.

Additionally, network jitter values (Figure 2.39) remained under 11 ms in all cases. Average traffic rates were recorded at 2.1 Mbps (UL) and 0.1 Mbps (DL), confirming that the communication demands of the NMPC loop are modest relative to 5G capacity.

Figure 2.39: Network jitter for DL (blue) and UL (green) channels.

The results of this field deployment confirm that the proposed architecture performs reliably in complex, resource-constrained, and latency-sensitive environments. The 5G NR SA network provided adequate coverage and low-latency communication, while the k8s-based edge cluster enabled high-frequency NMPC execution with dynamic resource allocation. Combined, these technologies offer a viable pathway for enabling autonomous aerial robots to operate in industrial settings with closed-loop control safely offloaded to edge infrastructure.

2.5 Machine Learning Offloading

In addition to control offloading, ML tasks such as perception and object detection are often too computationally intensive to run onboard MAV. Edge computing provides an effective solution by enabling these tasks to be offloaded to nearby servers while maintaining low-latency communication.

Several recent works have demonstrated the feasibility and benefits of ML offloading in robotic systems. In [46], a lightweight object recognition algorithm based on You Look Less than Once (YLLO) was executed on an edge node to support traffic area monitoring, preserving accuracy while minimizing data transmission. Similarly, [47] used edge computing to support real-time object identification and classification via the You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm for multiple aerial and mobile robots. Edge computing provided the necessary computational resources, while ROS handled communication.

Edge-based ML processing has also been applied to other tasks such as LiDAR data processing using Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) for improved odometry [48], Deep Learning (DL)-based UAV path planning [79], and cloud-assisted grasp planning [80]. Additionally, [81] explored cloud-edge teleoperation and visual recognition for dynamic self-balancing robots.

While end-to-end Neural Network (NN) control schemes have presented promising results [82], the presented work emphasizes model-based control for safety and interpretability. NN are used for perception and detection tasks, but not as the main control strategy. This modular separation ensures that the safety-critical control system remains explainable and predictable, while still leveraging ML for tasks like object detection and localization.

The framework, published in [30], is designed to support such hybrid deployments, where ML modules for perception are offloaded to a k8s edge cluster, while real-time control is handled separately using CBFs. This architecture allows the UAV to process vision-based cues in real-time, detect target objects, and update its control policy accordingly without overloading onboard hardware.

2.5.1 Machine Learning Offloading for Vision-Based Target Detection

This section presents the integration of ML modules within the edge-based architecture described in previous sections. The developed framework supports hybrid deployments, wherein real-time control is performed onboard the robot through CBFs, while perception and scene understanding, specifically object detection and localization, are offloaded to a k8s edge cluster. This design enables robust visual processing on resource-constrained UAVs by offloading computationally intensive ML tasks while maintaining safety and responsiveness at the control layer for precise Aerial Physical Interaction (APhI), as visualized in Figure 2.40.

Architecture Overview

Figure 2.41 illustrates the complete architecture for ML offloading. The aerial platform transmits camera data via a UDP tunnel to the edge cluster. Within the cluster, containerized ML modules perform target detection and localization using a trained convolutional NN (YOLO).

Figure 2.40: Schematic of the boundary of the CBFs, which guides the aerial platform's trajectory to reach the target precisely.

The detected position of the target $\mathbf{p}^{\text{trg}}(t) \triangleq [p_x^{\text{trg}}(t) \ p_y^{\text{trg}}(t) \ p_z^{\text{trg}}(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is then sent back to the UAV for integration with the control pipeline. To ensure temporal relevance, the system incorporates a filtering mechanism that discards outdated detections when the RTT delay exceeds a stability threshold τ_{max} , as expressed by (2.20). This delay-aware mechanism ensures that offloaded detections remain suitable for real-time control.

$$\mathbf{p}^{\text{trg}}(t) = \begin{cases} f(\mathbf{p}^{\text{trg}}(t + \tau_u(t))), & \text{if } \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \leq \tau_{\text{max}} \\ \text{"ignore"}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.20)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ is the target detection function executed in the edge computing environment.

Figure 2.41: Schematic of the architecture incorporating edge offloading for the target detection and localization.

The condition $\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \leq \tau_{\text{max}}$ ensures that the target localization is only considered if the communication delay is within acceptable limits. If the delays exceed τ_{max} , the target localization is disregarded to avoid using outdated or inaccurate data.

Dataset & Detection Strategy

To support robust object detection under varying environmental conditions, a custom dataset comprising 322 images was developed. The dataset captures various lighting conditions, occlusions, and backgrounds in simulated and real environments including tunnels, parking lots, and industrial settings. Three nested target classes (T_{good} , T_{better} , T_{best}) were labeled, enabling multiscale detection. A YOLO-based detector was trained and deployed in a dedicated k8s pod.

Edge-Integrated Target Localization

Following target detection, localization is performed by estimating the 6D pose of the target using a Perspective-n-Point (PnP) solver with 2D-3D correspondences from the Red-Green-Blue (RGB) and depth images. This process computes the target position and orientation relative to the UAV's camera frame and transforms it into the global frame.

Control Pipeline Integration via CBF

The localized target information is used to guide the UAV using a position controller with embedded CBF constraints. The control strategy ensures smooth convergence to the target while enforcing safety. The CBF design is shaped to guide the UAV safely into contact with the target, ensuring minimal deviation and safe APhI.

Within this framework, the CBF operates as a real-time safety layer, ensuring that the UAV's motion remains inside a dynamically defined safe set. Based on the predicted state evolution of the UAV relative to the target, the CBF constrains the control input so that the system respects predefined safety boundaries even when external disturbances or modeling uncertainties are present.

The design of the CBF is intentionally shaped to form a funnel-like safe region around the approach trajectory, gradually narrowing as the UAV nears the target. This geometry ensures that the UAV naturally aligns itself before contact, minimizing lateral deviations and reducing impact velocities. As a result, the UAV achieves soft interaction with the target surface without requiring an external motion planner or precomputed approach trajectory. Instead, the CBF dynamically reshapes the feasible control inputs based on the UAV's state and target position, thereby combining predictive safety with reactive control.

In the proposed architecture, this safety-aware controller complements the edge-offloaded perception pipeline by decoupling the time-critical control loop from the heavy computational load of the target detection module. While the target detection and localization are offloaded to the edge cluster, the CBF-enhanced control remains locally executed or lightly supervised to ensure low-latency responses. This hybrid design enables the UAV to exploit powerful edge-based perception while maintaining reliable, safety-critical control onboard.

2.5.2 Evaluation & Results

The proposed architecture was validated in both simulation and real-world scenarios. In simulation, experiments were performed in refinery and tunnel environments, demonstrating safe convergence to the target under CBF-based control and ML-based perception. Figure 2.42 shows the safe trajectories maintained within the CBF boundary. Position errors and commanded velocities, depicted in Figures 2.43 and 2.44, confirm the controller's effectiveness.

Figure 2.42: The CBF boundary layer along with the trajectories of the UAV guided by the CBF to the target.

Real-world experiments were conducted in an industrial facility where the UAV performed inspection missions with multiple locations of static targets. Detection quality was consistent, with minimal false negatives and no significant false positives, as summarized in Figure 2.45. Furthermore, the detection module successfully identified targets in various environmental conditions including overexposed daylight and dim tunnel scenarios, as shown in Figure 2.46. The edge offloading strategy allowed reliable perception even when onboard resources were inadequate to run the full detection pipeline.

Figure 2.43: Errors in position and yaw of the UAV for the two runs.

Figure 2.44: Commanded velocity for the UAV for the runs.

The presented architecture demonstrates the benefits of offloading ML-based perception tasks to the edge while maintaining onboard safety-critical control. The hybrid deployment model enables autonomous UAVs to operate effectively in computationally constrained environments and challenging field conditions. This approach supports robust, scalable, and safe perception-driven navigation in industrial robotics applications.

Figure 2.45: Plot of the sum of target detection through time during a flight test. Regions in yellow highlight moments when a target is within the camera's field of view.

Figure 2.46: Color and depth images of target detection in real flight application with previously unseen images.

2.6 Concluding Remarks

This chapter presented a comprehensive analysis of edge-offloading architectures for resource-constrained aerial robotic systems, with a primary focus on NMPC and its integration into edge-based environments. The proposed architectures demonstrate how advanced control strategies, which are computationally prohibitive for onboard processors, can be seamlessly executed at the edge while maintaining the demanding timing and stability requirements of aerial robotic applications. Through simulation, laboratory, and real-world experiments, including deployments in challenging environments such as underground mining sites, the feasibility and benefits of this approach have been rigorously validated.

The chapter introduced a unified control offloading framework, illustrating how NMPC modules can be containerized and deployed on k8s clusters to leverage scalable edge resources. This design enables high-rate, long-horizon predictive control of UAVs and supports real-time adaptation to dynamic environments, including collision avoidance and trajectory tracking tasks. The framework also accommodates hybrid deployments, as shown in the ML offloading section, where perception modules are processed at the edge while safety-critical control remains onboard or is supervised through CBFs. This architectural flexibility represents a key contribution of the chapter, opening the way for integrating advanced autonomy functions into lightweight aerial platforms.

Despite these advances, the chapter also highlights inherent challenges associated with edge-offloaded control. Foremost among these are communication delays (UL and DL) and processing delays caused by the execution of computationally intensive algorithms. While the experiments show that current implementations remain within stability bounds, these delays represent a critical constraint for time-critical control loops and will be examined in greater detail in Chapter 3. Likewise, resource allocation and scheduling within the edge cluster emerge as key factors in ensuring predictable performance, especially when multiple robotic agents or heterogeneous tasks are involved. These issues will be the focus of Chapters 4 and 5, where methods for latency-aware orchestration and dynamic resource management will be developed.

In summary, this chapter establishes the technical foundation for edge-offloaded NMPC and control-perception architectures, demonstrating their potential to unlock high-performance autonomy for UAVs operating in complex and constrained environments. By combining predictive control with scalable edge computing, the proposed framework addresses the limitations of onboard computation and sets the stage for the delay-aware, resource-optimized strategies that follow in the subsequent chapters.

Addressing Time Delay Impact

3.1 Overview

In Chapter 2, a novel edge-based architecture for resource-constrained robotic platforms operating in time-critical applications was presented. By leveraging edge computing, the proposed framework successfully overcame the computational limitations of onboard hardware, enabling the execution of high-rate and long-horizon NMPC with low processing latency. However, despite these advances, the performance of such edge-offloaded control loops remains vulnerable to communication delays, which can degrade tracking performance, violate safety margins, and destabilize the system if left unaddressed [6, 83].

While the problem of time delays has been extensively studied in the broader NCS literature [84–87], this thesis goes further by demonstrating how delay mitigation strategies can be integrated within a modern edge-based NMPC frameworks. Two approaches are developed and validated: (i) delay compensation, which predicts the UAV state at the instant of command reception by using real-time measurements of the RTT, thus allowing the NMPC to compute control inputs for the predicted state rather than the delayed state, and (ii) resilience through fallback actions, which introduces an onboard safety mechanism that continuously monitors communication KPIs, such as RTT, packet loss, and SINR, and switches to a lightweight local controller when edge control is considered unsafe.

These approaches are not competing but instead, they operate simultaneously to ensure robust performance. The delay compensation mechanism continuously adjusts the control inputs to counteract the effects of bounded communication delays, while the fallback actions act as a safety layer, ensuring that the UAV remains stable and within safe operating conditions even under extreme delay or link degradation [38, 44].

This chapter presents the motivation, design, and experimental validation of both mechanisms. It shows how the integration of delay compensation with a resilient fallback strategy enables predictive and safe autonomy of UAVs under time-varying communication conditions, laying the way for reliable deployments in industrial and other safety-critical environments [39, 40, 88].

3.2 Contributions

The main contributions of this chapter are summarized as (i) the integration of delay compensation into edge-offloaded NMPC through a state predictor that is designed to compensate for time-varying network delays by using real-time RTT measurements; (ii) the development of a novel switching strategy to enable safe fallback control, and (iii) a unified architecture for delay-resilient edge control.

The predictor estimates the UAV state at the time the edge-generated control action will be applied, thus reducing the mismatch between the state used for optimization and the actual UAV state at command execution. This compensator is implemented as part of the edge-offloaded NMPC framework and validated in experimental scenarios.

The switching mechanism uses communication KPIs, including latency and SINR thresholds, to estimate the potential position error caused by delays. When these indicators suggest that the offloaded NMPC can no longer guarantee safe control, the system reactively switches to a local Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID)-based controller running on the UAV's onboard computer. This guarantees bounded position error and stability even during extreme network degradation.

The chapter proposes a unified architecture where delay compensation and safety fallback actions operate in parallel. The predictive NMPC running on the edge remains the primary controller, while the onboard safety controller acts as a fallback fail-safe. This combination allows UAVs to take advantage of powerful edge computing resources while retaining a safety guarantee during communication uncertainties.

Together, these contributions significantly advance the state-of-the-art in edge-controlled robotic systems by addressing the key challenge of communication-induced delays in time-critical UAV applications. By combining real-time delay compensation mechanisms with a robust KPI-driven fallback strategy, the proposed framework not only preserves the benefits of edge-based NMPC, but also ensures safe and reliable operation under variable and potentially degraded network conditions.

3.3 Delay Compensation

Autonomous UAVs are increasingly deployed in industrial inspection, surveying, maintenance, and emergency response tasks, where timely and accurate control is essential for safety and mission success [89, 90]. Offloading NMPC to edge servers instead of cloud, reduces computational latency and enables complex control schemes otherwise infeasible on onboard hardware. As edge computing places storage and computational resources closer to the data source, it can be used to offload heavy algorithms and achieve real-time processing with reduced latency [91]. This type of edge-based control loop can be further accelerated with the adoption of 5G networking, which offers low communication delays and high reliability [52, 92]. However, unlike pure onboard control, edge-offloaded architectures introduce loop latency due to UL, processing, and DL delays. Even with modern 5G networks, these delays can vary dynamically based on network load, distance, and interference, leading to state mismatches and degraded control performance.

Traditional MPC formulations rarely account for communication delays explicitly. This chapter addresses this gap by integrating real-time delay compensation into the NMPC loop named PACED-5G (Predictive Autonomous Control using Edge for Drones over 5G). By measuring the instantaneous RTT between the UAV and the edge and using a moving average filter to smooth variations, the UAV state is predicted forward to the time of command execution. The NMPC thus optimizes over the predicted state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))$ instead of $\mathbf{x}(t)$, where $\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)$ is the measured RTT delay. This approach significantly reduces the effective latency of the control loop, maintaining high tracking accuracy under time-varying delays.

3.3.1 Controller Development for Delay Compensation

To account for communication and processing delays, the closed-loop system architecture introduced in Chapter 2 must be extended to explicitly incorporate these delays into the control design. This is achieved by predicting the UAV states corresponding to the moment when the control actions are expected to reach and actuate the aerial platform, as illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Block diagram of the edge architecture for the delay-compensation UAV-NMPC system.

System Dynamics

The overall delay in the closed-loop system can be addressed by modifying the UAV dynamics to include a delayed control input. This approach follows similar modeling strategies presented in [67] and [66], and is represented by the delayed-input formulation given in (3.1).

$$\ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) = \frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \mathbf{F}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) + \mathbf{G} - \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\dot{q}_\phi(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_\phi} (K_\phi q_\phi^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - q_\phi(t)) \quad (3.1b)$$

$$\dot{q}_\theta(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_\theta} (K_\theta q_\theta^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - q_\theta(t)) \quad (3.1c)$$

All model parameters remain consistent with those introduced in Chapter 2. As illustrated in the block diagram in Figure 3.1, the total RTT delay in the closed-loop system is defined as $\tau_{\text{rtt}} = \tau_u + \tau_p + \tau_d$.

The control objective is to design a controller that enables the UAV to track a desired trajectory while operating under time-varying delays and ensuring collision avoidance with dynamic obstacles.

The proposed solution is structured in two stages: (i) a state prediction mechanism to estimate the UAV's actual state at the time of control actuation, and (ii) a controller that computes delay-compensated control inputs. Both components are described in detail in the following subsections.

State Predictor

To compensate for the total control closed-loop delay τ_{rtt} , consisting of UL, processing, and DL components, a state prediction mechanism is developed to estimate the UAV's actual state at the time the control input is applied, as presented in our published work [31].

The architecture includes a loopback mechanism, whereby the UAV's onboard computer returns the time-stamped control input to the edge-based predictor, along with current odometry data of both the UAV and surrounding obstacles. The predictor estimates the closed-loop delay in discrete time using a moving average, as shown in (3.2).

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}, k+1} &= (1 - \alpha) \cdot \widehat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}, k} + \alpha \cdot \tau_{\text{rtt}, k}, \\ \text{with } \tau_{\text{rtt}, 0} &= 0\end{aligned}\tag{3.2}$$

Here, $\tau_{\text{rtt}, k}$ is the measured difference between the current timestamp and the timestamp of the received control signal. The smoothing parameter α is utilized based on a sliding window calculated by (3.3).

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{k}, & \text{for } k \leq \sigma \\ \frac{1}{\sigma}, & \text{for } k > \sigma \end{cases}\tag{3.3}$$

where σ the sliding window length.

The predictions of the positions and velocities are modeled as formulated in (3.4).

$$\widehat{\mathbf{p}}(t) = \mathbf{p}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))\tag{3.4a}$$

$$\implies \widehat{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(t) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))\tag{3.4b}$$

Since the control inputs are delayed, they have to be designed in such a way that the current inputs ensure that the future state after a delay tracks the future trajectory with minimal error. Therefore, an prediction of future states of the UAV's and the obstacle needs to be generated to be used in the control law. To compensate for the delayed states presented in (3.4b), the future velocity is approximated by a first order Taylor expansion around the current estimate (while assuming constant velocity), expressed in (3.5).

$$\widehat{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \widehat{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(t) + \ddot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \cdot \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)\tag{3.5}$$

By utilizing (3.1a) and assuming constant UAV velocity for each τ_{rtt} iteration, the expression (3.5) can be expanded as in (3.6) and sequentially (3.7).

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) + \left(\frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \mathbf{F}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) + \mathbf{G} - \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \right) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (3.6)$$

$$\implies \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{A} \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))^{-1} \left(\dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) + \left(\frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \mathbf{F}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) + \mathbf{G} \right) \right) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (3.7)$$

Further, future predictions of the position can be predicted from (3.7) using the relationship (3.8).

$$\widehat{\mathbf{p}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \widehat{\mathbf{p}}(t) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \cdot \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (3.8)$$

The control input $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \mathbf{F}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))$ depends on the attitude dynamics, thus, the future predictions for the roll and pitch are derived by following similar steps from (3.4a)-(3.8), and using the relationships (3.1b), (3.1c), as represented in (3.9a) through (3.9d).

$$\widehat{q}_\phi(t) = q_\phi(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \quad (3.9a)$$

$$\widehat{q}_\theta(t) = q_\theta(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \quad (3.9b)$$

$$\widehat{q}_\phi(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \widehat{q}_\phi(t) + \dot{q}_\phi(t) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (3.9c)$$

$$\widehat{q}_\theta(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \widehat{q}_\theta(t) + \dot{q}_\theta(t) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t), \quad (3.9d)$$

where

$$\dot{q}_\phi(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_\phi} (K_\phi q_\phi^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - \widehat{q}_\phi(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)))$$

$$\dot{q}_\theta(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_\theta} (K_\theta q_\theta^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - \widehat{q}_\theta(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))),$$

so (3.9c) and (3.9d) become (3.10).

$$\widehat{q}_\phi(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \left(\mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{\alpha_\phi} \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \right)^{-1} \left(\widehat{q}_\phi(t) - \frac{1}{\alpha_\phi} (K_\phi q_\phi^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))) \right) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (3.10a)$$

$$\widehat{q}_\theta(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \left(\mathbf{I} + \frac{1}{\alpha_\theta} \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \right)^{-1} \left(\widehat{q}_\theta(t) - \frac{1}{\alpha_\theta} (K_\theta q_\theta^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))) \right) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (3.10b)$$

Similarly, the future prediction of the obstacle location, \mathbf{p}^{obs} is estimated as expressed in (3.11).

$$\dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t) + \mathbf{G} \cdot \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \widehat{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t) + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t) \cdot \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t), \quad (3.11)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{obs}}(t) = \mathbf{p}^{\text{obs}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))$ is the predicted position of the obstacle. Here, the considered obstacle has an initial velocity, but the only force acting on the obstacle is gravity.

Nonlinear Model Predictive Control

The objective of the high-level NMPC is to generate control inputs $\mathbf{u} \triangleq [q_\phi^{\text{ref}}(t) \quad q_\theta^{\text{ref}}(t) \quad T(t)]$ that enable tracking of the desired reference position trajectory, produced by the trajectory generation module (cf. Figure 3.1). Due to the presence of time-varying delays, the control inputs must be designed with respect to the predicted future states of the UAV.

A state vector is therefore constructed using the predicted future position, velocity, roll, and pitch as $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\hat{\mathbf{p}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}})^\top \quad \hat{\dot{\mathbf{p}}}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}})^\top \quad \hat{q}_\phi(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}) \quad \hat{q}_\theta(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}})]^\top$, as derived in (3.7)–(3.8) and (3.10).

The NMPC optimizes the control actions over a finite prediction horizon of h steps, with a sampling time $T_s = \frac{1}{R_s}$ (where R_s the MPC update rate), based on the forward Euler integration of the predicted state evolution. The reference trajectory, \mathbf{x}^{ref} , is sampled through the prediction horizon and used in the cost function $J_c(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{u}_{k-1})$, as detailed in Chapter 2.

Additionally, the optimization includes constraints for input bounds and dynamic obstacle avoidance. Since the obstacles are modeled as unactuated objects, their predicted positions across the horizon are propagated using Euler-based state evolution. The corresponding constraints are formulated as in Chapter 2.

3.3.2 Evaluation & Results

The performance of the PACED-5G architecture is experimentally validated using the quadrotor UAV, *Crazyflie 2.0*. Odometry feedback for both the UAV and dynamic obstacles is provided by a *Vicon MoCap* system.

The edge cluster is deployed remotely at the data centers of the Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE), located in Luleå. The specifications of this remote k8s cluster resemble those of the in-house system, and are summarized in Table 3.1. These resources provide substantial computational capabilities suitable for real-time control.

Table 3.1: K8s cluster specifications

Specs	Cluster
k8s version	v1.20.15
Worker nodes	3
CPU	60 cores total (20 per node)
Memory	590 GiB total (196 GiB per node)
Management	RKE
CNI	Canal

For the trajectory tracking demonstration, a circular reference trajectory is generated and provided to the NMPC

$$p_x^{\text{ref}}(k) = \sin(k/600) \text{ m}, \quad p_y^{\text{ref}}(k) = \cos(k/600) \text{ m}, \quad p_z^{\text{ref}}(k) = 0.8 \text{ m},$$

where k is the discrete time index. The NMPC samples the states at 30 Hz ($T_s \approx 0.033$ s) with a prediction horizon of $N = 60$ time steps.

The system is evaluated in two experimental scenarios: (i) tracking without dynamic obstacles, and (ii) tracking in the presence of dynamic obstacles.

Comparison with Uncompensated Control

To validate the effectiveness of the delay compensation strategy, a comparative experiment was conducted between two configurations: (i) UAV control without delay compensation, and (ii) UAV control using the proposed state predictor. The objective was to assess the impact of unmodeled communication delays on the control performance and evaluate the benefits of prediction-based compensation.

Figure 3.2 presents the instantaneous and moving average estimates of the RTT delay (τ_{rtt}) during flight. The observed delays exhibit temporal variation, with the moving average stabilizing around 67 milliseconds. Although this value may be way below the maximum allowable delay τ_{max} , even such minimal latency has a measurable impact on the tracking accuracy of the aerial platform in time-critical operations.

Figure 3.2: Instantaneous and moving average estimate of the delay in the closed-loop system over the flight duration.

Figure 3.3 illustrates the position tracking error in each spatial dimension. The predictor significantly reduces this error, particularly along the y -axis, where uncompensated control leads to major deviations. This improvement is further visualized in Figure 3.4, which shows the 3D trajectory of the UAV compared to the reference path. When delay compensation is not applied, the UAV deviates notably from the intended path. In contrast, the compensated system maintains close compliance to the reference, demonstrating the predictor's corrective influence.

To assess prediction reliability, Figure 3.5 displays the prediction error in the x , y , and z positions, along with the corresponding Euclidean norm. The predictor maintains sub-centimeter accuracy, with Euclidean error consistently below 2 millimeters, underscoring the reliability of the delay prediction and correction mechanism.

Figure 3.3: Tracking error in UAV's position.

A quantitative summary of the results is provided in Table 3.2, showing the Root Mean Square (RMS) tracking error for each axis. Without the predictor, the overall deviation is large, most notably with a 33.5 cm Euclidean RMS Error (RMSE), driven by high y-axis drift. In contrast, the predictor reduces the RMSE to below 6 cm overall. The estimation error (i.e., the difference between predicted and actual states) is also minimal, remaining within 0.7 cm in Euclidean distance across the entire flight. These results demonstrate that the proposed predictor significantly improves trajectory tracking performance, effectively compensating for time-varying delays in the loop. By ensuring that the UAV state predictions closely align with the true states, the predictor allows the NMPC to compute more accurate control inputs, which translates to smoother and more reliable flight behavior, which is critical for safety and operational consistency in time-critical missions.

Table 3.2: Position tracking performance

Controller	RMSE			
	$e_x(\text{cm})$	$e_y(\text{cm})$	$e_z(\text{cm})$	$e_{\text{trj}}(\text{cm})$
With prediction	4.46	3.75	0.90	5.70
Without prediction	6.45	32.99	2.28	33.55
Estimation error	0.49	0.50	0.11	0.69

Figure 3.4: Trajectory tracked by the UAV with and without compensation for the delays in the system for the given reference trajectory.

Figure 3.5: Error in the prediction of the states (x, y, z) and their Euclidean distance.

These results confirm that even under relatively low-latency conditions, delay-induced performance degradation can be substantial. The proposed predictor effectively mitigates this issue, enabling robust and accurate trajectory tracking under realistic network delay conditions.

Obstacle Avoidance

In this scenario, the UAV is tasked with tracking a reference trajectory while reacting to a dynamic obstacle. To evaluate the system's real-time responsiveness under edge-offloaded control with delays, a moving obstacle is thrown towards the UAV at two separate instances as it follows a circular path. Given the inherent latency in offloaded control, this scenario is executed only with the delay-compensated controller enabled, as attempting it without the state predictor would significantly increase the risk of collision.

Figure 3.6 illustrates the resulting UAV trajectories both in the absence and presence of the obstacle. As shown, the NMPC, running on the edge, successfully anticipates the future state of the UAV and the incoming obstacle by leveraging the delay-compensated predictions from the state predictor. Upon detecting a predicted collision based on the obstacle's predicted motion, the controller proactively generates evasive control actions that steer the UAV away from the potential impact zone. Once the dynamic obstacle is no longer in the UAV's proximity, the NMPC smoothly guides the UAV back onto the reference trajectory.

Figure 3.6: Trajectory taken by the UAV in the absence and presence of the obstacle while following a reference trajectory, along with the obstacle trajectories during possible collisions.

This experiment confirms the capability of the proposed PACED-5G architecture to maintain safety and continuity of mission execution in dynamic environments where real-time obstacle avoidance is required. It also highlights the importance of accurate state prediction in enabling proactive maneuvers under communication delays. Overall, the system achieves effective closed-loop behavior under high-level control latency, validating both the robustness of the predictor and the practicality of deploying such architectures in real-world, delay-prone conditions.

3.4 Resilience through Fallback Actions

While delay compensation can mitigate the effects of bounded communication delays, there remain real-world scenarios such as extreme packet loss, sudden SINR degradation, or out-of-coverage events, where offloaded control becomes unsafe or infeasible. In such cases, relying solely on the edge-offloaded NMPC risks destabilizing the UAV or causing large position deviations.

To mitigate such risks, recent efforts have explored switching mechanisms between remote and local control as a form of system redundancy. Several studies, such as [41,64], have investigated delay-tolerant edge algorithms that aim to operate acceptably under moderate latency variations. However, these approaches typically rely on robustness within the control algorithm itself and do not explicitly introduce fallback strategies when communication degrades beyond safe operational limits.

More direct switching frameworks have been proposed in the context of autonomous driving and industrial control. For instance, in [93], cloud-based controllers are used for managing fleets of autonomous vehicles, but control is transferred to edge-based controllers when latency exceeds a predefined threshold. Similarly, [94] considers dynamic switching between different edge servers to maintain performance under varying network conditions. However, these works largely neglect cases of extreme latency or total communication loss, where switching to a fully onboard controller becomes essential.

Closer to the robotics domain, [95] introduces a self-reliant MPC deployed in the cloud, with a replacement controller activated during transition periods that degrade performance. Other hybrid schemes in industrial contexts have been proposed in [96,97], where edge and local controllers collaborate based on a logic that prioritizes real-time constraints. In particular, [96] uses a logic where the local controller replicates the edge controller's command if it is delivered in time, otherwise, it defaults to a local command. In contrast, [97] applies a region-based logic: when the system operates within a performance region, the edge controller governs the process, if it deviates, a local controller ensures stability.

Several classical approaches have also addressed similar concerns in delay-sensitive systems, such as those explored in time-delay control literature [6]. More recent works, such as [98], propose a framework where the cloud MPC either controls the system directly, supports a local controller, or relinquishes control entirely when network conditions deteriorate. Similarly, [99] presents a tri-level hierarchy where a cloud MPC (fast and accurate), a local MPC (slower and suboptimal), and a LQR operate at different fallback levels based on the latency observed in control command reception.

Despite their innovation, these prior works often rely on static latency thresholds or rough metrics for switching. What sets the approach presented in this thesis apart is its use of communication-layer KPIs, to estimate the control error in real time. Rather than reacting merely to delays, the proposed switching mechanism predicts the impact of degraded communication on the UAV's positional error and switches to a local, lightweight PID controller only when necessary, which is when the delay-induced error is projected to exceed an acceptable threshold.

This position-aware, KPI-driven logic enables smoother switching compared to existing schemes. By doing so, the framework ensures that edge-based MPC is utilized whenever safe and advantageous, but never at the cost of system safety. Furthermore, the fallback controller runs fully onboard the UAV, without relying on external computation, ensuring mission continuity even under full communication loss. The overall architecture with the integration of the switching mechanism is depicted in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Control block diagram of the system with the switching mechanism integration.

3.4.1 Control Architecture & Redundancy Integration

While Section 3.3 focused on mitigating bounded communication delays through edge-side delay compensation, this section addresses unbounded or unpredictable delays by integrating resilient safety mechanisms directly into the onboard system of the robot. Therefore, the overall architecture includes two control pipelines: (i) the edge NMPC controller that is executed on the k8s edge cluster and computes optimized control inputs $\mathbf{u}^{\text{mpc}}(t)$ based on predicted states $\mathbf{x}(t - \tau_u(t) + \hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t))$ and the reference states $\mathbf{x}_{\text{mp}}^{\text{ref}}(t)$, generated by the mission planner, and (ii) an onboard PID controller that is executed directly on the UAV and generates fallback commands $\mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}(t)$ based on the current local odometry $\mathbf{x}(t)$ and the reference odometry $\mathbf{x}_{\text{fp}}^{\text{ref}}(t)$, extracted by the fallback planner.

A switching mechanism selects between \mathbf{u}^{mpc} and \mathbf{u}^{pid} depending on the estimated position error caused by communication delays and the SINR, measured throughout the mission to estimate the signal quality and predict potential signal drops. This switching logic, published in [32], enables optimized edge-based control, while ensuring that control always remains within safe bounds, through safety fallback actions.

Edge Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller

The edge-deployed NMPC controller has been fully described in Chapter 2 and in Section 3.3 including the delay compensation mechanism. It operates over UDP tunnels and runs in a dedicated k8s pod. The controller optimizes a multi-objective cost function over a prediction horizon h , and computes thrust and attitude commands $\mathbf{u}^{\text{mpc}} \triangleq [q_\phi^{\text{ref}} \ q_\theta^{\text{ref}} \ T]^\top$ subject to control and safety constraints.

Since the NMPC requires knowledge of the current UAV state, a state predictor is implemented at the edge to estimate the UAV's position, velocity, and attitude using delayed inputs, as described in Section 3.3.1.

Onboard PID Controller

The local fallback controller is a classic PID structure designed for rapid execution under constrained resources. It operates on odometry data available onboard and outputs control commands $\mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}(t)$. The PID control law used to compute the fallback control actions is given by (3.12).

$$\mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}(t) = \mathbf{K}_p \mathbf{e}(t) + \mathbf{K}_i \int_0^t \mathbf{e}(\tau) d\tau + \mathbf{K}_d \frac{d\mathbf{e}(t)}{dt} \quad (3.12)$$

where $\mathbf{e}(t) = \mathbf{x}_{\text{fp}}^{\text{ref}}(t) - \mathbf{x}(t)$ is the tracking error, and \mathbf{K}_p , \mathbf{K}_i , and \mathbf{K}_d are diagonal gain matrices for the proportional, integral, and derivative terms, respectively.

To prevent unsafe inputs to the LLC, each command is saturated using (3.13).

$$\mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}(t) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{u}_{\text{max}}, & \text{for } \mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}(t) \geq \mathbf{u}_{\text{max}} \\ \mathbf{u}_{\text{min}}, & \text{for } \mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}(t) \leq \mathbf{u}_{\text{min}} \\ \mathbf{u}^{\text{pid}}, & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (3.13)$$

The PID gains \mathbf{K}_p , \mathbf{K}_i , and \mathbf{K}_d are tuned to allow safe operation even under degraded communication.

3.4.2 Switching Strategy

Unlike traditional switching strategies based solely on RTT metrics [100], the approach presented here introduces a multi-criteria switching strategy that estimates the potential position error due to DL latency, monitors packet loss, and incorporates radio-level indicators such as the SINR. These indicators together inform a robust decision-making framework that determines whether the system should operate in offloaded control mode via the edge-based NMPC or onboard control mode via the local PID controller.

Figure 3.8 illustrates the overall architecture and flow of the switching strategy, which incorporates a two-level switching approach. The first level evaluates whether the estimated position error remains below a predefined threshold, while the second level assesses whether the SINR value stays above a desired limit.

Figure 3.8: Overall block diagram of the system with all the modules. The switching mechanism is highlighted with all its components.

Error Estimation based on the Downlink Latency

Due to DL communication delays, the actual position of the UAV, denoted as $\mathbf{p}(t)$, driven by the control command $\mathbf{u}(t)$, may deviate from its intended reference position $\mathbf{p}^{\text{ref}}(t)$, especially when the UAV maintains non-zero velocity, $\mathbf{v}(t) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \neq \mathbf{0}$.

Although the estimated error $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_d(t) \triangleq [\hat{e}_{d,x}(t) \ \hat{e}_{d,y}(t) \ \hat{e}_{d,z}(t)]^\top$, which is computed based on the DL latency τ_d , does not represent the full position error (i.e., $\|\mathbf{p}(t) - \mathbf{p}^{\text{ref}}(t)\|$), it captures the portion of error introduced specifically by communication delays. Other sources of error, such as disturbances, model uncertainties, or controller imperfections, are excluded, as they are not communication-related and would persist regardless of whether the controller runs onboard or offloaded.

Figure 3.9 illustrates the DL latency timeline. For each transmitted control command \mathbf{u}_k , where $k \in 0, 1, \dots, n$, the transmission and reception timestamps are denoted as τ_k^{tx} and τ_k^{rx} , respectively. Assuming a constant control update period T_s , computed by the update rate R_s , the UAV velocity is sampled at the time the last valid command $\mathbf{u}_{k-(m+1)}$ was applied, where m is the number of consecutively dropped packets.

Based on this setup, the delay-induced position estimation error is modeled as (3.14).

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_d(t) = \mathbf{v}_{k-(m+1)}(t) \cdot \tau_d(t) \quad (3.14)$$

where $\tau_d(t)$ represents the current DL delay.

In this work, two formulations for $\tau_d(t)$ are considered to characterize different aspects of delay behavior.

Consecutive Command Delay: This formulation measures the delay between the reception of two successive commands at the UAV and is expressed in (3.15).

$$\tau_{dc}(t) = \tau_k^{\text{rx}} - \tau_{k-(m+1)}^{\text{rx}} \quad (3.15)$$

Therefore, the corresponding estimated error is calculated in (3.16).

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{dc}(t) = \mathbf{v}_{k-(m+1)}(t) \cdot \tau_{dc}(t) \quad (3.16)$$

Figure 3.9: Latency timeline based on transmitted and received control commands \mathbf{u}_k .

Transmission-to-Reception Delay: This formulation captures the full delay from the time a command was generated at the edge to its reception by the UAV and is expressed in (3.17).

$$\tau_{\text{dr}}(t) = \tau_k^{\text{rx}} - \tau_k^{\text{tx}} + m \cdot T_s, \quad (3.17)$$

with the corresponding estimated error computed in (3.18).

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dr}}(t) = \mathbf{v}_{k-(m+1)}(t) \cdot \tau_{\text{dr}}(t) \quad (3.18)$$

In practice, these two estimates reflect slightly different effects, as when $\tau_d = T_s$ then both estimations should coincide ($\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dc}} = \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dr}}$), while when $\tau_d > T_s$ then $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dc}} < \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dr}}$ and when $\tau_d < T_s$ then $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dc}} > \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dr}}$. Thus, to capture a balanced estimate of the delay-induced error, the average of both is taken, using (3.19).

$$\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{d}}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dc}}(t) + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dr}}(t)) \quad (3.19)$$

Finally, to determine whether the system must switch to a safety fallback mode, the magnitude of the estimated delay-induced error is compared against a predefined threshold e^{thr} . This magnitude is computed by (3.20).

$$\hat{e}(t) = \|\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{d}}(t)\| = \sqrt{\hat{e}_{\text{d},x}^2(t) + \hat{e}_{\text{d},y}^2(t) + \hat{e}_{\text{d},z}^2(t)}, \quad (3.20)$$

and the switching condition is triggered when (3.21) is true.

$$\hat{e}(t) > e^{\text{thr}} \quad (3.21)$$

This approach enables the switching mechanism to anticipate degradation in control performance due to DL delays and activate onboard fallback actions before unsafe deviation occurs.

Signal Strength

In addition to delay-based indicators, communication KPIs related to channel conditions can offer early warnings about potential link degradation. Even in scenarios where the observed delay is within acceptable limits, the communication link may be prone to sudden loss due to poor signal quality. One such indicator is the SINR, which provides a real-time assessment of channel reliability.

To proactively ensure safe operation, the switching mechanism monitors the SINR metric and triggers a fallback to onboard control when the measured value falls below a predefined threshold s^{thr} . This behavior is described by the condition (3.22).

$$s(t) < s^{\text{thr}} \quad (3.22)$$

The threshold s^{thr} is chosen based on prior empirical studies and link analysis, ensuring that the system maintains sufficient latency and throughput performance for offloaded control processes under nominal conditions. When the condition in (3.22) is met, the system considers the wireless channel unsuitable for offloaded control and switches to the onboard fallback controller.

Switch Formulation

The system is designed to ensure bounded position error and maintain a reliable communication link for safe UAV operation. While it is impossible to eliminate the position error entirely due to modeling inaccuracies, control limitations, or external disturbances, the goal is to guarantee that this error remains within an acceptable safety margin. Maintaining such bounded behavior is particularly critical in time-critical systems, where even small deviations can lead to instability or unsafe flight behavior. Therefore, the proposed architecture continuously monitors both control performance and network quality to ensure that any degradation in communication does not compromise the UAV's stability or operational safety.

Since a portion of the error is directly influenced by end-to-end communication delay and application-layer packet loss, the switching strategy uses an estimated latency-induced error, $\hat{e}(t)$, to determine when to switch control authority. If $\hat{e}(t)$ exceeds a predefined safety threshold e^{thr} , i.e., $\hat{e}(t) > e^{\text{thr}}$, the system is predicted to deviate beyond its allowable tracking margin, and the controller switches from the edge-offloaded NMPC to the onboard PID fallback. Conversely, once the delay reduces and the estimated error satisfies $\hat{e}(t) \leq e^{\text{thr}}$, control is switched back to the offloaded NMPC.

While the onboard PID controller typically provides inferior tracking performance compared to the edge-based NMPC, it ensures robust fail-safe operation under degraded communication conditions, prioritizing safety over optimality.

In addition to this error-based switch, a second switching layer monitors the SINR. As illustrated in Figure 3.8, this SINR-based switch triggers a fallback when the received signal quality $s(t)$ drops below a critical threshold s^{thr} , i.e., $s(t) < s^{\text{thr}}$. This mechanism allows the system to react to rapid link degradation before a full connection loss occurs, even if the latency and error estimation metrics are still within bounds. The SINR switch overrides the error switch and directly switches the system to onboard mode for safety.

To avoid rapid and undesirable switching between control modes, the system employs a sliding window filter to smooth out transient fluctuations in communication metrics. A control switch is triggered only if a threshold violation persists over a sustained number of consecutive time steps N_{sw} , indicating the size of the sliding window. This behavior is formalized in (3.23).

$$\frac{1}{N_{\text{sw}}} \sum_{k=N_s}^t \mathbb{I}[\hat{e}_k > e^{\text{thr}} \text{ or } s_k < s^{\text{thr}}] \geq \gamma, \quad (3.23)$$

where $N_s = t - N_{\text{sw}} + 1$

$\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function that outputs 1 if the condition is true, and 0 otherwise, and $\gamma \in (0, 1]$ is the decision threshold that determines the minimum fraction of violations required to trigger the switch.

Together, the two-level switching strategy, based on error estimation and SINR metrics, ensures a robust and resilient control scheme that preserves the stability and safety of the UAV under uncertain communication conditions.

3.4.3 Evaluation & Results

The experimental evaluation was conducted using the following components: (i) a commercial 5G NR system operating in the mid-band (3.7 GHz) at Luleå University of Technology; (ii) a local `Ericsson DOT` indoor base station for stable 5G coverage, and (iii) a k8s-enabled edge cluster deployed near the core network breakout to ensure minimal communication latency. This low-latency performance has been rigorously analyzed in prior work [52]. A subset of the edge cluster resources was containerized using k8s pods for task orchestration. The UAV platform used in this study is the `Crazyflie 2.0`, while accurate state estimation and ground truth validation were achieved using a `Vicon MoCap` system.

To demonstrate the switching strategy under realistic conditions, the UAV intentionally initiated UL and DL traffic that exceeded the User Equipment's (UE) transmission and reception capabilities. This setup emulates real-world situations where communication bottlenecks arise due to fluctuating data payloads, competing network traffic, or dynamic channel conditions. In practical scenarios, such congestion can occur when UAVs transmit large sensor datasets, such as high-resolution images or LiDAR scans, alongside continuous telemetry and control data streams. By generating such network saturation autonomously, the experiment creates a controlled yet representative communication load that stresses the 5G link and the edge-offloaded control loop. This allows for the observation of system behavior under conditions that mirror those encountered in field operations. Similar test cases and motivation are discussed in [101], where the impact of network congestion on control stability and latency performance was analyzed in detail.

A representative mission scenario was considered, where the UAV autonomously follows a circular trajectory while relying entirely on offloaded edge processing. During flight, the network was disturbed to degrade link quality and induce increased delays. This degradation was caused by exceeding UL and DL data capacity or by introducing severe signal interference at multiple instances. These events were intentionally injected to trigger the switching strategy and evaluate system robustness.

Switching Events During Flight

Figure 3.10: UAV trajectory in 3 axes. The switching mechanism to the onboard PID controller is triggered under poor connectivity. Initially, the UAV operates with the 5G-edge-enabled NMPC controller. During the experiment, three switching events occur between offloaded and onboard control. Switching decisions are marked with the red signal.

Figures 3.10 and 3.11 illustrate the dynamic behavior of the UAV when operating under fluctuating network conditions. In these experiments, gradual and abrupt degradations of the wireless channel, manifested as drops in SINR, act as triggers for the switching mechanism. A threshold of $s^{\text{thr}} = 6$ dB was selected based on empirical observations and studies of 5G performance near cell edges or in environments with elevated interference levels [4]. When the measured SINR falls below this threshold, the system interprets the communication link as unreliable and automatically transitions control authority from the offloaded NMPC to the onboard PID controller. Conversely, once the SINR recovers above the defined threshold, the system reverts to edge-based operation. The results clearly demonstrate the responsiveness of the switching logic, as the system consistently ensures continuity of control and flight stability despite severe communication fluctuations.

Figure 3.11: Top view of reference and actual trajectories. During offloaded-MPC control, the UAV follows a circular path. When onboard-PID is activated, the UAV switches to hovering at the home position $\mathbf{p}^{\text{home}} = [0 \ 4 \ 0.8]^T$.

Although the BW requirements for offloaded operation are modest, approximately 30 Kbps for state feedback and 15 Kbps for control commands, the SINR degradation affects modulation and coding schemes, potentially dropping from 64-QAM (Quadrature Amplitude Modulation) to 16-QAM. This leads to reduced throughput and increased transmission latency. When SINR drops below the configured threshold, the switching mechanism activates the onboard PID controller. It is observed that tracking accuracy degrades slightly during fallback control due to PID limitations, and transients are visible during switching. While further tuning or a dedicated transitional controller could improve performance, such refinements fall beyond the scope of this study.

Latency-Based Switching Triggered by Delay Conditions

In a second set of experiments, the UAV executed the same trajectory while streaming excessive data to artificially degrade both UL and DL performance. This scenario mimics common real-world cases where applications produce highly variable data rates (e.g., real-time vision pipelines). Simultaneously, UAV motion affects channel conditions dynamically.

Figure 3.12: Estimated error $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{dc}$ with corresponding measured delay τ_{dc} . Latency induction begins at approximately 18.5 seconds.

Figures 3.12 and 3.13 present the time series of the latency estimations τ_{dc} and τ_{dr} , along with their respective predicted position errors $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{dc}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{dr}$. A pronounced surge in both latency and estimated error is observed beginning at approximately $t = 18.5$ s, which corresponds to the intentional injection of traffic overload. Each delay formulation exhibits distinct sensitivities. For example, $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{dr}$ which accounts for command generation delay and dropped packets, is particularly influenced by the frequency and duration of packet loss events, while $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{dc}$ reflects variations in command arrival intervals more directly.

Moreover, both error signals exhibit sharp fluctuations that are further amplified by changes in UAV velocity. As control commands become increasingly delayed, the UAV reacts to outdated state information, often with overcompensating control actions that lead to instability or deviation from the reference path. These observations highlight the limitations of relying on a single error formulation for triggering fallback actions. As such, the proposed switching strategy uses a combined average of both estimators to improve robustness and reduce sensitivity to transient spikes in either individual metric. This approach balances responsiveness with reliability, avoiding oscillatory switching decisions, and ensuring that the fallback is activated when communication issues indicate a degradation in control performance.

Figure 3.13: Estimated error $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_{\text{dr}}$ with corresponding measured delay τ_{dr} . Latency induction begins at approximately 18.5 seconds.

Switch Activation via Filtered Error Signal

The combined error estimate $\hat{e}(t)$, derived as the mean of $\hat{e}_{\text{dc}}(t)$ and $\hat{e}_{\text{dr}}(t)$, is shown in Figure 3.14. Due to its inherently high frequency of fluctuation, the raw error signal is not used directly for switching. Instead, a sliding window filter (length: 50 samples) is applied to generate a smoother metric. When this filtered error exceeds the predefined threshold $e^{\text{thr}} = 0.15$ m, the system transitions to onboard control. Once the average error falls below the threshold again, it switches back to the optimal edge-based controller.

The estimated error corresponds solely to latency-induced deviation. The results show that the proposed switching framework reliably detects unsafe control conditions and maintains UAV stability by falling back to a simpler but safer onboard controller. The complete switching mechanism was validated through multiple cycles of network degradation and recovery.

Overall, the experimental results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed switching mechanism under realistic network impairments. By monitoring delay-induced error estimates and channel quality metrics such as SINR, the system successfully transitions between offloaded NMPC and onboard PID control to preserve stability and mission continuity, therefore guaranteeing the safety of the closed-loop system.

Figure 3.14: Estimated latency-induced error $\hat{e}(t)$ (gray), its sliding window average (black), and the threshold $e^{\text{thr}} = 0.15$ meters (red). When the filtered error exceeds the threshold, a switch is triggered.

3.5 Concluding Remarks

This chapter addressed one of the most critical challenges in edge-offloaded robotic control systems which is the impact of time delays. Although edge computing offers significant advantages in terms of computational offloading and modularity, the inherent delays in communication, particularly over wireless links such as 5G, pose serious limitations to the stability and performance of time-critical control loops in aerial robotic platforms. Chapter 3 introduced two complementary strategies to mitigate this issue: (i) a predictive delay compensation scheme, and (ii) a robust fallback mechanism through an onboard switching strategy.

A delay-aware control framework was developed, where the UAV system model was augmented with delay dynamics. A state predictor was designed to anticipate the UAV's future state based on measured RTT, enabling the NMPC to issue control actions that are valid upon arrival. This predictive model, integrated within the previously introduced edge-offloading framework (PACED-5G), was experimentally validated under real-world 5G network conditions. The results demonstrated a marked improvement in trajectory tracking and system responsiveness, particularly when compared to uncompensated control.

Complementing this, a resilience mechanism was introduced to maintain safe operation under conditions where delay becomes unbounded, or the communication channel degrades significantly. A two-level switching strategy was deployed onboard the UAV, using error estimation from DL delay and SINR measurements as the primary indicators. When communication quality falls below predefined thresholds, the control system transitions from the edge-deployed NMPC to a lightweight onboard PID controller. Experimental evaluations validated the robustness of this approach, demonstrating successful fallback operation in high-latency and low-SINR scenarios, while maintaining bounded error and mission continuity.

Together, the delay compensation and fallback strategies presented in this chapter significantly enhance the reliability of edge-controlled UAVs in real-world deployments. They offer complementary safety mechanisms with one predictive and integrated within the controller, and the other reactive and embedded in the vehicle's onboard logic. These results demonstrate that with careful system design and integration, edge-offloaded architectures can overcome the constraints imposed by variable network performance.

In subsequent chapters, the challenges associated with processing delays and resource constraints in MAS will be addressed. Specifically, the focus will shift toward adaptive and dynamic resource allocation, and scalable orchestration mechanisms, further expanding the architectural resilience introduced here.

Edge Architectures for Multi-Agent Systems

4.1 Overview

MAS are rapidly emerging as a key paradigm in robotics, enabling teams of robots to collaboratively execute complex tasks that would be otherwise infeasible for a single agent [102, 103]. Such systems are especially prevalent in logistics, infrastructure inspection, surveillance, and industrial automation [104–106]. However, MAS pose substantial technical challenges, particularly due to the limited onboard computational resources of many mobile robots, the high communication demands of inter-agent coordination, and the need to enforce safety and synchronization across distributed units.

While previous chapters introduced edge computing as a viable solution to overcome onboard limitations in single-agent systems, this chapter extends those insights to the domain of MAS architectures. In MAS, the need for scalable coordination, low-latency communication, and centralized or hybrid control strategies is even more pronounced [107]. The inherent parallelism of MAS requires not only intelligent control strategies but also efficient computation offloading and system-wide synchronization [108, 109].

The convergence of edge computing, low-latency 5G networking [18, 110], and containerized orchestration frameworks such as k8s offers a promising pathway for real-time MAS deployments [111]. Edge architectures are increasingly used to host decision-making modules such as SLAM [55, 112], task allocation [113], or visual perception [114], thereby freeing resource-constrained robots from running compute-heavy modules locally.

This chapter presents two complementary frameworks that leverage these technological advances for MAS: (i) an Edge-based Centralized NMPC (E-CNMPC) architecture that enables real-time, optimal trajectory control for multiple ground or aerial robots, and (ii) a hybrid CBF-based architecture that partitions constraint management between the edge and the robots, enabling scalable and safe operation of heterogeneous UAV and Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV) teams [115, 116].

4.2 Contributions

The chapter delivers several key contributions across both centralized and hybrid control strategies for robotic MAS such as: (i) a novel edge-based framework for enabling centralized control for MAS; (ii) seamless scalability via containerization and orchestration; (iii) a hybrid edge-assisted architecture for improved management of heterogeneous MAS, and (iv) experimental validation and scalability demonstration of the proposed frameworks.

The main contribution is the development of a novel E-CNMPC architecture that offloads centralized control of MAS to an edge-based k8s cluster, thus enabling optimal trajectory tracking and swarm coordination while satisfying hard constraints such as inter-agent collision avoidance and swarm cohesion. This work demonstrates how real-time, large-scale centralized control becomes feasible through edge computing, overcoming onboard limitations.

Moreover, these frameworks leverages containerized deployments and k8s orchestration to provide scalable, resilient, and hardware-agnostic control system execution, thus enabling real-time reconfiguration, redeployment, and dynamic resource allocation as the number of agents or mission complexity evolves.

Additionally, this work proposes a control architecture for safe, coordinated task execution involving aerial and ground robots (UAVs and UGVs). It introduces edge-offloaded centralized constraint management combined with onboard CBF-based controllers to enforce intra-layer and inter-layer safety constraints, to support deliberate physical interaction tasks such as landing UAVs on moving UGVs, while enabling multi-robot scalability.

Finally, the thesis validates both frameworks in experimental and simulation environments with ground robots, and heterogeneous UAV-UGV systems. Thus, demonstrating the robustness, scalability, and coordination performance of the proposed architectures under real-time constraints and communication imperfections.

4.3 Edge-Based Centralized Control Architectures

The integration of edge computing into robotic systems has emerged as a revolutionary approach to support time-critical, computationally demanding tasks, especially in applications involving MAS coordination. Numerous robotic applications have leveraged cloud or edge infrastructures for offloading various processes, including mapping, localization, and visual processing. For instance, robotic frameworks using ROS have been integrated with cloud backends for task execution, visualization, and control as demonstrated in [117–119]. Similarly, in [120], ground robots autonomously navigated in data center environments while offloading measurement and visualization processes to the cloud.

In the control domain, MPC has garnered attention due to its ability to handle system dynamics, predict future states, and impose complex constraints. Several works have investigated the offloading of MPC to cloud or edge systems in single-agent scenarios, such as [63, 99, 121–123]. In the previous chapters, for example, edge-based NMPC controllers are applied to a single UAV, confirming the viability of offloading heavy control algorithms to low-latency edge clusters. These implementations, however, are not designed and applied to robotic MAS.

When extended to MAS, the control problem becomes significantly more complex. A clear distinction can be drawn between centralized and distributed control approaches. Distributed MPC has been widely studied for MAS due to its scalability and reduced computational burden [124–128]. These approaches enable local decision-making and decentralization of computational load. However, distributed control often suffers from suboptimal coordination, increased communication overhead, and lack of global constraint enforcement, particularly for collision avoidance or formation-keeping tasks [129–132].

Conversely, centralized MPC frameworks offer superior performance in optimizing collective behaviors by solving a global optimization problem for all agents simultaneously. These schemes have been explored in the context of platoon control [133], UAV formation placement [134], and narrow-environment navigation [135]. A comparative study in [108] highlights that centralized schemes outperform distributed methods for small to medium-sized teams but face scalability issues due to scheduling delays and computational limitations as the number of agents grows.

Despite their advantages, centralized approaches remain rare in practical MAS deployments, primarily due to the limitations of onboard resources and the absence of architectures that support high-performance real-time execution. This gap has prompted the development of offloaded MPC architectures hosted on edge clusters, such as the proposed E-CNMPC framework published in [33]. Unlike cloud-based implementations, edge systems significantly reduce the end-to-end latency, making them suitable for real-time MAS control.

In addition to control logic, the deployment environment plays a critical role. The introduction of containerized robotics and k8s-based orchestration has enabled modular, scalable, and fault-tolerant robotic architectures. Works like [56, 111, 136] propose containerized controllers and k8s frameworks to manage deployment across edge nodes. Other related efforts include resource orchestration using stochastic optimization [57], and ROS-integrated monitoring and deployment systems [53, 54].

The proposed E-CNMPC framework builds on these foundations by combining a centralized control strategy with a containerized, ROS-compatible edge infrastructure. It supports real-time, scalable deployment for multi-robot systems by (i) solving a centralized optimization problem that includes hard constraints for collision avoidance and swarm cohesion, and (ii) allowing on-demand computational scaling based on the number of agents and control complexity. The inclusion of hard inter-agent distance constraints allows the controller to enforce collective behaviors such as formation keeping or dispersion, a notable improvement over classical approaches like leader-follower.

By exploiting container orchestration tools such as k8s, and deploying the control pipeline as a cloud-native service, E-CNMPC enables hardware abstraction, resilient deployment, and operator transparency, ensuring that users can interface with the control system from any lightweight client without needing specialized computation capabilities.

In summary, while prior research has successfully demonstrated edge-based offloading for robotic tasks such as perception and single-agent control, the E-CNMPC framework uniquely integrates real-time centralized control, swarm-level constraint enforcement, and cloud-native edge orchestration to address the scalability, latency, and coordination challenges of robotic MAS.

4.3.1 Multiple Ground Autonomous Agents

This section presents the edge-based centralized architecture applied to a MAS of robotic UGVs. The core concept involves centralized coordination through a NMPC strategy offloaded to an edge cluster. As illustrated in Figure 4.1, each agent sends its current state to the edge node, which computes a global control solution based on the aggregated system state. Despite the spatial distribution of agents, the collected data are processed as a unified dataset to satisfy the input requirements of the E-CNMPCC.

Figure 4.1: Block diagram of the E-CNMPCC framework including the k8s architecture for controlling a MAS.

The edge controller generates control actions for each agent by considering the entire system’s dynamics, enabling coordinated behavior, optimal trajectory generation, and collision avoidance. The prediction horizon of the E-CNMPCC can be extended to produce smoother, safer trajectories at the cost of increased computational complexity. This computational burden is alleviated by leveraging edge computing resources, which enable real-time control even under high-dimensional optimization constraints.

Each robot transmits its state vector $\mathbf{x}_i(t)$ to the edge cluster, where $i \in 1, 2, \dots, n_a$ and n_a is the number of agents of the MAS. Due to UL delay, the received states are represented as $\mathbf{x}_i(t - \tau_u(t))$. After solving the NMPC problem, the control commands $\mathbf{u}_i(t)$ are transmitted to the agents, arriving with a DL delay $\tau_d(t)$ and thus the applied commands are $\mathbf{u}_i(t - \tau_d(t))$.

4.3.2 Centralized Nonlinear Model Predictive Control Scheme

The base E-CNMPCC module is based on the preliminary work discussed in the previous sections. However, unlike the previous chapters, which focused on aerial robots, the present formulation targets non-holonomic UGVs regulated by nonlinear kinematic constraints. The E-CNMPCC framework is reformulated to support coordination, safety, and swarm behavior across multiple ground agents.

System Dynamics

Each ground robot is modeled using a nonlinear unicycle-type kinematic model described by (4.1).

$$\dot{p}_x(t) = \cos(q_\psi(t)) \cdot u_v(t) \quad (4.1a)$$

$$\dot{p}_y(t) = \sin(q_\psi(t)) \cdot u_v(t) \quad (4.1b)$$

$$\dot{q}_\psi(t) = u_w(t), \quad (4.1c)$$

where $\mathbf{p}(t) \triangleq [p_x(t) \ p_y(t)]^\top$ and $\mathbf{v}(t) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t)$ describe the position and velocity states and $q_\psi(t)$ is the heading state. It is assumed that the ground robot takes input commands in the form of a forward/backward velocity $u_v(t)$ and an angular rate command as $u_w(t)$. Each agents' states is described as $\mathbf{x}_i(t) \triangleq [p_{x,i}(t) \ p_{y,i}(t) \ q_{\psi,i}(t)]^\top$ and inputs $\mathbf{u}_i(t) \triangleq [u_{v,i}(t) \ u_{w,i}(t)]^\top$.

In the centralized formulation, all agent states are aggregated into a stacked state vector $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_1^\top \ \mathbf{x}_2^\top \ \dots \ \mathbf{x}_{n_a}^\top]^\top$, and control input $\mathbf{u} \triangleq [\mathbf{u}_1^\top \ \mathbf{u}_2^\top \ \dots \ \mathbf{u}_{n_a}^\top]^\top$.

Cost Function

The control objective is discretized with a sampling time T_s and it is formulated over a finite prediction horizon h , using a discrete-time Euler approximation of the dynamics, $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \zeta(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k)$. At each timestep k , the cost function is defined by (4.2).

$$\begin{aligned} J_c = & \sum_{m=0}^h \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} \underbrace{\left\{ \left(\mathbf{p}_{i, k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{p}_{i, k+m|k} \right)^\top \mathbf{Q}_p \left(\mathbf{p}_{i, k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{p}_{i, k+m|k} \right) \right\}}_{\text{Position cost}} \\ & + \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{u}_{i, k+m|k} - \mathbf{u}_{i, k+m-1|k} \right)^\top \mathbf{Q}_{\Delta u} \left(\mathbf{u}_{i, k+m|k} - \mathbf{u}_{i, k+m-1|k} \right)}_{\text{Smoothness cost}} \\ & + \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{u}_{i, k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{u}_{i, k+m|k} \right)^\top \mathbf{Q}_u \left(\mathbf{u}_{i, k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{u}_{i, k+m|k} \right)}_{\text{Actuation cost}} \\ & + \underbrace{Q_\psi \left(1 - \cos(q_{\psi, i} - q_{\psi, i}^{\text{ref}}) \right)}_{\text{Heading cost}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

where the cost matrices $\mathbf{Q}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$, $Q_\psi \in \mathbb{R}$, $\mathbf{Q}_u, \mathbf{Q}_{\Delta u} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ weigh the position and heading error, control effort, and rate of change of inputs, respectively. While the other terms follow the classical quadratic penalties, the penalty on the heading state follows a different form. The centralized scheme requires that all agents share the same coordinate frame for their states, therefore such the 2π -modularity of the heading state q_ψ must be captured properly to avoid the discontinuity at $q_\psi \sim \pm\pi$. Although this approach is computationally complex, the utilized solver [69] in combination with the assistance from the edge offloading can overcome these limitations.

Safety and Collision Avoidance Constraints

To ensure safe operation and enforce minimum distances between UGVs, set-exclusion constraints for pairs are introduced. For agents i and l , a hard constraint ensures their mutual distance exceeds a safety radius r_{safe} , expressed by (4.3).

$$C_{\text{safe}}^{l,i}(\mathbf{x}_k) := \left[r_{\text{safe}}^2 - (p_{x,i,k+m|k} - p_{x,l,k+m|k})^2 - (p_{y,i,k+m|k} - p_{y,l,k+m|k})^2 \right]_+ = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

Similarly, an additional expression $C_{\text{circle}}^i(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{z}^{\text{obs}})$ is formed as a general static circle-type obstacle that all agents should avoid using the same kind of circle-expression (4.4), where $\mathbf{z}^{\text{obs}} \triangleq [r_{\text{obs}} \quad r_{\text{safe}} \quad (\mathbf{p}^{\text{obs}})^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4$.

$$C_{\text{circle}}^i(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{z}^{\text{obs}}) = \left[(r_{\text{obs}} + r_{\text{safe}})^2 - (p_{x,i,k+m} - p_{x,k+m}^{\text{obs}})^2 - (p_{y,i,k+m} - p_{y,k+m}^{\text{obs}})^2 \right]_+ = 0, \quad (4.4)$$

Swarming Constraints

To promote cohesive group behavior, an upper bound r_{swarm} is imposed on the distance between agents to maintain swarming behavior (4.5).

$$C_{\text{swarm}}^{l,i}(\mathbf{x}_k) := \left[-r_{\text{swarm}}^2 + (p_{x,i,k+m|k} - p_{x,l,k+m|k})^2 + (p_{y,i,k+m|k} - p_{y,l,k+m|k})^2 \right]_+ = 0 \quad (4.5)$$

These constraints set a maximum allowed distance between agents in the system defined by r_{swarm} , and are imposed along the prediction horizon for all agents.

Optimization

The complete NMPC optimization problem is defined in (4.6).

$$\underset{\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{x}_k}{\text{Minimize}} J_c(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k; \mathbf{u}_{k-1|k}) \quad (4.6a)$$

$$\text{s.t.: } \mathbf{x}_{k+m+1|k} = \zeta(\mathbf{x}_{k+m|k}, \mathbf{u}_{k+m|k})$$

$$m = 0, \dots, h-1 \quad (4.6b)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k} \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max}$$

$$m = 0, \dots, h \quad (4.6c)$$

Constraints (4.3) – (4.5)

$$i, l = 1, \dots, n_a \quad (4.6d)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,k|k} = \mathbf{x}_{i,k}$$

$$i = 1, \dots, n_a \quad (4.6e)$$

$\zeta(\cdot)$ is the discretized system model, and J_c is the cost defined in (4.2). Control inputs are subject to hard bounds, and all safety and swarm constraints are enforced as equality constraints using a quadratic penalty method [72].

Solver & Computational Considerations

The optimization problem is solved using the optimization engine solver [69], which supports embedded implementation of constrained CNMPC using operator splitting and fast gradient methods. The use of quadratic penalty methods enables systematic enforcement of nonlinear equality constraints, where constraint violation is penalized iteratively until a specified feasibility threshold is met.

Given the rapid growth in the number of constraints (especially with increasing n_a and horizon h), the problem becomes computationally intensive. However, this complexity is well accommodated by the edge-based deployment, which provides scalable computational resources. This enables the formulation and real-time solution of large centralized problems that would be infeasible on onboard hardware.

4.3.3 Evaluation & Results

This section presents the experimental validation of the proposed E-CNMPC framework for coordinated control of multiple ground robots. A series of experiments was conducted to evaluate performance in terms of constraint satisfaction, trajectory tracking, computational load, and network-induced delay.

Experimental Setup

The MAS consists of four TurtleBot (TB) ground robots [137], whose position and orientation states are acquired through a Vicon MoCap system [138]. The edge system is hosted on a k8s cluster, with hardware specifications resembling the ones listed in Section 2. Control commands are executed in a containerized E-CNMPC pod deployed on the edge worker nodes of the k8s cluster.

Figure 4.2: Experimental setup A and B of the proposed framework.

Two network configurations were tested, illustrated in Figure 4.2: (i) in setup A, the edge cluster connects only to the TB network (Wi-Fi) and MoCap data is relayed through a separate workstation, while (ii) in setup B, the edge cluster connects to both the TB network (Wi-Fi) and MoCap network, enabling direct access to state data.

E-CNMPC Performance Under Varying Horizon

Figures 4.3–4.5 present the minimum inter-agent distances and computation times obtained under three different prediction horizons: 20, 40, and 60 steps. When the prediction horizon is limited to 20 steps, the agents display unstable and unsafe behavior, due to the controller’s limited ability to predict future interactions. Increasing the horizon to 40 steps improves performance, as the controller can anticipate potential conflicts earlier and adjust trajectories accordingly, however, intermittent proximity violations still occur, particularly in scenarios involving rapid changes in relative motion between agents. At 60 steps, the system achieves fully stable and safe operation, maintaining all inter-agent distances above the defined safety threshold. This demonstrates that extending the prediction horizon enhances the controller’s capacity to foresee and mitigate interaction conflicts, resulting in smoother and safer cooperative maneuvers. Although longer horizons increase the computational load, the edge-based implementation effectively accommodates this added complexity, ensuring real-time operation without compromising performance.

Figure 4.3: Minimum inter-agent distances (top), and solver computation time (bottom) for 20-step prediction horizons.

Figure 4.4: Minimum inter-agent distances (top), and solver computation time (bottom) for 40-step prediction horizons.

Figure 4.5: Minimum inter-agent distances (top), and solver computation time (bottom) for 60-step prediction horizons.

However, increased horizon results in longer computation time. The use of edge resources ensures feasibility even at 60 steps. The solver consistently meets real-time requirements due to offloading.

Effect of Initial Tolerance on Solver Convergence

Figure 4.6 compares solver behavior under relaxed initial tolerance (10^{-3}) compared to the stricter default tolerance (10^{-5}). A higher tolerance results in faster convergence, but sacrifices solution quality, and robots diverge from reference paths and occasionally reach invalid states. The results confirm the need for a careful trade-off between solver accuracy and computation time.

Figure 4.6: Minimum inter-agent distances (top), and solver computation time (bottom) for 60-step prediction horizon, with initial solver tolerance set to 10^{-3} .

Swarming Behavior & Obstacle Avoidance

In Figure 4.7, the system effectively maintains both the minimum inter-agent distance, based on the safety constraints, required for collision avoidance and the maximum allowable distance to preserve swarm cohesion throughout the mission. The agents dynamically adjust their paths while ensuring the group remains tightly coordinated to fulfill the swarm constraints, demonstrating the controller's ability to uphold spatial relationships across the team under nominal conditions.

Figure 4.7: Swarm behavior enforcement: Inter-agent distances (top), and solver computation time (bottom) for four agents with 60-step prediction horizon and default tolerance.

Figure 4.8: Swarm behavior with obstacle avoidance: Inter-agent distances (top), and solver computation time (bottom) during static obstacle navigation.

In a more challenging scenario shown in Figure 4.8, a static obstacle is introduced into the environment. Despite this added constraint, the controller successfully ensures that all agents re-plan their trajectories to safely navigate around the obstacle while still maintaining the desired inter-agent distances. The simultaneous satisfaction of collision avoidance, swarming, and obstacle avoidance constraints highlights the robustness of the proposed edge-offloaded centralized controller in managing multiple concurrent objectives in real-time.

Trajectory Performance Evaluation

Figure 4.9 illustrates the resulting trajectories of the ground robots across the three previously described experimental scenarios, each designed to evaluate distinct aspects of MAS coordination. (i) Agents are tasked with exchanging positions, requiring the E-CNMPC controller to compute globally coordinated trajectories that ensure safe, smooth transitions across overlapping paths; (ii) evaluates a leader-follower setup, in which only a single robot (the leader) is assigned a goal, and the remaining agents follow while maintaining the predefined swarm cohesion and collision avoidance constraints, and (iii) builds on the second by introducing a static obstacle into the shared workspace.

Figure 4.9: Trajectories of four TBs in three scenarios: (a) position exchange returning to initial locations; (b) swarm formation following a leader to a goal; (c) swarm formation with obstacle avoidance. In (b) and (c), \circ indicates start and \times end positions. Dashed large circles represent maximum inter-agent distance; small circles indicate minimum collision-avoidance threshold.

Network Delay Evaluation

The system's responsiveness was evaluated under both network setups. The RTT is computed as:

$$\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) = \tau_{\text{u}}(t) + \tau_{\text{p}}(t) + \tau_{\text{d}}(t), \quad (4.7)$$

where τ_{u} and τ_{d} denote UL and DL communication time, and τ_{p} is the NMPC execution (processing) time.

Figures 4.10–4.12 present the measured timing components of the communication pipeline, where background traffic has been inserted to emulate realistic scenarios. Under setup A, where the edge unit receives motion capture data via an intermediary workstation over Wi-Fi, both UL and DL delays are noticeably higher, averaging 124.7 ms and 214.3 ms, respectively, with peak values reaching 917.9 ms for UL and 793 ms for DL. In contrast, setup B, where the edge unit connects directly to the MoCap system, significantly reduces UL delay, achieving a mean of 10 ms and a maximum of 98.2 ms. The DL delay remains unchanged across both configurations, as it shares the same Wi-Fi transmission route to the robots.

Figure 4.10: UL transmission delay from ground robots to the edge cluster (setup A).

Figure 4.11: UL transmission delay from ground robots to the edge cluster (setup B).

The processing time, shown in Figure 4.13, remains stable (mean: 100.6 ms, max: 168.2 ms), indicating the edge machine is capable of solving the CNMPC even under high constraints.

Figure 4.12: DL transmission delay from the edge cluster to the ground robots.

Figure 4.13: Computation time required for executing the E-CNMPC controller at each step.

Figure 4.14: RTT variation for setup A and setup B.

The resulting RTTs are plotted in Figure 4.14. Setup B yields lower average RTT (325.3 ms vs. 448.6 ms), confirming the benefit of direct MoCap to edge connection.

Computation Load & Edge Resource Utilization

Figure 4.15 shows the CPU usage and corresponding solver compute time. The k8s pod dynamically scales its resource usage based on task complexity. CPU usage peaks above 90% during moments of high constraint activity (e.g., near collision or tight swarming), confirming effective resource utilization.

Figure 4.15: Solver computation time (top), and CPU usage of the E-CNMPC k8s pod (bottom) during task execution.

The solver maintains real-time performance, even during computational spikes caused by reduced tolerance, long horizon, or active constraints.

The experimental evaluation demonstrates that the proposed E-CNMPC framework enables safe and coordinated control of multiple ground robots under tight timing and resource constraints. The use of edge computing allows the system to scale to complex tasks involving long prediction horizons, strict solver tolerances, and MAS constraints such as swarming and collision avoidance. These results validate the feasibility and scalability of edge-offloaded centralized NMPC for modern robotic MAS operating in real-world settings.

4.4 Edge-Assisted Control Barrier Functions

CBFs have emerged as a promising approach for enforcing safety constraints in MAS, particularly under real-time constraints and limited onboard resources [139]. CBFs ensure forward invariance of safe sets while allowing minimally invasive corrections to a nominal controller. These characteristics make them suitable for reactive navigation and coordinated control tasks.

The deployment of heterogeneous MAS, including UAVs and UGVs, in industrial automation and logistics applications has highlighted the need for scalable and safe control strategies [104, 106]. In such settings, UAVs perform vertical inspection, mapping, or delivery tasks, while UGVs provide heavy-duty transport and extended operation time. When operating together, especially in shared task spaces, precise coordination is required not only within aerial or ground layers but also across them [115, 140].

A particularly challenging scenario arises during UAV landings on moving UGVs. This task requires soft-contact-based control, where the UAV must safely descend, track the UGV in motion, and avoid nearby obstacles or other UAVs. CBFs are ideal for modeling and enforcing such complex, layered constraints. Recent works [141–143] use CBFs in manipulation, vision-based docking, and constrained landings, but many are limited to single-robot setups or final landing phases without coordination with other mobile robots.

The work builds on these foundations and proposes a hybrid edge-based framework where real-time safety constraints are enforced onboard using CBFs, while higher-level planning and coordination are offloaded to edge servers. This design allows UAVs and UGVs to coordinate in real-time, land simultaneously without airspace conflicts, and dynamically adjust their trajectories based on environmental feedback. Unlike previous approaches [116, 144, 145], the solution incorporates both intra-layer and inter-layer safety constraints, including dynamic obstacle avoidance, physical interaction planning, and scalable deployment across large robot teams.

By leveraging edge computing, local real-time responsiveness is preserved while offloading resource-intensive coordination to scalable edge nodes. This balance allows for safety-critical CBF execution onboard, even in MAS, where constraint dimensionality increases rapidly with agent count. Experimental results in both real and simulated environments validate the feasibility of the proposed approach for UAV-UGV task coordination and physical interaction.

4.4.1 System Overview & Problem Formulation

This section presents an edge-assisted control framework tailored for multi-robot systems composed of heterogeneous UAVs and UGVs. The key contribution of this work lies in the hybrid control architecture, where an edge cluster coordinates safety-critical constraints and offloads computationally intensive modules in a centralized manner, while low-level controllers enforce real-time safety onboard each robot. The framework ensures scalability, safety, and coordination across multiple UAV-UGV pairs operating within confined and shared task spaces. The concept is visualized in Figure 4.16 for three UAVs and three UGVs on the world frame. As an illustration of potential constraints in the operation of UAV-UGV pairs, the figure highlights all unsafe regions of operations for UAV 1.

Figure 4.16: A schematic of robots with their associated coordinate frames. The translucent shapes around the robots illustrate UAV 1’s unsafe regions of operation. The region varies depending on the interaction between the concerned robots.

We consider a cooperative robotic MAS consisting of UAV-UGV pairs executing aerial and ground-level tasks in parallel. Each UAV is paired with a corresponding UGV that it returns to after task completion, facilitating safe landing and battery efficiency. The UAVs are modeled using second-order quadrotor dynamics, and UGVs are represented using a differential-drive unicycle model. The coordination challenge is formulated under multiple safety-critical constraints including: (i) Aerial-Aerial (AA) separation for UAVs to avoid aerodynamic downwash; (ii) Ground-Ground (GG) separation for UGVs to avoid collisions; (iii) Aerial-Ground-Corresponding (AGC) interaction to enable vertical landing; (iv) Aerial-Ground-Other (AGO) separation to prevent UAVs from obstructing each other’s landing spaces, and (v) task-space bounds for both robot types. The architecture aims to ensure safe interaction through CBFs while supporting decentralized execution and efficient resource allocation.

4.4.2 Edge-Based Hybrid Control Architecture

The hybrid control strategy proposed in this work, illustrated in Figure 4.17, forms the core architectural contribution of this thesis. It is designed around a hybrid structure that distinctly separates high-level centralized functions offloaded to the edge cluster from low-level, real-time control processes executing onboard. This separation is not only a response to the limitations of onboard processing and communication in MAS but also a strategic enabler for scalability, modularity, and resilience.

Figure 4.17: Edge architecture, where each robot has its own decentralized control block and receives CBF constraints and its position estimation from the edge cluster.

At the upper tier, a centralized edge cluster performs computationally intensive and coordination heavy tasks. This includes the localization unit for aggregating and distributing position estimates, the task assignment module for handling task scheduling and distribution, and most critically, the Watcher module, which is responsible for detecting inter-agent conflicts and generating CBF constraints in real-time. These constraints encapsulate safety, collision avoidance, swarming behavior, and airspace coordination, challenges that grow combinatorially with the number of robots.

At the lower tier, each individual robot, either UAV or UGV, is equipped with a lightweight Decentralized Control Block (DCB) that is executed entirely onboard to preserve low-latency responsiveness. These DCBs are designed to operate autonomously even in the presence of intermittent network delays or edge-side failures. Each DCB consists of three main modules: (i) a nominal position controller, typically based on a go-to-goal strategy; (ii) a safety filter, implemented as a constrained optimization layer that incorporates first-order, time-varying CBFs received from the Watcher, and (iii) a low-level actuator controller, which transforms the filtered high-level commands into platform-specific motor inputs. This architectural layering enables robust execution of safety-critical behaviors while reducing onboard computational burden.

For UGVs, a Near-Identity Diffeomorphism (NID) transformation is applied to the unicycle dynamics, effectively shifting the control point to a location in front of the robot’s center of mass. This transformation enables a linear representation of otherwise non-holonomic dynamics, thus simplifying the incorporation of CBF constraints within the safety filter. The transformed control commands are then mapped to linear and angular velocities and subsequently to wheel actuation commands.

For UAVs, a cascaded control structure is adopted. Here, CBFs are embedded between the outer-loop position controller and the inner-loop velocity controller. The filtered velocity setpoints are used to generate thrust vectors and attitude references. These are then tracked using geometric attitude controllers implemented onboard. This architecture ensures that the safety guarantees are not only preserved but are also fully decoupled from nominal trajectory tracking, thereby enabling robust execution even under aggressive motion or task changes.

In summary, this hybrid edge-assisted architecture achieves a critical balance between centralized situational awareness and decentralized real-time actuation. By offloading constraint generation and coordination logic to the edge while maintaining autonomous safety-critical execution onboard, the framework enables scalable, safe, and high-performance coordination of heterogeneous multi-robot systems operating in constrained environments.

4.4.3 Control Barrier Function Implementation

CBFs are employed to impose safety constraints arising from the previously defined inter-robot interaction models. These CBFs are designed to ensure that agents respect a wide range of collision avoidance and coordination constraints, across AA, GG, AGC, and AGO interactions, while continuing to execute their assigned tasks. Within the architecture, the Watcher module centrally monitors the state of all robots, detects potential conflicts, and generates the corresponding constraint gradients based on current system dynamics. These constraint matrices are then transmitted to each robot's DCB, where they are integrated into a Quadratic Program (QP) that adjusts the robot's nominal control input in a minimally invasive manner.

Each CBF is shown to enforce its associated constraint under time-varying conditions. Notably, the AGC landing constraint is validated as a proper time-varying CBF ensuring forward invariance and convergence to safe states.

4.4.4 Evaluation & Results

The architecture was experimentally validated on three UAV-UGV pairs in a warehouse-like scenario. The UAVs completed inspection tasks before returning to and landing on their corresponding UGVs, with key outcomes: (i) the AGC constraint enabled vertical landing without requiring external planners; (ii) AA, GG, and AGO constraints ensured collision-free interactions between heterogeneous agents, and (iii) task-space constraints maintained robots within operational bounds. Figure 4.18 illustrates successful trajectory tracking and inter-robot constraint enforcement.

Figure 4.18: Circles highlight the UAVs, and plain and dashed arrows respectively point at the directions of the motions of the UAVs and UGVs. Experiment sequence: (a) UAVs and UGVs go to their first tasks from their initial positions; (b) UAVs return from their first tasks; (c) UAVs land on their UGVs (UAV 3 is yet to land); (d) UAVs take-off to go to their second tasks; (e) UAVs land after their second tasks.

Scalability via Simulation

To validate the scalability of the proposed hybrid control architecture, a series of simulated experiments were conducted in the `Gazebo` simulation using heterogeneous robot teams of 5, 10, and 20 UAV-UGV pairs, as illustrated in Figure 4.19. Each robot operated within a `Docker` container, with resource constraints configured to emulate typical embedded platforms such as the `Raspberry Pi 4`. This containerized deployment ensured a realistic assessment of the computational limitations found in real-world robotic systems.

Figure 4.19: `Gazebo` environment with twenty UAV-UGV pairs. Landing platforms (orange-colored discs) are attached to the top of the UGVs.

Figures 4.20 and 4.21 present the CPU usage profiles of the decentralized controllers and the centralized edge modules, respectively. The results show that the onboard control loops remained bounded in CPU utilization, even as the number of agents increased. While the UAV containers occasionally approached high CPU loads, particularly due to the more demanding 3D CBF, based filtering, the system continued to operate within feasible resource limits. This validates the suitability of the proposed architecture for low-power embedded devices.

At the same time, the computationally intensive high-level modules, such as the `Watcher` and the task assignment unit, were successfully offloaded to the edge cluster. These components exhibited increased CPU usage as the number of agents grew, as shown in Figure 4.21. This is acceptable, as the edge machine can be provisioned with greater computational resources and can scale vertically or horizontally depending on deployment needs.

These results highlight the core advantage of the proposed hybrid architecture, by decoupling low-level safety-critical control (which remains onboard) from high-level constraint evaluation (offloaded to the edge), the system maintains real-time performance even as the scale of the robot team grows. Furthermore, the ability to modularly scale the edge cluster's resources reinforces its role as a central coordination backbone in robotic MAS operating under resource and safety constraints.

Figure 4.20: CPU usage of (a) UAV containers; (b) UGV containers; (c) the Watcher in the master container for the simulation with 20 pairs. The black dashed lines represent the bounds of the CPU utilization.

Figure 4.21: CPU usage of the edge cluster running computationally intensive tasks.

4.5 Concluding Remarks

This chapter presented edge-oriented architectural frameworks for scalable and collaborative control of robotic MAS. The primary focus was placed on the E-CNMPC framework, which enables optimized coordination of multiple ground robots by offloading complex control computation to a nearby edge cluster. Through this architecture, resource-constrained agents can benefit from advanced centralized control strategies without compromising real-time performance or system responsiveness. Additionally, a hybrid architecture with centralized components, offloaded to the edge cluster, and distributed low-level modules is presented for edge-assisted systems.

The E-CNMPC framework demonstrated how offloading NMPC to the edge not only alleviates the computational burden on individual agents but also enhances the overall system performance in terms of trajectory smoothness, collision avoidance, and swarm cohesion. A key benefit of centralization in this context is the ability to generate globally optimal solutions for the MAS by jointly considering the trajectories and constraints of all agents. However, such centralized schemes typically introduce high computational overhead, particularly with increasing agent count or longer prediction horizons. By leveraging containerized deployment and scalable k8s-based edge clusters, the proposed architecture achieved real-time execution even in dense MAS scenarios, highlighting the feasibility of centralized control for MAS under practical resource constraints.

The experimental results further validated the flexibility of the architecture, showing how increased prediction horizons and stricter solver tolerances could be supported thanks to the edge's computational capacity. Additionally, the latency measurements and RTT analyses underscored the importance of network topology and communication routing in sustaining closed-loop performance. Importantly, the modular design of the architecture also allows for the dynamic tuning of parameters such as swarm constraints, obstacle avoidance, and optimization granularity to meet mission-specific requirements. However, limitations in the capacity of computational complexity of the system are observed, which need to be addressed and resolved.

Complementing the centralized framework, the chapter also introduced an edge-assisted hybrid control architecture for heterogeneous UAV-UGV systems. This second architecture distributed safety-critical control loops onboard each robot while offloading constraint detection and conflict resolution to an edge-based Watcher module. By combining the low-latency requirements of onboard safety enforcement with the global situational awareness of the edge, the system enabled safe inter-robot interactions, landing maneuvers, and aerial-ground coordination, while maintaining scalability and fault tolerance.

Despite the demonstrated effectiveness of both edge-based architectures, one emerging challenge remains, mainly managing the dynamic allocation of computational resources at the edge as system demands vary. As the number of agents increases, or as mission complexity changes over time (e.g., due to adaptive prediction horizons or dynamic constraint enforcement), the computational load on the edge fluctuates significantly. Efficient and adaptive resource allocation becomes essential to ensure QoS, maintain real-time performance, and avoid overloading edge servers.

This leads directly to the focus of the next chapter, which explores adaptive and dynamic resource allocation strategies in edge-enabled robotic MAS. Chapter 5 will address how advanced orchestration tools, such as container scheduling, vertical and horizontal scaling, and load balancing, can be integrated into edge infrastructures to manage the computational demands introduced by centralized control architectures. These mechanisms are critical for enabling resilient, scalable, and mission-adaptive deployments in real-world robotic systems.

Dynamic Resource Allocation

5.1 Overview

The previous chapters explored scalable edge architectures for both single-agent and MAS, focusing on addressing time delay challenges and centralized control frameworks. As these systems scale in size, and complexity, the importance of dynamic and efficient resource management becomes paramount. In particular, centralized control methods such as CNMPC, while effective for orchestrating collective robot behavior, impose varying and often growing computational demands depending on the number of agents and prediction horizons involved.

This chapter addresses the critical challenge of dynamic resource allocation within such edge-controlled MAS. It focuses on how to adaptively provision and scale computational resources in real-time, ensuring that the performance benefits of centralized control architectures are retained, even under shifting mission parameters and network conditions.

In that end, cloud computing has been a major technology across various applications, including robotics, offering scalable computing resources and storage [38, 39]. However, its noticeable latency poses challenges for time-sensitive robotic tasks [40], such as collision avoidance, where both rapid data processing and minimal time delays are critical [41]. Even though edge computing, does not provide the “near-limitless” resources of cloud computing, it offers a potential solution to these extensive delays [43]. Its advantage lies in the proximity of edge servers to the data sources, drastically reducing the time delays inherent in data transmission to and from cloud servers. This proximity is particularly beneficial for tasks requiring real-time processing, making edge computing an appealing alternative for robotics applications where quick decision-making is essential [12, 44].

While various robotic subjects may benefit from edge offloading, such as autonomous driving [146], MAS system applications present unique benefits but also challenges [39]. These systems can be tackled either in centralized or distributed approaches, based on the application’s requirements. Importantly, the real-time requirements and the size of the MAS should be carefully considered. Thereby, edge computing can provide distributed processing and centralized logic to respect these requirements.

Employing a centralized scheme for real-time coordination in MAS provides the potential to significantly enhance system performance by effectively delegating tasks and optimizing behavior [147]. However, such an approach demands computational units that are capable of managing substantial workloads. The integration of cloud and edge computing technologies presents a promising approach to increase the scalability and robustness of robotic MAS applications, addressing the computational and latency challenges inherent in centralized control schemes as centralized MPC and NMPC.

Building on this foundation, this chapter presents an edge-native framework for scalable and adaptive resource management. It introduces a hierarchy of mechanisms for dynamically scheduling, provisioning, and optimizing the deployment of centralized control modules based on system needs and available resources. Key technical components include: (i) scaling methodologies that distinguish between vertical and horizontal strategies for resource and controller scaling; (ii) a formal MAS CNMPC formulation that serves as the underlying control structure, along with mission planning and system-level integration; (iii) a reactive scheduling mechanism that adapts controller deployment in real-time based on agent count and system state; (iv) a predictive resource allocation framework, leveraging regression models and control laws to preemptively allocate resources and minimize RTT delays, and (v) an optimization layer that jointly considers control performance and edge resource constraints to achieve minimal-cost deployment at runtime.

Altogether, this chapter forms the cornerstone of the thesis by demonstrating how intelligent resource orchestration can unlock the full potential of edge-powered, centralized robotic MAS control in real-world deployments.

5.2 Contributions

This chapter presents the core contributions of the thesis, focusing on dynamic resource allocation for edge-enabled centralized control of MAS. While previous chapters established the architectural and algorithmic foundations of edge-based control for time-critical and computationally constrained systems, this chapter advances the state-of-the-art by introducing a dynamic resource allocation layer that enables robust, scalable, and efficient closed-loop control in dynamic MAS scenarios. This layer bridges the gap between control theory and computational orchestration, allowing the control system to adapt in real time to fluctuations in computational load, network conditions, and agent count. In doing so, it lays the groundwork for autonomous edge orchestration for robotic MAS.

The key contributions of this work are (i) dynamic deployment of centralized controllers; (ii) dynamic resource allocation and vertical scaling; (iii) optimization-based controller assignment and load balancing; (iv) stability-aware resource control for closed-loop systems, and (v) integration of mission planning and resource-aware scheduling

A novel scheduling architecture is introduced to dynamically deploy and reconfigure CNMPCs based on the time-varying number of agents and system requirements. The scheduling mechanism monitors the system in real time and deploys or updates CNMPC instances within the edge cluster accordingly. This allows each controller to efficiently manage a subset of agents, overcoming the static assumptions of fixed-agent designs in prior work.

A regression-based resource modeling framework is developed to estimate the computational complexity of each CNMPC instance based on its prediction horizon and the number of controlled agents. Using this model, a control law is designed to dynamically allocate CPU and memory resources to each controller. The goal is to bound RTT delays and maintain control performance under latency-sensitive conditions.

An optimization problem is formulated to compute the minimum number of CNMPC instances required at each time step to handle all agents, while considering edge resource constraints (e.g., worker node capacities, current load). The optimization determines how many agents each CNMPC should control, the appropriate prediction horizon, and on which edge node it should be deployed. This enables horizontal scaling and intelligent load balancing across the edge cluster.

Unlike previous dynamic offloading strategies that ignore control-theoretic considerations, this work directly links resource allocation to system stability. A feedback mechanism is implemented to monitor RTT delay and reallocate resources when the delay approaches critical thresholds, preserving closed-loop stability even under fluctuating communication and computational loads.

A mission planner interfaces with the scheduling mechanism to handle agent reassignments during runtime. The planner tracks the evolving mission profile and agent distribution and triggers rescheduling events when significant changes occur. This supports real-time adaptability in complex and dynamic environments.

5.3 Scaling Methodologies

Edge computing platforms provide a flexible structure for deploying time-critical robotic applications that exhibit variable computational demands. To ensure both real-time performance and resource efficiency in such systems, intelligent scaling mechanisms must be integrated into the orchestration pipeline. These mechanisms dynamically adapt computational resource allocations and application deployment strategies in response to evolving system conditions, such as changes in workload, control demands, or network performance.

While this thesis presents a detailed implementation of such a framework in the context of CNMPC for MAS, the underlying resource management concepts are broadly applicable. The proposed methodology is agnostic to the specific type of control or planning algorithm, and can be extended to other latency-sensitive, resource-intensive robotic workloads, such as distributed SLAM, MAS task allocation, or perception pipelines. In this chapter, the CNMPC serves as a concrete and demanding use case that naturally exposes the challenges of dynamic resource allocation on edge-based systems.

To effectively manage scalability, this work introduces and distinguishes between two key scaling paradigms: vertical scaling and horizontal scaling. While these terms have roots in traditional cloud computing, they are reinterpreted in this thesis to reflect the real-time constraints, control-level requirements, and orchestration goals of edge-enabled robotic systems.

5.3.1 Resource Provisioning Strategies

Vertical scaling refers to modifying the computational resource allocation (e.g., CPU cores, memory) for a given deployed application, without altering the number of application instances. In the proposed architecture, vertical scaling is applied to dynamically provision computational resources to individual CNMPC controllers running in k8s pods. This ensures that controllers experiencing elevated computational demands, due to factors such as increased agent count or longer prediction horizons, are allocated sufficient resources to maintain real-time responsiveness.

Crucially, vertical scaling is reactive as the system continuously monitors relevant performance metrics such as RTT and increases the resource allocation of a control instance if those metrics exceed predefined thresholds. This approach allows fine-grained tuning of performance, avoids unnecessary replication of controllers, and reduces latency without architectural reconfiguration.

While this work focuses on CNMPC, the same mechanism could be used for any closed-loop module where computational effort varies over time, such as complex optimization-based planners, data association engines, or real-time inference pipelines.

5.3.2 Controller Deployment Strategies

Horizontal scaling, in contrast, refers to deploying multiple instances of the control (or general application) logic across the edge infrastructure. In this work, it is implemented by instantiating multiple CNMPC controllers, each responsible for controlling a dynamically assigned subset of agents. This approach addresses scalability challenges by distributing the control workload, thereby reducing the size and complexity of each optimization problem and preventing overload on any single computational node.

A centralized scheduling mechanism dynamically determines: (i) the number of controller instances needed; (ii) the number of agents each controller should manage, and (iii) the specific edge node each instance should run on, based on resource availability.

This strategy enables load balancing across the cluster and facilitates resilient, mission-aware orchestration, especially important in MAS where agent size, behavior, and task complexity may change over time.

Together, vertical and horizontal scaling form the foundation of the proposed dynamic resource allocation framework. The former ensures adaptation within individual applications, while the latter enables global orchestration across the system. These concepts are implemented through a combination of online monitoring, control logic, and optimization-driven scheduling, all of which will be detailed in the following sections.

While designed around CNMPC control for MAS comprised of UAV, the framework is generalizable and provides a blueprint for resource-adaptive orchestration of robotic workloads on edge computing platforms.

5.4 Centralized Control Framework

Before introducing the proposed reactive scheduling architecture and dynamic resource-aware control, it is essential to clearly define the problem. The MAS edge-based system is presented, followed by an overview of the controllers used in this work, and conclude with infrastructure and deployment setup of the closed-loop systems.

5.4.1 Multi-Agent CNMPC Formulation

While there are numerous critical tasks that resource-constrained robots can transfer to the edge, centralized control offers unique challenges and possibilities. Particularly, CNMPC stands to gain significantly from being carried out on edge servers. Additionally, employing CNMPCs allows evaluating the closed-loop system's stability. The centralized framework that is proposed demonstrates an exceptional capacity to supervise and enhance the performance of multiple agents. For this functionality, agents must first register within the proposed edge-based framework. After registration at every time step t , the edge cluster receives information about the total number of agents, n_a . Following this, agents start sending their states, i.e., positions $\mathbf{p}_i(t)$, velocities $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_i(t)$, and orientations $\mathbf{q}_i(t)$. These state components form the state vector $\mathbf{x}_i(t)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_a$, similarly to the previous chapters. These signals are delayed as they travel from the robots to the edge k8s cluster. Thus, the edge receives the information as $\mathbf{x}_i(t - \tau_u(t))$. Additionally, reference state signals denoted as $\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{ref}}(t)$ are generated by a mission planner, for each agent. The CNMPC algorithms then processes these states to generate control actions for each agent, represented as $\mathbf{u}_i(t)$, aiming to optimize the system's collective action. Consequently, these control actions are sent from the edge k8s cluster back to the agents. To describe this delay, the control actions received by agents are referred to as $\mathbf{u}_i(t - \tau_d(t))$.

System Dynamics

Extensive research has been conducted on using MPC for controlling UAVs flight trajectory, as documented in prior works [148, 149]. This study utilizes CNMPC, which incorporates the UAV model from [68], and leverages the NMPC approach that efficiently compensates for time delays, that was presented in the previous chapters. While the model accounts for delays, still it is important to consider the maximum allowable delay. So sequentially, the control law presented in the upcoming Section 5.6.2 guarantees the stability of the closed-loop system. As expressed in Chapter 2, UAVs are represented as rigid-body robots with six DoF, demonstrated in (5.1).

$$\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_i(t) = \frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{q}_i(t)) \mathbf{F}_i(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) + \mathbf{G} - \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_i(t) \quad (5.1a)$$

$$\dot{q}_{\phi,i}(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_{\phi}} (K_{\phi} q_{\phi,i}^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - q_{\phi,i}(t)) \quad (5.1b)$$

$$\dot{q}_{\theta,i}(t) = \frac{1}{\alpha_{\theta}} (K_{\theta} q_{\theta,i}^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - q_{\theta,i}(t)) \quad (5.1c)$$

The vectors $\mathbf{p}_i(t) \triangleq [p_{x,i}(t) \ p_{y,i}(t) \ p_{z,i}(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbf{q}_i(t) \triangleq [q_{\phi,i}(t) \ q_{\theta,i}(t) \ q_{\psi,i}(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ represent each agent's position and orientation. Here, $i = 1, \dots, n_{\text{apc},j}$ signifies each agent within the count of $n_{\text{apc},j}$ agents managed by the j^{th} controller, with $j = 1, \dots, n_c$, where n_c indicates the total controllers deployed to manage all n_a agents. The parameter $m \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ specifies the agent's mass. The matrices $\mathbf{R}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ are rotation matrices related to Euler angles, while $\mathbf{F}_i(t) \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ F_{z,i}(t)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^3$ represent the cumulative thrust forces. These forces rely on control inputs $\mathbf{u}_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, accounting for roll, pitch, and total thrust for each agent. The vector $\mathbf{G} \triangleq [0 \ 0 \ -9.81]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^3$ signifies gravity, and $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ characterizes the drag coefficients. The desired reference inputs, $q_{\phi,i}^{\text{ref}}, q_{\theta,i}^{\text{ref}} \in [-\pi, \pi]$, are supplied with time constants $\alpha_\phi, \alpha_\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ and proportional gains $K_\phi, K_\theta \in \mathbb{R}$.

State Estimator

In alignment with Section 3.3, to compensate for the system's overall time delays, τ_{rtt} , the predicted position is utilized and velocity of each UAV as described in (5.2).

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_i(t) = \mathbf{p}_i(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \quad (5.2a)$$

$$\implies \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t) = \dot{\mathbf{p}}_i(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \quad (5.2b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}}_i(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i(t) + \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (5.2c)$$

$$\implies \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t) + \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_i(t) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (5.2d)$$

By combining the future states of the agents as derived from (5.2d) with (5.1a), the agents' future states can be predicted according to the control inputs as described in (5.3).

$$\dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t) + \left(\frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{q}_i(t)) \mathbf{F}_i(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) + \mathbf{G} - \mathbf{A} \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \right) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (5.3)$$

$$\implies \dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{A} \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))^{-1} \left(\dot{\hat{\mathbf{p}}}_i(t) + \left(\frac{1}{m} \mathbf{R}_i(\mathbf{q}_i(t)) \mathbf{F}_i(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) + \mathbf{G} \right) \right) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)$$

The control input $\mathbf{u}_i(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))$ is influenced by the attitude dynamics. Consequently, to predict roll and pitch in the future, the same approach as described in (5.2) and (5.3) is applied, using the relationships specified in (5.1b) and (5.1c). Thus, the roll and pitch estimates are given by (5.4).

$$\hat{q}_{\phi,i}(t) = q_{\phi,i}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \quad (5.4a)$$

$$\hat{q}_{\theta,i}(t) = q_{\theta,i}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) \quad (5.4b)$$

$$\hat{q}_{\phi,i}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \hat{q}_{\phi,i}(t) + \dot{q}_{\phi,i}(t) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t) \quad (5.4c)$$

$$\hat{q}_{\theta,i}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) = \hat{q}_{\theta,i}(t) + \dot{q}_{\theta,i}(t) \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t), \quad (5.4d)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}_{\phi,i}(t) &= \frac{1}{\alpha_{\phi}} (K_{\phi} q_{\phi,i}^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - \widehat{q}_{\phi,i}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))) \\ \dot{q}_{\theta,i}(t) &= \frac{1}{\alpha_{\theta}} (K_{\theta} q_{\theta,i}^{\text{ref}}(t - \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)) - \widehat{q}_{\theta,i}(t + \tau_{\text{rtt}}(t))) \end{aligned}$$

Cost Function

The aim of the controllers is to establish a function where the control inputs \mathbf{u}_i guarantee paths that prevent collisions and reach the target reference positions $\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{ref}}$. For any agent i , the state vector is characterized as $\mathbf{x}_i \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_i^{\top} \quad \dot{\mathbf{p}}_i^{\top} \quad q_{\phi,i} \quad q_{\theta,i}]^{\top}$, with the control inputs defined by $\mathbf{u}_i \triangleq [q_{\phi,i}^{\text{ref}} \quad q_{\theta,i}^{\text{ref}} \quad T_i]^{\top}$, where $T_i \in [0, 1]$ represents the thrust normalized by each agent's mass. Additionally, the dynamics of the system are discretized as described in Chapter 2.

The controller assesses the progression of the state over the prediction horizon (h_j), to optimize the control inputs. The control inputs are represented by $\mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k}$. The reference trajectory, $\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{ref}}$, is sampled across the prediction horizon to define the cost functions $J_{c,j}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_i, \mathbf{u}_{i,k-1})$ for each controller as specified in (5.5), where $j = 1, \dots, n_c$ indicates each controller among the total controllers.

$$\begin{aligned} J_{c,j} &= \sum_{m=0}^{h_j} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{apc},j}} \left\{ \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{x}_{i,k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{x}_{i,k+m|k} \right)^{\top} \mathbf{Q}_x \left(\mathbf{x}_{i,k+m}^{\text{ref}} - \mathbf{x}_{i,k+m|k} \right)}_{\text{State cost}} \right. \\ &\quad + \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k} - \mathbf{u}_{i,k+m-1|k} \right)^{\top} \mathbf{Q}_{\Delta u} \left(\mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k} - \mathbf{u}_{i,k+m-1|k} \right)}_{\text{Smoothness cost}} \\ &\quad \left. + \underbrace{\left(\mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k} + \mathbf{G} \right)^{\top} \mathbf{Q}_u \left(\mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k} + \mathbf{G} \right)}_{\text{Actuation cost}} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

The cost function is tailored to reduce state errors using the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{8 \times 8}$. At the same time, it ensures control signals remain smooth through the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_{\Delta u} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$, which helps mitigate fluctuations between consecutive control inputs. Additionally, the matrix $\mathbf{Q}_u \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ maintains the control inputs close to hovering mode. This function integrates time delays and each agent's state in a centralized framework to generate collision-free paths while penalizing deviations from target positions.

The complexity of the controllers is dependent on the number of agents being managed ($n_{\text{apc},j}$), the prediction horizon (h_j), and the sampling period (T_s). Although the proposed approach is robust, it imposes higher computational demands compared to other methods due to its centralized setup, where all agents ($n_{\text{apc},j}$) share their states. Nonetheless, this increased computational requirement is effectively handled by the monitored edge resources, which aid in the execution of the controller and generation of optimal solutions. In Section 5.6, it is detail how to co-design the control applications and optimize the deployment of the centralized controller to ensure that the resource requirements are met.

Control Input Constraints

To ensure smooth system behavior and guarantee that the computed control inputs remain within desired bounds, control input constraints are implemented in addition to the cost functions. These constraints ensure bounded values, as expressed in (5.6a)-(5.6d), and prevent overly aggressive control actions, as described in (5.7). In the following constraints, the function $[h_c]_+ = \max\{0, h_c\}$ is used to represent a constrained area. This formulation ensures that h_c takes on positive values when the constraint is violated and negative or zero when the constraint is satisfied.

$$\left[q_{\phi, i, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\phi, i, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\phi, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0 \quad (5.6a)$$

$$\left[q_{\phi, i, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\phi, i, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\phi, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0 \quad (5.6b)$$

$$\left[q_{\theta, i, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\theta, i, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\theta, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0 \quad (5.6c)$$

$$\left[q_{\theta, i, k+m|k}^{\text{ref}} - q_{\theta, i, k+m-1|k}^{\text{ref}} - \Delta q_{\theta, \text{max}} \right]_+ = 0, \quad (5.6d)$$

and the hard bounds on control inputs defined by the thrust is limited by the motors are expressed in (5.7).

$$\mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}_{i, k+m|k} \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max} \quad (5.7)$$

$\Delta q_{\phi, \text{max}}$ and $\Delta q_{\theta, \text{max}}$ indicate the greatest permissible alteration in input for each time step. Meanwhile, \mathbf{u}_{\min} and \mathbf{u}_{\max} define the minimum and maximum control input values, which are restricted by the UAV's design specifications.

Collision Avoidance Constraints

To enforce collision avoidance as a constraint over the cost function, the estimated positions of the UAVs is considered over the prediction horizon. Therefore, an agent-to-agent (l, i) collision avoidance constraint $C^{l,i}$ is presented in (5.8). The constraint becomes an equality when satisfied, enforcing a minimum separation of r_{safe} between each agent.

$$\begin{aligned} C^{l,i}(\mathbf{x}_{i, k+m}) := & \left[(p_{z, i, k+m|k} - p_{z, l, k+m|k}) + L \right]_+ \\ & \times \left[(p_{z, i, k+m|k} + p_{z, l, k+m|k}) + L \right]_+ \\ & \times \left[r_{\text{safe}}^2 - (p_{x, i, k+m|k} - p_{x, l, k+m|k})^2 \right. \\ & \left. - (p_{y, i, k+m|k} - p_{y, l, k+m|k})^2 \right]_+ = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

where $i, l \in [1, n_a]$ with $i < l$ for all agent pairs. L represents the minimum allowable vertical distance between two agents to ensure safety and minimize disturbances.

Optimization

The CNMPC problems' are solved with the PANOC using the (5.9). The goal is to minimize cost function (5.5), while respecting the designed constraints.

$$\underset{\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{x}_k}{\text{Minimize}} J_{c,j}(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k; \mathbf{u}_{k-1|k}) \quad (5.9a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{s.t.: } \mathbf{x}_{i,k+m+1|k} &= \zeta(\mathbf{x}_{i,k+m|k}, \mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k}) \\ m &= 0, \dots, h_j - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (5.9b)$$

Constraints (5.6a) – (5.6d)

$$m = 0, \dots, h_j \quad (5.9c)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}_{i,k+m|k} \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max}$$

$$m = 0, \dots, h_j \quad (5.9d)$$

$$C^{l,i}(\mathbf{x}_{i,k+m}) = 0$$

$$m = 0, \dots, h_j, \quad i, l = 1, \dots, n_a \quad (5.9e)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,k|k} = \mathbf{x}_{i,k} \text{ notag} \quad (5.9f)$$

$$i = 1, \dots, n_a \quad (5.9g)$$

5.4.2 Mission Planner

The next stage of the proposed framework involves defining the operational objectives of the offloaded application. These objectives can be predetermined for autonomous missions, such as exploration or inspection, or dynamically assigned by a human operator during execution. The framework accounts for variations in the number of active agents, reflecting realistic MAS scenarios in which individual units may fail, withdraw from the mission, or be newly introduced into the centralized control scheme. Accordingly, the high-level mission planner continuously evaluates the total number of agents, denoted as $n_a(k)$, at each discrete time step k , as outlined in Algorithm 1. Based on this information, the planner distributes the agents spatially following the formulation in (5.10), thereby ensuring the sequential and coordinated initiation of missions. Each agent in the system is denoted by n_i , where $i = 1, \dots, n_a$.

Let's assume $\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{ref}} \triangleq [p_{x,i}^{\text{ref}}(k) \ p_{y,j}^{\text{ref}}(k) \ p_{z,j}^{\text{ref}}(k)]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, the desired position for each agent, given by (5.10):

$$p_{x,i}^{\text{ref}}(k) = w_1 \cdot r_{\text{safe}} \cdot s_1(i) \cdot (-1)^i \quad (5.10a)$$

$$p_{y,i}^{\text{ref}}(k) = w_1 \cdot r_{\text{safe}} \cdot s_1(i) \cdot (-1)^{\lfloor \frac{i+1}{2} \rfloor} \quad (5.10b)$$

$$p_{z,i}^{\text{ref}}(k) = h_{\text{trj}} \quad (5.10c)$$

Algorithm 1: Dynamically subscribing agents to the centralized schemes to establish communication

```

1 while  $k = 0$  do
2   for  $i = 1 : n_a(0)$  do
3     Initialize communication with agents  $n_i$ 
4 while  $k > 0$  do
5   if  $n_a(k) > n_a(k-1)$  then
6     for  $i = n_a(k-1) + 1 : n_a(k)$  do
7       Initialize communication with agents  $n_i$ 
8   if  $n_a(k) < n_a(k-1)$  then
9     for  $i = n_a(k) + 1 : n_a(k-1)$  do
10      Deactivate communication with agents  $n_i$ 

```

The weight w_1 is utilized, so that $w_1 \cdot r_{\text{safe}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ denotes the minimum safe operating distance between agents (r_{safe} is the minimum separation distance to ensure collision-free trajectories as noted in Section 5.4). h_{trj} represents the flying altitude of the agents (specific to UAVs). The variable s_1 is a scattering parameter with $l \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, which defines the spatial distribution of agents, as given by (5.11). The parameter l is selected to ensure that the agents are arranged in an expanding square formation, so that they are spread in the free space before starting performing a specific mission.

$$s_1(i) = 1 + \lfloor \frac{i-1}{l} \rfloor \quad (5.11)$$

This process is essential to ensure a safe distance between agents. The minimum safe operating distance not only helps prevent collisions during missions but also contributes to bounding the required computational resources. As agents are positioned closer together, the centralized controllers need to allocate more computational resources to generate feasible solutions for the agents to navigate the environment. This increased resource demand arises from the heightened complexity of managing multiple agents in proximity, where the interactions and coordination between them are more computationally intensive. Moreover, tightly spaced agents lead to a denser constraint landscape for optimization, increasing both the number and stiffness of safety-related constraints. Ensuring spatial separation at the planning stage thus provides a proactive mechanism to preserve system scalability and maintain real-time feasibility.

5.4.3 System Infrastructure & Deployment Setup

In this section, the utilized system for the experimental evaluation of the proposed architecture is analyzed, comprising the MAS, the k8s cluster, and the communication among nodes.

Multi-Agent Aerial Robots

The agents utilized in this work are UAVs, which have been widely studied due to their growing role in MAS. For this study, the `Crazyflie` MAV from `Bitcraze` is selected, more specifically the `Crazyflie 2.1` nano-quadrotor [150]. The specifications of these UAVs, which are essential to understanding their operational characteristics within the system, are obtained from [151], and are summarized in Table 5.1. The firmware used was the official `Crazyflie` firmware version 2023.03 [152].

Table 5.1: Parameters for the UAV model

Notation	Value	Definition
g	9.82 m/s ²	Gravitational acceleration
A_x	0.1	Damping constant coefficient around x axis
A_y	0.1	Damping constant coefficient around y axis
A_z	0.2	Damping constant coefficient around z axis
τ_ϕ	0.5	Time constant for roll angle
τ_θ	0.5	Time constant for pitch angle
K_ϕ	1	Gain for roll angle
K_θ	1	Gain for pitch angle
m	0.027 kg	Total mass
I_{xx}	1.395 kg · m ²	Moment of inertia around x axis
I_{yy}	1.395 kg · m ²	Moment of inertia around y axis
I_{zz}	2.173 kg · m ²	Moment of inertia around z axis

For position feedback, a `Vicon` MoCap system is employed, and a custom ROS node is developed to compute and broadcast odometry data for each UAV. Communication with the agents is established using the `Crazyradio PA` dongle, which was connected to a local ground station. This station streamed real-time odometry data and control commands to the edge system and vice versa, as discussed in Section 2.3.2. The overall framework was designed to support scalable MAS deployments, and the same control infrastructure was used to validate large-scale scenarios with simulated agents.

Edge Cluster

In this work, `k8s` is used solely as an orchestration layer to manage containerized workloads across edge nodes. The proposed approach does not rely on the default `k8s` scheduler, horizontal/vertical pod autoscaling, or built-in load balancing mechanisms. Instead, the core contributions and performance benefits derive from the integrated framework, which includes: (i) the offline resource modeling component based on a second-order polynomial regression, (ii) the delay-based feedback control law for dynamic resource allocation, and (iii) the online optimization problem that defines application reconfiguration and resource availability.

These components operate independently of k8s scheduling heuristics. Thus, k8s acts as a deployment and communication backbone, enabling, but not dictating, the dynamic resource allocation strategies introduced in this work.

By offloading computationally intensive control and predictive algorithms to the edge cluster, the aerial agents are relieved of onboard processing demands and can focus on mission execution. This architectural division enhances overall system scalability, reduces computational load on agents, and supports stable MAS operation even in dynamic and resource-constrained environments.

Resource Allocation Adjustment

To facilitate dynamic resource allocation, Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) is used to grant the scheduler permissions for deploying, updating, and removing controller pods via the k8s command-line interface (`kubectl`), as detailed in Section 5.5.1. The scheduler continuously monitors CPU and memory usage across all cluster nodes using the k8s Metrics Server [153], which exposes system statistics through standardized summary Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).

RBAC is a critical enabler of this adaptive and dynamic resource control frameworks. Through fine-grained role definitions and permission bindings, the scheduler is authorized to interact directly with the k8s API server to dynamically manage the lifecycle of controller pods. Specifically, deployment, deletion, and updating of CNMPC pods are performed on-the-fly using authorized API requests. These actions are securely performed by assigning the scheduler a custom service account with create, delete, patch, and update privileges over relevant k8s resources (e.g., pods, deployments, and services) within a designated namespace. This enables the system to autonomously scale the number of controllers, modify their computational specifications, or remove inactive modules, ensuring optimal use of the cluster's available resources without manual intervention.

Based on these observations, the scheduler dynamically adjusts each controller pod's resource requests and limits (CPU and memory) according to the adopted scheduling policy. Although the monitoring operates at a frequency of 1 Hz, to prevent unnecessary fluctuations, actual resource adjustments are only triggered when a sliding window of resource usage values consistently exceeds a predefined threshold.

While updates occur continuously, all resource allocation decisions are subject to current edge node availability. The feasibility of each allocation request is guaranteed by the optimization problem formulated in Section 5.6.3, ensuring that controller deployment remains within the limits of cluster capacity.

Unlike traditional distributed robotic systems where peer-to-peer communication is common, this approach routes all coordination and data exchange through the edge cluster. The edge thereby becomes the central hub for coordination, enabling each agent to receive task and constraint information without requiring direct communication with other agents. This centralized communication model streamlines coordination, reduces inter-agent coupling, and supports scalability for large robotic fleets.

5.5 Reactive Scheduling Architecture

The deployment of centralized control strategies, especially computationally intensive ones such as CNMPC, in cloud or edge-based robotic systems introduces significant challenges related to resource scalability, timing constraints, and dynamic workload distribution. As the number of agents and controller parameters vary throughout a mission, static resource allocation becomes insufficient to guarantee performance, stability, and responsiveness. Efficient runtime orchestration is thus critical for managing limited edge resources while maintaining real-time feasibility.

Recent efforts such as KubeROS [154] have explored k8s-based frameworks for large-scale robotic deployments. However, unlike KubeROS, which requires robotic agents to be directly integrated into the k8s cluster, the approach proposed in this work allows for loose coupling between robots and the orchestration infrastructure. This architectural separation provides a high degree of flexibility, enabling agents to dynamically join or leave the centralized control scheme without reconfiguring the cluster itself.

While KubeROS addresses generalized robotic software deployment, the proposed framework specifically targets the automated and dynamic orchestration of centralized control processes, where CNMPC instances must be deployed, updated, or terminated in response to mission demands. A core limitation of existing centralized schemes is their inability to scale when faced with real-time demands from large or variable-sized agent groups. This work overcomes that constraint through a reactive scheduling mechanism, capable of monitoring system resources and coordinating CNMPC deployment in a fully adaptive and closed-loop fashion.

The scheduling mechanism also leverages a k8s-based edge infrastructure, not merely for container orchestration, but as a foundation for real-time resource management. In this setup, CNMPC instances are deployed on designated edge worker nodes with explicit resource assignments, and are adjusted based on online measurements such as agent counts and controller configurations (e.g., prediction horizon).

The reactive scheduling architecture thus forms a core contribution of this chapter, and has been published in [35]. It operates continuously to ensure that controller instances are not only correctly deployed and scaled, but also efficiently mapped to available computational resources, enabling scalability, performance, and adaptability in edge-controlled MAS. The rest of this section presents the main components and operational logic of the scheduling framework, including controller deployment monitoring and dynamic resource adjustment.

5.5.1 Scheduling Mechanism

The scheduling mechanism serves as a core component of the reactive scheduling architecture illustrated in Figure 5.1. It receives the necessary information from the mission planner, including the number of agents and the CNMPC parameters ($h(t)$ and n_a). Leveraging this information, the scheduler dynamically generates the necessary deployments required for the operation of the CNMPCs, considering as well the computational requirements. In addition to creating deployments, corresponding services are established that facilitate seamless message exchange between the edge and the agents.

Figure 5.1: Overview of the block diagram. The edge cluster includes the mission planner, the scheduler, the controllers, and the proxy server, while the MAS includes the agents and the other end of the UPD tunnel.

The scheduler leverages various features via the k8s command-line tool, `kubectl`. As a result, the scheduler not only monitors the deployment of controllers and their resource utilization but also ensures continuous execution by creating replicas. This redundancy guarantees that edge controllers remain operational, even in cases where pods running controllers face interruptions in their execution. To enhance the scheduler’s effectiveness, insights are extracted from the k8s environment. These logs provide essential feedback, allowing the scheduler to fine-tune its performance and optimize the allocation of computational resources. Overall, the scheduler serves as a main component within the edge-based control system, harnessing k8s capabilities to facilitate dynamic deployments, resource management, and robust communication between edge controllers and agents.

The monitoring of the system by the scheduler is established based on the resource requirements and the CNMPC parameters, as shown in Figure 5.1. The scheduler forwards corresponding information to the controllers, such as the prediction horizon and number of agents vectors $\mathbf{h}(t)$ and $\mathbf{n}_{\text{apc}}(t)$, respectively. These vectors describe the prediction length and number of agents of each controller, while considering the maximum controllable agent per CNMPC due to the optimizer’s limitations. The scheduler will deploy each CNMPC with corresponding resources based on $\mathbf{r}_{\text{alc}}(t)$, that specifies the requested resources of each controller.

Monitoring the Deployment of Centralized Controllers

In this step, it was crucial to determine the maximum number of agents that can be effectively controlled by a single CNMPC, thereby facilitating the calculation of the required number of CNMPCs to govern all available agents. This calculation was performed empirically, and the corresponding n_{max} value was selected. Based on this knowledge, a dynamic deployment strategy for CNMPCs was devised, as illustrated in Algorithm 2. While [154] uses a load balancer to manage the number of VMs required for motion planning, the proposed approach takes a more dynamic and flexible approach by allowing the scheduler to generate and terminate deployments as needed based on various inputs such as the number of agents and mission planner objectives.

Algorithm 2: Deployment of CNMPCs based on the total number of agents (n_a)

```

1 if  $n_a \neq n_a^{old}$  then
2    $n_c \leftarrow \text{int}\left(\frac{n_a - 1}{n_{\max}} + 1\right)$ ;
3   if  $n_a < n_a^{old}$  then
4     for  $j \leftarrow n_c$  to  $n_c^{old}$  do
5       Delete unnecessary deployments;
6     for  $j \leftarrow 2n_a + 1$  to  $2n_a^{old} + 1$  do
7       Delete unnecessary services;
8   if  $n_a \neq 0$  then
9      $n_{\text{apc}} \leftarrow \text{int}\left(\frac{n_a - 1}{n_c}\right)$ ;
10     $n_{\text{apc}}^f \leftarrow \frac{n_a - 1}{n_c}$ ;
11     $counter \leftarrow 0$ ;
12    for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $n_c$  do
13      if  $n_{\text{apc}} = n_{\text{apc}}^f$  then
14        Create or update deployments;
15        Create or update services;
16      else
17         $counter \leftarrow counter + 1$ ;
18         $n_{\text{apc}} \leftarrow \text{int}\left(\frac{n_a - 1}{n_c}\right) + 1$ ;
19         $n_{\text{apc}}^f \leftarrow \frac{n_a - counter}{n_c}$ ;
20        Create or update deployments;
21        Create or update services;
22         $n_{\text{apc}} \leftarrow n_{\text{apc}} - 1$ ;
23     $n_a^{old} \leftarrow n_a$ ;
24     $n_c^{old} \leftarrow n_c$ ;

```

The total number of deployed CNMPC instances required to control all agents at a given time step is denoted as n_c . The variables n_a^{old} and n_c^{old} represent, respectively, the number of agents and the number of CNMPCs used in the previous iteration of the scheduling loop. To determine how the agents should be distributed across controllers, two intermediary parameters are introduced: $n_{\text{apc}}^f \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, which represents the floating-point value of agents per controller, and $n_{\text{apc}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$, which is its rounded integer approximation used for actual deployment.

An auxiliary variable, *counter*, is also introduced to facilitate the indexing and sequential deployment of CNMPC instances during the scheduling process. It ensures that each CNMPC instance is assigned the appropriate agent subset and configuration parameters without overlap or redundancy.

Adaptive Resource Allocation

In contrast to prior edge-based robotic control frameworks, such as the one introduced in the previous chapters, the present architecture introduces an application-aware adaptive resource allocation strategy. Rather than relying on static provisioning or default resource schedulers, this method explicitly accounts for the runtime computational demands of each CNMPC instance and dynamically maps them to the available edge resources.

Unlike high-level deployment frameworks such as the one presented in KubeROS [154], which orchestrate robotic workloads based solely on hardware availability, the proposed approach formulates and utilizes an empirical resource model. This model estimates the computational requirements of CNMPC instances based on two core application parameters: the number of agents under centralized control and the chosen prediction horizon. These parameters directly influence the complexity of the optimization problem solved by each controller and, by extension, the computational workload required for real-time execution.

This analysis leads to formulate Eq. (5.12), for the CPU allocation.

$$r_{\text{alc},j,\text{min}}^{\text{cpu}}(t) = f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}(t)) = \alpha \cdot \frac{n_{\text{apc},j}(t) - 1}{1 - N_n} + r_{\text{min}}^{\text{cpu}} \quad (\text{cores}) \quad (5.12a)$$

$$r_{\text{alc},j,\text{max}}^{\text{cpu}}(t) = f_2(n_{\text{apc},j}(t)) = \alpha \cdot \frac{n_{\text{apc},j}(t) - 1}{1 - N_n} + r_{\text{max}}^{\text{cpu}} \quad (\text{cores}) \quad (5.12b)$$

Additionally, the memory requirements are modeled through parameterized functions defined in (5.13).

$$r_{\text{alc},j,\text{min}}^{\text{mem}}(t) = g_1(n_{\text{apc},j}(t)) = \beta \cdot \frac{n_{\text{apc},j}(t) - 1}{1 - N_n} + r_{\text{min}}^{\text{mem}} \quad (\text{MiB}) \quad (5.13a)$$

$$r_{\text{alc},j,\text{max}}^{\text{mem}}(t) = g_2(n_{\text{apc},j}(t)) = \beta \cdot \frac{n_{\text{apc},j}(t) - 1}{1 - N_n} + r_{\text{max}}^{\text{mem}} \quad (\text{MiB}) \quad (5.13b)$$

Here, $n_{\text{apc},j} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ denotes the number of agents managed by each CNMPC $j = 1, \dots, n_c$, and $N_n \in [0, 1)$, reflects the normalized representation of the prediction horizon or update rate. The constants $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{Z}_{> 0}$ are empirically derived through offline system profiling, while the baseline minimum and maximum computational thresholds are defined by $r_{\text{min}}^{\text{cpu}}, r_{\text{max}}^{\text{cpu}}, r_{\text{min}}^{\text{mem}}$, and $r_{\text{max}}^{\text{mem}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{> 0}$. These represent the minimal and maximal resource boundaries within which each CNMPC instance must operate to maintain stability and computational feasibility. Based on these information, the resource allocation vector for each controller j is denoted as $\mathbf{r}_{\text{alc},j}(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} r_{\text{alc},j,\text{min}}^{\text{cpu}}(t) & r_{\text{alc},j,\text{max}}^{\text{cpu}}(t) & r_{\text{alc},j,\text{min}}^{\text{mem}}(t) & r_{\text{alc},j,\text{max}}^{\text{mem}}(t) \end{bmatrix}^\top \in \mathbb{Z}^4$.

This formulation enables each controller to be deployed with a proper allocation of CPU cores and memory, ensuring that resources are used efficiently without compromising control performance. It also mitigates the risk of over-provisioning, which is especially important when dealing with limited edge resources and multiple concurrent applications.

While this resource model is designed around the characteristics of CNMPC schemes, the methodology itself is broadly generalizable. The approach does not rely on the internal structure of the control algorithm, instead, it treats the application as a resource-intensive containerized workload with identifiable scaling patterns.

By substituting CNMPC-specific parameters (e.g., number of agents, prediction horizon) with equivalent descriptors of computational load for other applications (e.g., neural network size, sensor input frequency, or dataset size), the same modeling and deployment logic can be applied. Thus, although the current implementation focuses on CNMPC as a representative use case, the resource modeling and allocation mechanism is applicable to a wide range of robotics and cyber-physical applications where runtime performance is sensitive to both algorithmic complexity and environmental dynamics. This abstraction reinforces the flexibility of the framework and its suitability for broader adoption in diverse edge-based robotic control pipelines.

5.5.2 Evaluation & Results

The proposed scheduling mechanism and adaptive resource allocation framework are evaluated through a combination of a simulated MAS and a real edge cluster. A high-level overview of the cluster architecture is detailed in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: The k8s cluster experimental setup with a snapshot of the external VM that hosts the simulator. Three CNMPCs are distributed to two worker nodes, and control the trajectory of 21 UAVs.

Experimental Setup

The proposed framework is evaluated using a dedicated real-time cloud testbed, emulating an edge cluster, provided by Ericsson Research [155], which operates on OpenStack [156]. Within this infrastructure, a k8s cluster hosts the scheduling mechanism, while a dedicated external VM is used to simulate MAS of aerial robots using the RotorS ROS-Gazebo plugin [78].

The k8s cluster comprises one master node and three worker nodes. The mission planner, scheduler, and UDP tunnel components are continuously active, while CNMPC pods are deployed dynamically based on current task demands. Worker nodes 1 and 2 are designated for CNMPC deployments due to their higher computational capacity, while worker node 3 hosts auxiliary modules (e.g., mission planner, scheduler, roscore) given its relatively lower specifications. The scheduler explicitly assigns CNMPCs to worker nodes based on the current resource availability and estimated computational needs.

Specifications of all nodes, including the VM responsible for simulating agents, are summarized in Table 5.2. K8s version v1.26.1 and Docker v24.0.5 are used as the orchestration and container runtime, respectively. All components, including the scheduling mechanism, are deployed as k8s pods, enabling isolated and scalable execution.

Table 5.2: K8s cluster and simulator VM specifications

Node	CPU	Memory	Environment
Master Node	3-core	2 GB	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS
Worker Node 1	32-core	460 GB	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS
Worker Node 2	16-core	32 GB	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS
Worker Node 3	4-core	8 GB	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS
Simulator	32-core	480 GB	Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS

Resources Evaluation

To assess the impact of the scheduling mechanism on computational efficiency, the resource utilization with and without scheduling was compared. As depicted in Figure 5.3, resource usage without scheduling (left) increases sharply with the number of agents, risking overload, while, the proposed mechanism (right) dynamically allocates agents across multiple CNMPC instances and balances them between worker nodes, maintaining utilization within acceptable limits.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of resources utilization with (right figure) and without (left figure) scheduling mechanism.

For example, as the number of agents exceeds 21, the scheduler automatically triggers the deployment of a third CNMPC, distributing agents as follows: 7 agents on CNMPC₁ (Worker Node 1), 7 on CNMPC₂ (Worker Node 1), and 7 on CNMPC₃ (Worker Node 2). This distribution minimizes bottlenecks and highlights the architecture’s scalability, which contrasts with traditional centralized schemes that are limited by single-node computation.

Tracking Performance

Tracking performance during real-time transitions is visualized in Figure 5.4. The figure illustrates the RMSE of UAV trajectories during dynamic changes in the number of agents and CNMPC assignments. Initially, four UAVs are controlled by CNMPC₁. At $t = 65$ seconds, the addition of three UAVs triggers the deployment of CNMPC'₁, to which all agents migrate. Later, at $t = 125$ seconds, three more UAVs are introduced, prompting the scheduler to deploy CNMPC''₁ and CNMPC₂.

Figure 5.4: Tracking error of ten UAVs when transitioning between CNMPCs.

During the migration phase, UAV₆ and UAV₇ experience a transient increase in tracking error caused by the reassignment of setpoints and the redistribution of control authority among newly deployed CNMPC instances. This temporary deviation is attributed to the brief reinitialization period required for the new controllers to synchronize with the updated system state and constraints. Despite these transitions, the error remains bounded within acceptable tolerance limits and rapidly converges back to nominal levels once the controllers stabilize, and without compromising trajectory accuracy or overall closed-loop stability.

CPU Utilization Assessment

As discussed in Chapter 3, to enable stable control in edge-enabled systems, communication and processing delays must be kept within strict bounds. Thus, the total RTT is modeled as show in (5.14).

$$\tau_{\text{rtt}} \leq \tau_{\text{max}}, \tag{5.14}$$

where $\tau_{\text{rtt}} = \tau_u + \tau_d + \tau_p$

While communication delays are relatively stable due to lightweight data transmission (odometry and control commands), τ_p is strongly affected by CPU availability.

Figure 5.5 demonstrates the empirical correlation between CPU utilization and CNMPC processing time τ_p . As CPU usage increases beyond a safe region (shaded blue zone), the processing time rises, risking violation of the RTT constraint. To mitigate this, the system applies the resource models defined in (5.12) and (5.13), combined with a sliding window averaging method, to keep CPU usage and RTT within safe bounds, regardless of system size.

Figure 5.5: Correlation between the CPU and the processing time τ_p along with the target CPU utilization range represented with the blue zone.

The findings validate that CPU overhead directly impacts solver performance and, consequently, real-time control stability. By incorporating CPU-awareness into the scheduling logic, the proposed architecture achieves optimal trade-offs between scalability, efficiency, and robustness.

5.6 Dynamic Resource-Aware Control

The deployment of centralized control schemes for real-time coordination in MAS offers significant potential to enhance system-wide performance by enabling global task allocation and trajectory optimization [147]. However, such approaches impose substantial computational demands, often exceeding the capabilities of onboard robotic systems, particularly when the number of agents or the complexity of the control algorithm increases.

To overcome these limitations, this work integrates edge computing with dynamic resource allocation strategies to enhance the scalability, robustness, and responsiveness of CNMPC schemes. The resulting architecture is published in [36], and illustrated in Figure 5.6, highlighting the proposed system’s capacity to adaptively manage computational resources while maintaining closed-loop stability under time-varying conditions.

Figure 5.6: High-level overview of the proposed edge framework.

Edge and cloud-based robotics architectures have previously demonstrated potential in off-loading computational workloads [135, 157]. However, such systems have traditionally assumed static operational parameters (e.g., fixed number of agents), limiting their ability to adapt dynamically. In contrast, this work introduces a fully dynamic, delay-aware resource management framework designed to the needs of CNMPC-based MAS control, enabling adaptation in response to changes in agent count, control parameters, and communication conditions.

The debate between centralized and distributed control architectures is longstanding [108]. Centralized methods are generally preferable for small-to-moderate agent groups, where global coordination enables superior task allocation and predictive trajectory planning. Nevertheless, their scalability is limited by the computational load imposed on the central controller. Conversely, distributed and decentralized schemes [124, 125, 129, 130] improve scalability by distributing computation but may suffer from suboptimal coordination and limited foresight.

While several hybrid control strategies have been proposed [131–134], they often neglect the dynamic nature of real-world missions, where agent availability and control complexity evolve over time. Consequently, centralized control schemes are often dismissed as impractical for large-scale systems due to their computational intensity, particularly for CNMPC, where online optimization becomes increasingly computationally intensive.

In resource-constrained robotic systems, choosing the most suitable control approach [158] and computational layer is essential, whether it's device-level, edge, or cloud. UAVs, with restricted payload capacity and limited flight duration, gain advantages from being fitted with lightweight onboard computers [159]. Nevertheless, this setup limits their capability to tackle sophisticated computations such as NMPCs, particularly CNMPCs, making offloading a viable option. Several studies have explored the placement of control applications for computation, utilizing edge or cloud offloading [63, 99, 123, 157, 160].

Although the studies mentioned earlier concentrated on single agent systems, the approach proposed in Section 5.5 explored a MAS with a fixed agent count, enabling us to allocate resources in advance. Researchers in [161], also addressed a robotic MAS for collaborative decision-making problem, in a distributed networked system, by utilizing IOTA [162]. Moreover, in Chapter 2, the closed-loop system stability over the edge was examined, but no a single control law was designed to guarantee stability when the variable time delays in the edge-enabled MAS were present.

In contrast to the prior works and the presented approach of Section 5.5, the current approach introduces a dynamic, delay-aware resource allocation framework designed specifically for edge-offloaded centralized control of MAS UAV. While previous studies have investigated offloading for single-agent scenarios [63, 123], or assumed fixed agent counts [33], the proposed framework is designed to adaptively reallocate resources based on changes in the number of active agents and the prediction horizon of each controller. Moreover, unlike the previously proposed approach of Section 5.5, which analyzed edge-enabled stability without active delay compensation, now a control law that adjusts resource allocations in real time to maintain closed-loop stability under varying communication delays is presented. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work to combine feedback-based resource control, complexity modeling, and optimization-driven application reconfiguration for edge-offloaded centralized control of MAS of UAVs.

By offloading the computational process of the controllers to the edge layer, the system is able to dynamically allocate resources to address the challenges previously mentioned. Cloud and edge computing technologies, which include virtualization, containerized applications, and orchestration platforms like k8s [163], have improved application offloading, deployment, and dynamic resource management. This leads to decreased edge deployment time and advances the capabilities of robotics [53, 54]. Such technologies play a key role in developing the next generation of robotic MAS, enabling dynamic resource allocation, such as CPU shares. While many studies have integrated horizontal and vertical scaling through edge computing for dynamic allocation [164–167], the proposed approach introduces a novel method that combines both scaling strategies with an approximation and an optimization function. This approach not only takes into account the availability of resources, but also dynamically reconfigures the application to ensure optimal performance.

Several studies have proposed dynamic resource allocation [164, 165, 168, 169]. Nonetheless, these studies primarily focus on managing processing times for incoming requests and responses [170, 171], addressing edge computing overload through scheduling methods [172, 173], or integrating resource allocation with network slicing [174, 175]. In [176], an edge-based control solution was proposed to handle control delays for a remotely controlled UAV by modeling the delays. Similarly, [50] introduced both a control mechanism and a resource estimation method for precise robot navigation.

While these approaches offer valuable insights into dynamic resource allocation and delay control, none explicitly examine their impact on system stability, particularly when considering fluctuating application demands, varying time delays, and the need for application reconfiguration. Furthermore, ensuring the availability of resources to meet application requirements remains a critical but underexplored aspect.

Overall, unlike existing approaches that rely solely on set-based control [50], fixed schedules [175, 176], or reactive scaling policies [171] for edge resource allocation, the presented framework introduces a novel combination of control-theoretic [164] and application co-design approach as highlighted in Table 5.3. The resource demands of CNMPC are modeled using a second-order polynomial regression function, representing the nonlinear impact of varying numbers of agent and prediction horizon. Additionally, a feedback control law that compensates for communication and processing delays is designed by dynamically adjusting CPU allocation. To meet application and system requirements and performance under resource constraints, the application parameters are also reconfigured dynamically.

Table 5.3: Comparison of edge-based dynamic resource allocation methods

Feature↓ / Method→	[50]	[176]	[171]	[164]	Proposed Work
Dynamic resource modeling	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Time delay-aware resource control	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓
Application reconfiguration	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓
Online optimization framework	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Stability assurance under delay	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓
Scheduling on edge infrastructure	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
Horizontal scalability	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓
Vertical scalability	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Real-time responsiveness	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓

In that end, a multidimensional problem is addressed by aiming to ensure both optimized performance and stability through dynamic resource allocation. To achieve this, two complementary strategies are applied: (a) developing a model to identify the correlation between system performance and resource allocation, and (b) designing a control law to compensate for varying communication time delays. these strategies are implemented with the development of several components as depicted in Figure 5.7, such as the scheduler, the optimization problem, the resource allocation and the mission planner.

Figure 5.7: Overview of the proposed edge framework with the developed components.

5.6.1 Offline Resource Modeling

This work introduces a dynamic resource allocation mechanism designed to the application’s requirements, using curve fitting to establish the equilibrium operating point. It also involves controlling this resource allocation to ensure the stability of the centralized system with varying communication delays. Furthermore, the parameters of the application (the CNMPC parameters), are carefully managed along with the resource allocation to ensure the overall performance and stability of the closed-loop system over the edge. Similar approach can be used for other control methods (nonlinear optimization) for approximating their parameters with delays. Therefore, the proposed dynamic resource allocation method can be employed for that approximate function, considering CNMPC controllers.

Despite their optimized performance, centralized control schemes inherently face scalability challenges due to the rapid growth of computational demands as the number of agents and control parameters increase. The optimization process within each CNMPC must simultaneously account for multiple state trajectories, constraints, and interactions across all agents, resulting in nonlinear increases in computational load. Consequently, executing these algorithms on local or onboard processors becomes infeasible, especially in large-scale missions. To address this limitation, the proposed mechanism leverages the distributed computational capacity of the edge infrastructure, allowing resource-intensive control computations to be dynamically allocated to powerful edge servers, thus, enabling real-time distribution of workloads across multiple worker nodes, and ensuring necessary computational resources.

By allocating computational resources, the response time of the application can be monitored. Figure 5.8 showcases a direct correlation between CPU utilization and the response time of the centralized controller. It illustrates both the processing time τ_p and the CPU usage for a mission involving 4 agents, using fixed limited computational resources. There is a bound by the controller for generating a feasible response at 100 s. Therefore, when CPU utilization exceeds approximately 60%, the application fails to generate a response within the desired time frame. The proposed approach aims to overcome this issue by dynamically allocating the appropriate amount of resources to ensure that responses are computed within this time limit or even shorter intervals, thus maintaining the stability of the closed-loop system.

Figure 5.8: Correlation between (a) the processing time τ_p of the centralized controller, and (b) the CPU usage.

Thus, strategically allocating computational resources is crucial not only for improving performance but also for ensuring bounded response times, which in turn supports system stability. The complexity of the application, denoted by $c \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and measured in millicpu units, directly influences the required computational resources and, consequently, the processing times. The complexity of the centralized application, $c(t)$, is a function f_1 , of the number of agents $n_{\text{apc},j}(t)$ and the prediction horizon $h_j(t)$ of the j^{th} CNMPC at any given time t . This model enables capturing the nonlinear relationship between $n_{\text{apc},j}(t)$, $h_j(t)$, and $c(t)$, considering both their individual and interactive effects on complexity, as expressed in (5.15).

$$c(t) = f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}(t), h_j(t)) \quad (5.15)$$

The process of computing the accurate model (5.15) is performed offline and is represented by the “Problem Complexity” block in Figure 5.10. The process includes the following steps:

1. **Data Collection:** Gather empirical data on system performance metrics for various combinations of $n_{\text{apc},j}$ (number of agents) and h_j (prediction horizon). For each combination of $n_{\text{apc},j}$ and h_j , a consistent number of samples, denoted as S , is collected. These metrics include CPU usage measurements, which are then used to compute the complexity measure c . This data provides the necessary inputs for modeling the computational complexity of the system.

2. **Model Identification:** Define the second-order polynomial model that represents the relationship between the independent variables (the number of agents $n_{\text{apc},j}$ and the prediction horizon h_j) and the dependent variable (the complexity c). This step involves establishing the functional form of the model based on the collected data, ensuring it accurately captures the interactions between the system's key variables.
3. **Coefficients' Estimation:** Perform polynomial regression analysis on the collected data to determine the coefficients of the polynomial model. The objective is to minimize the error between the observed complexities (from real data) and those predicted by the model. This step involves applying regression techniques to estimate the coefficients, which define the polynomial and allow for predictions of complexity based on different values of $n_{\text{apc},j}$ and h_j .

Data Collection

The data collection process for determining the computational complexity of the system, denoted by $c(t)$, is performed using a Monte Carlo method. In the context, the Monte Carlo method is applied to simulate various system configurations, which include different combinations of the number of agents, $n_{\text{apc},j}(t)$, and prediction horizons, $h_j(t)$, within different initial conditions (distances among the agents).

The core idea is to generate multiple random samples of the system's input parameters, and then compute the corresponding complexity for each sample. This approach allows capturing a broad range of possible system states and ensures that the presented model accounts for the variability inherent in real-world conditions. The Monte Carlo method can be described mathematically as given in (5.16).

$$\left\{ (n_{\text{apc},j}^1(t), h_j^1(t)), (n_{\text{apc},j}^1(t), h_j^2(t)), \dots \right. \\ \left. \dots, (n_{\text{apc},j}^S(t), h_j^{S-1}(t)), (n_{\text{apc},j}^S(t), h_j^S(t)) \right\} \quad (5.16)$$

where S is the total number of random samples, and $n_{\text{apc},j}^k(t) \in [1, n_{\text{max}}]$ and $h_j^k(t) \in [1, h_{\text{max}}]$ represent the k^{th} random sample drawn from their respective distributions.

For each generated sample, the corresponding CPU usage is recorded. The system's complexity $c(t)$ is then computed based on the observed CPU usage for each configuration. These measurements reflect how different agent counts and prediction horizons affect resource consumption under real-time execution. The system's complexity $c(t)$ is then computed based on the observed CPU usage for each configuration, as expressed in (5.17). This quantification enables the mapping of operational parameters to measurable resource demands, forming the basis for building a predictive model.

$$c_k(t) = f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}^k(t), h_j^k(t)), \quad (5.17)$$

where $c_k(t)$ represents the complexity corresponding to the k^{th} sample, and $f_1(\cdot)$ is the function that maps the system's parameters to the computational complexity.

Model Identification

To precisely identify the corresponding model for $c(t)$ from the collected data, a second-order polynomial regression model is used. Thus, the complexity $f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}(t), h_j(t))$ is mathematically approximated using a second-order polynomial equation, as given in (5.18). Despite the model selection, the proposed approach can support alternative models as well, as discussed in Section 5.7.1.

$$f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}(t), h_j(t)) = \alpha n_{\text{apc},j}^2(t) + \beta n_{\text{apc},j}(t)h_j(t) + \gamma h_j^2(t) + \delta n_{\text{apc},j}(t) + \varepsilon h_j(t) + \zeta, \quad (5.18)$$

where α , β , γ , δ , ε , and ζ are the coefficients to be defined.

The second-order polynomial provides an optimal compromise between flexibility and simplicity in modeling. It accurately captures the system's nonlinearities, while avoiding the overfitting risks that accompany higher-order models. Additionally, the coefficients α , β , γ , δ , ε , ζ are straightforward to calculate, allowing for an evaluation of both the individual and combined influences of $n_{\text{apc},j}(t)$ and $h_j(t)$ on computational complexity.

Coefficients' Estimation

To estimate the coefficients, the Least Square (LS) minimization method is utilized in this optimization process. The core objective of curve fitting is to minimize the sum of squared residuals, where the residuals represent the differences between the observed data y_{data} , and the predicted values by the model $f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}(t), h_j(t), \mathbf{p})$. This curve-fitting function facilitates the estimation of model parameters that best capture the relationship between the independent variables $n_{\text{apc},j}$, h_j , and the dependent variable $y_{\text{data},i}$. The minimization of the objective function J_e which quantifies the sum of squared residuals, is expressed as follows in (5.19).

$$\text{Minimize } J_e(\mathbf{p}) \quad (5.19a)$$

$$\text{Minimize } \sum_{i=1}^{n_o} [y_{\text{data},i} - f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}, h_j, \mathbf{p})]^2, \quad (5.19b)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = [\alpha \ \beta \ \gamma \ \delta \ \varepsilon \ \zeta]^T$ denotes the parameter vector to be estimated, and n_o refer to the total count of observations.

The fitting procedure includes determining the vector \mathbf{p} that minimizes the objective function J_e . To account for data variance, a vector $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is introduced, representing the standard deviations of the errors in each observed data point $y_{\text{data},i}$. Incorporating $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ adjusts the objective function to account for variability in error magnitude, as expressed in (5.20).

$$J_e(\mathbf{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_o} \left(\frac{y_{\text{data},i} - f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}, h_j, \mathbf{p})}{\sigma_i} \right)^2, \quad (5.20)$$

where σ_i is the standard deviation corresponding to the i^{th} data point, ensuring that residuals with higher variance are appropriately weighted in the minimization process.

Utilizing σ allows for weighted LS fitting, which is particularly beneficial for emphasizing regions of the data with greater accuracy, especially in cases where measurement noise or variance is not uniformly distributed. This approach gives greater influence to data points with lower uncertainty and reduces the impact of noisier observations, leading to a more robust and reliable model. The curve-fitting process outputs the optimal parameter values \mathbf{p}_{opt} that minimize J_e along with an estimate of the covariance matrix associated with these parameters. This covariance matrix is essential for assessing the confidence intervals of the parameter estimates and examining the correlations between them, which further enables sensitivity analysis and robustness evaluation of the model under different operating conditions.

The resulting model must be interpretable, offering clear insights into how variations in the number of agents and the prediction horizon influence problem complexity. This interpretability facilitates the tuning and validation of the model within real-time control scenarios. By leveraging this curve-fitting approach, the CNMPC problem's complexity under evolving conditions can be dynamically assessed, enabling efficient and adaptive resource management in edge-based deployments.

Figure 5.9: 3D illustration of the curve fitting extracted by the second-order polynomial regression model.

A 3D visualization of the second-order polynomial regression model is depicted in Figure 5.9. As both the number of agents and the prediction horizon increase, the system's complexity naturally rises, reflecting the nonlinear relationship captured by the fitted model.

Sequentially, the equilibrium resource allocation $r_e(t)$ can be estimated using the function $f_2(c(t))$, as expressed in (5.21). This relationship is also depicted in the ‘‘Resource Allocation’’ block of Figure 2.4.

$$r_e(t) = f_2(c(t)), \quad (5.21)$$

where

$$f_2(c(t)) = w_2 \cdot c(t)$$

where $w_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ refers to a weight scalar to normalize the second-order polynomial regression model to the CPU shares.

5.6.2 Online Control Law

Edge-controlled systems, much like any networked system, are subject to time delays, as depicted in Figure 5.10. These delays are related to the communication process and can be divided into UL delays (τ_u) and DL delays (τ_d). Moreover, the controller's response time, owned to the processing time τ_p , is also crucial. Leveraging the computational proximity and responsiveness of edge infrastructure, this work enables dynamic assignment of resources to regulate controller processing time, as elaborated in this section.

Figure 5.10: Block diagram of the proposed edge architecture. The architecture includes the dynamic resource allocation modules in the gray frame and the centralized controllers in the blue frame. The operation within the red frame are executed offline.

For the closed-loop system to maintain stability, as demonstrated in the previous chapters, it is crucial that the total RTT delay, defined as $\tau_{rtt}(t) = \tau_p(t) + \tau_u(t) + \tau_d(t)$, stays within a specified maximum allowable time, τ_{max} . Thus, compliance with (5.22) is mandatory.

$$\tau_{rtt}(t) \leq \tau_{max} \quad (5.22a)$$

$$\implies \tau_p(t) \leq \tau_{max} - \tau_u(t) - \tau_d(t) \quad (5.22b)$$

Therefore, a control law is designed, as described in Section 5.6.2, to ensure that the total RTT delay complies with (5.22), within some given bounded delays.

Dynamic Resource Allocation Control Law

To ensure the computation of a feasible response time within the desired time frame, resource modeling allows determining the equilibrium resources $r_e(t)$ based on the number of agents and the prediction horizon. However, stability of the closed-loop system must also be maintained in the presence of time delays. To address this, an additional term, $r_c(t)$, is introduced to allocate extra resources to centralized control applications whenever a reduction in $\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)$ is required. Since the RTT $\tau_{\text{rtt}}(t)$ must satisfy (5.22a), and by extension, $\tau_p(t)$ must comply with (5.22b), the estimated RTT $\hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t)$ is computed based on the moving average of the communication and processing delays of the CNMPC. Given the UL delay, the delayed information $\hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t - \tau_u(t))$ is utilized, as expressed in (5.23).

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t - \tau_u(t)) = & \tau_p^{\text{av}}(t - \tau_u(t)) + \tau_u^{\text{av}}(t - \tau_u(t)) \\ & + \tau_d^{\text{av}}(t - \tau_u(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (5.23)$$

where τ_p^{av} , τ_u^{av} , and τ_d^{av} are the moving average processing time, UL delay, and DL delay, respectively, calculated using a sliding window method (5.24).

$$\tau^{\text{av}}(t) = \tau^{\text{av}}(t - 1) + \frac{\tau(t) - \tau(t - M)}{M}, \quad (5.24)$$

where

$$\tau^{\text{av}}(t - 1) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \tau(t - i),$$

where M is the size of the sliding window.

Given (5.23), a control law that calculates the additional resource allocation $r_c(t)$ is designed based on the error $e_\tau(t)$, which represents the deviation of $\hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}$ from τ_{max} , as expressed in (5.25).

$$r_c(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } e_\tau(t) \geq 0 \\ f_3(e_\tau(t)), & \text{if } e_\tau(t) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (5.25)$$

where

$$e_\tau(t) = \tau_{\text{max}} - \hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t - \tau_u(t))$$

When $e_\tau(t) \geq 0$, the constraint (5.22a) is satisfied, and $r_c(t)$ is set to zero. In this case, the CPU shares are allocated solely based on the equilibrium resources $r_e(t)$. However, when $e_\tau(t) < 0$, additional resources are allocated using a control signal $f_3(e_\tau(t))$, defined as in (5.26).

$$f_3(e_\tau(t)) = K \cdot e_\tau(t) = K \cdot (\tau_{\text{max}} - \hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t - \tau_u(t))) \quad (5.26)$$

where K is a proportional gain.

The requested resources $r_{\text{req}}(t)$ are computed by combining the equilibrium resource allocation $r_e(t)$ (5.21) with the communication compensatory resources $r_c(t)$ (5.26), as shown in (5.27).

$$r_{\text{req}}(t) = f_4(r_e(t), r_c(t)) \quad (5.27a)$$

$$\implies r_{\text{req}}(t) = w_3 \cdot r_e(t) + w_4 \cdot r_c(t), \quad (5.27b)$$

where $w_3, w_4 \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ are experimentally defined weights used to address modeling and control inaccuracies. The components are given by:

$$r_e(t) = w_2 \cdot c(t) \quad (5.21)$$

$$r_c(t) = K \cdot (\tau_{\text{max}} - \hat{\tau}_{\text{rtt}}(t - \tau_u(t))) \quad (5.26)$$

By integrating the second-order polynomial regression model with the control law, the system dynamically adjusts resource allocation to maintain stability in the closed-loop system while ensuring scalability with respect to the number of agents. This approach is summarized in the resource allocation workflow illustrated in Figure 5.10.

5.6.3 Optimization of Resource Allocation

When dynamically requesting resources for controller execution, it is essential to respect constraints imposed by both the controller characteristics and the specifications of the k8s cluster. Therefore, to optimize the deployment of controllers within the k8s cluster, an optimization problem is posed. The problem formulation also accounts for changes in the number of active agents during operation. In cases of unexpected agent behavior or failure, the affected agents can be excluded from the optimization problem, allowing the system to reallocate resources and reconfigure controller deployments accordingly.

Cost Function

The goal of deploying centralized control schemes in the cluster is to ensure that the resources requested by the centralized control applications do not exceed the available computational capacity of the cluster. Simultaneously, to optimize the performance of the centralized control closed-loop systems, both the number of agents controlled by each controller \mathbf{n}_{apc} , and the prediction horizon length \mathbf{h} for each controller are aimed to be maximized. In addition, the cost function should return the optimized resource request for each controller, denoted as \mathbf{r}_{opt} .

However, increasing the number of agents per controller and the prediction horizon length raises the complexity of each centralized application, which, in turn, increases the required resources, as outlined in Section 5.6.1.

Two different scenarios are considered: (a) the available resources remain constant, and the optimization problem is evaluated accordingly; (b) the available resources change dynamically, simulating a realistic environment where external applications simultaneously utilize cluster resources.

For both scenarios, a cost function is considered, that deploy the centralized controllers in the cluster by optimizing \mathbf{n}_{apc} , \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{r}_{opt} , as formulated in (5.28).

$$J_r = \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} \sum_{s=1}^{n_{k8s}} (w_5 \cdot n_{\text{apc},j,k} + w_6 \cdot h_{j,k}) x_{j,s,k}, \quad (5.28)$$

where $w_5, w_6 \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ are weights for the maximization of $n_{\text{apc},j}$ and h_j , and $x_{j,s,k} \in \{0, 1\}$ is a binary variable indicating whether the j^{th} controller is active.

Centralized Control Constraints

To ensure that the deployment of the centralized controllers complies to their specifications and limitations, the constraints described in (5.29) are introduced.

$$n_{\text{apc},j} \leq n_{\text{max}} \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n_c \quad (5.29a)$$

$$h_j \leq h_{\text{max}} \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n_c \quad (5.29b)$$

These constraints ensure that no controller is assigned more agents than its maximum capacity, denoted by n_{max} , and that the number of prediction horizon steps remains within the allowable limit, h_{max} .

Resource Constraints

Next, the optimization problem must respect the resource constraints of the k8s cluster, particularly the available computational capacity. If this constraint is violated and the requested resources exceed availability, the deployment of the controllers will stall or fail. To prevent this, the constraints in (5.30) are introduced.

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_c} r_{\text{req},j} \cdot x_{j,s} \leq r_{k8s,s} \quad \forall s = 1, \dots, n_{k8s} \quad (5.30a)$$

$$r_{\text{req},j} \leq r_{k8s,s} + M \cdot (1 - x_{j,s}) \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n_c \\ \forall s = 1, \dots, n_{k8s} \quad (5.30b)$$

These constraints ensure that the computational resources, $r_{\text{req},j}$, requested by each controller j remain within the available resources $r_{k8s,s}$ of the cluster, thereby guaranteeing stable and successful deployment. This is achieved by ensuring that each controller is assigned to a k8s node with sufficient resources to meet its resource requests, as expressed in (5.30b). Simultaneously, as multiple controllers can be deployed to a single k8s node, constraint (5.30a) guarantees that the total resources requested by all controllers on a given node do not exceed the node's computational capacity.

System Constraints

Finally, the system constraints are defined to guarantee the smooth operation of the entire closed-loop system, as expressed in (5.31).

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_c} n_{\text{apc},j} = n_a \quad (5.31a)$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{n_{k8s}} x_{j,s} = 1 \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n_c \quad (5.31b)$$

$$n_{\text{apc},j} \leq n_{\text{max}} \cdot \sum_{s=1}^{n_{k8s}} x_{j,s} \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n_c \quad (5.31c)$$

$$h_j \leq h_{\text{max}} \cdot \sum_{s=1}^{n_{k8s}} x_{j,s} \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, n_c \quad (5.31d)$$

These constraints ensure that every agent is controlled by exactly one controller (5.31a), each controller is deployed on a single k8s cluster node (5.31b), and controllers manage agents and set prediction horizons only when they are active (5.31c)–(5.31d).

Optimization

The optimization problem is formulated as a MILP [177], involving integer decision variables ($n_{\text{apc},j}$, h_j) and continuous variables ($r_{\text{req},j}$). To solve this problem, the Gurobi optimizer [178] is used, aiming to maximize the cost function (5.28) while ensuring compliance with the specified constraints. The complete optimization problem is described in (5.32).

$$\text{Maximize } J_T(\mathbf{n}_{\text{apc},k}, \mathbf{h}_k; \mathbf{x}_k) \quad (5.32a)$$

$$\text{s.t.: Constraints (5.29a) – (5.29b)}$$

$$\text{Constraint (5.30a) – (5.30b)}$$

$$\text{Constraints (5.31a) – (5.31d)}$$

After the optimization problem is solved, all necessary information for deploying the controllers is forwarded to the scheduler. The scheduler receives this information along with the resource allocation vector, \mathbf{r}_{alc} , which specifies the final resource allocation for each controller and the respective node of the cluster where the controller should be deployed. Consequently, the scheduler is responsible for deploying, updating, and removing controllers on demand, based on the output of the optimization problem. The scheduler leverages k8s features, and the `kubectl` command line tool, to ensure seamless execution of all the modules of the architectures.

5.6.4 Evaluation & Results

To validate the proposed architecture, an edge computing environment was established using a three-node k8s cluster, as detailed in Chapter 2. Additionally, the system integrates a varying number of aerial agents from the MAS described in Section 5.4.3. The scheduling mechanism dynamically deploys and updates controller resources based on the outcomes of the proposed resource allocation strategy.

The experimental validation is divided into three main parts. Firstly, the accuracy and performance of the second-order polynomial regression model developed in Section 5.6.1 is evaluated. This step verifies the model’s ability to predict equilibrium resources across diverse system configurations, including varying agent counts and control horizons, as visualized in Figure 5.11. Next, the designed control law for delay compensation, as described in Section 5.6.2 is validated. This experiment assesses the effectiveness of the control strategy in maintaining system stability by mitigating time delays in the centralized control loop. Finally, the optimization problem and the dynamic resource allocation mechanism within the three-node k8s cluster, developed in Section 5.6.3 is evaluated. This assessment focuses on the system’s ability to adapt resource allocation to changes in workload and maintain optimal performance, while respecting the resource availability of the k8s cluster.

Resources Evaluation

The model introduced in Section 5.6.1 was evaluated through experimental tests with varying number of the agent and prediction horizon lengths, as demonstrated in Figure 5.11. It aims to precisely estimate resource requirements based on these variables, ensuring efficient utilization while keeping CPU consumption within desirable limits. As seen in Figure 5.8, it is essential that CPU consumption remains below 60%, regardless of the number of agent and prediction horizon lengths. This approach showcases the model’s capability to adjust to the computational requirements of edge-based MAS, providing scalable and reliable system operations.

Figure 5.11: CPU utilization for different combinations of $(n_{apc,j}, h_j)$. The CPU percentage remains within desired thresholds for every combination of $n_{apc,j}$ and h_j .

Figure 5.12: System time delays measured comprising: (a) UL; (b) DL; (c) solver time; (d) RTT. The dashed lines denote average values computed over a sliding window of 1000 samples, while the faded lines indicate the raw data. In (d), the yellow dashed line indicates the maximum permissible delay, τ_{\max} . (e) displays the desired (solid line) versus actual (filled area) CPU allocations in millicpu.

To estimate the CPU utilization, (5.33) is applied.

$$CPU = \frac{CPU_{\text{used}}}{CPU_{\text{pod}}} \cdot 100\%, \quad (5.33)$$

where CPU_{used} refer to the measured CPU shares used by the centralized controllers, and CPU_{pod} refer to the allocated CPU shares based on \mathbf{r}_{alc} . Both CPU_{used} and CPU_{pod} are expressed in millicpu.

As illustrated in Figure 5.11, the model effectively stabilizes CPU usage even with variations in both the number of agents and the prediction horizon. The number of agents per controller can range $\in [1, n_{\max}]$, where $n_{\max} = 9$, while the prediction horizon may vary $\in [1, h_{\max}]$, where $h_{\max} = 40$ for $n_{\text{apc},j} \leq 7$, and $h_{\max} = 20$ for $7 < n_{\text{apc},j} \leq 9$.

Stability Validation

The system's stability requirements are analyzed and the control law's performance is evaluated by tracking delays and computing moving averages over a sliding window containing 1000 samples, as depicted in Figure 5.12. To challenge the system's stability, an extra artificial UL delay of 0.100 s is added.

As the RTT got closer to the maximum allowable delay due to the increase in UL delay (refer to Figure 5.12 a), the control law dynamically allocated more resources to the controllers (as shown in Figure 5.12 e), keeping the RTT within acceptable boundaries (see Figure 5.12 d). This dynamic adjustment enables the controllers to accelerate the CNMPC optimization process and produce viable solutions more rapidly, demonstrated by the reduced solver time in Figure 5.12 c. When delays extend beyond what the control law can manage, the robots revert to fallback onboard actions, as detailed in the previous chapters.

Optimization Assessment

This evaluation demonstrates the optimizer’s capacity to handle dynamic workload scaling, controller deployment, and intelligent distribution of computational tasks in a constrained edge environment with a focus on changing number of agents, n_a . The optimizer accounts for these variations and computes the number of agents per controller ($n_{\text{apc},j}$), the prediction horizon length (h_j), and the optimized resource allocation ($r_{\text{opt},j}$) for each controller j , while respecting the system constraints. Figure 5.13 provides a detailed illustration of the optimizer’s output, showcasing the distribution of centralized controllers across the k8s cluster nodes.

Figure 5.13: Illustration of the output of the optimizer, where the columns correspond to the three k8s cluster nodes (Node 1, Node 2, and Node 3). The rows present (a) the number of agents assigned to each controller; (b) the prediction horizon lengths; (c) the optimized resources of each controller; (d) the allocated resources at each node, along with the available resources.

The figure highlights, for each node of the cluster, the allocation details, including the number of agents managed by each controller, the prediction horizon assigned to each controller, and the corresponding resource allocation. Notably, a single node can host multiple controllers, provided the optimizer generates feasible solutions within the defined constraints.

For instance, at time step 36, the proposed framework demonstrates its scalability and efficiency by controlling 65 agents through the deployment of 15 controllers distributed across 3 edge nodes. This distribution is determined by the optimization problem, which ensures that the allocation of controllers and resources across the servers complies to system constraints while maximizing performance.

The different controllers are represented by distinct colors in Figure 5.13. The total computational capacity of the nodes is indicated by a dashed red line in Figure 5.13 d. This framework accounts for the dynamic variation of available edge resources, as each node can host multiple applications, and the resource demands of these applications can vary at each time step. Nodes are capable of running multiple controllers simultaneously, with the requested resources for each controller depicted in Figure 5.13 c.

The controllers monitor $n_{\text{apc},j}$ agents, illustrated in Figure 5.13 a, and plan for a prediction horizon h_j , shown in Figure 5.13 b. Depending on the total available resources, each controller dynamically adjusts the number of agents it controls and the prediction horizon it plans for, guided by the optimization problem defined in (5.32). This ensures that the system operates within its resource constraints while optimizing performance.

Figure 5.14 illustrates the CPU usage of the controllers during a mission. Since the RTT is not directly controlled but instead adjust the resources of the k8s pods, it is crucial to maintain CPU percentage levels within desired ranges to ensure bounded solver times. To achieve this the optimization problem is employed, and resources are dynamically allocated as needed, following the second-order polynomial regression model, and the designed control law. Once the new resource allocation takes effect, and the optimization problem generates a feasible solution, the CPU usage, and solver time remain within desired values.

Figure 5.14: CPU usage of the controllers' pods.

The primary goal was to ensure that the resource allocation strategy provided sufficient resources for the execution of the controller. This objective was successfully achieved, as demonstrated by the CPU usage data. Throughout the mission, CPU usage remained below the defined threshold of 60%, as illustrated in Figure 5.14. These results confirm that the proposed resource allocation strategy maintains consistent controller performance and prevents overload, even under dynamic mission conditions and varying agent configurations.

Table 5.4: Comparison of regression models and sensitivity analysis using WMSE

Model	Data Range	WMSE
First-order polynomial	Full dataset	23.31
Second-order polynomial	$n_{\text{apc},j} \in [1, 4] \ \& \ h_j \in [10, 40]$	20.78
Second-order polynomial	$n_{\text{apc},j} \in [1, 6] \ \& \ h_j \in [10, 40]$	24.21
Second-order polynomial	$n_{\text{apc},j} \in [4, 9] \ \& \ h_j \in [10, 40]$	24.05
Second-order polynomial	$n_{\text{apc},j} \in [1, 9] \ \& \ h_j \in [10, 20]$	7.47
Second-order polynomial	$n_{\text{apc},j} \in [1, 9] \ \& \ h_j \in [20, 40]$	28.38
Second-order polynomial	Full dataset	22.57
Third-order polynomial	Full dataset	21.93
Exponential	Full dataset	29.19
Logarithmic	Full dataset	26.78

5.7 Discussion

This chapter presented a dynamic resource allocation strategy tailored for offloaded centralized control systems. To support this contribution, several critical aspects are discussed, including model selection, parameter sensitivity, system complexity, and robustness. These considerations provide further insight into the framework's behavior and highlight areas for future improvement and practical deployment.

5.7.1 Model Selection & Sensitivity Analysis

The proposed framework is designed to support a variety of models that correlate the number of agents and the prediction horizon to the application's computational complexity. Depending on the application, different functional forms, such as polynomial, exponential, or logarithmic models, may be appropriate. This flexibility allows the approach to be generalized across different classes of control applications.

In this study, a second-order polynomial regression model is selected because it offered the best trade-off between accuracy and complexity. As shown in Table 5.4, it achieves a lower normalized Weighted Mean Squared Error (WMSE) compared to linear, exponential, and logarithmic models for the full dataset ($n_{\text{apc},j} \in [1, 4] \ \& \ h_j \in [10, 40]$), while avoiding the overfitting risk and computational cost of higher-order polynomials. Nevertheless, the framework is not constrained by this specific choice. The control law and optimization formulation described in Sections 5.6.2 and 5.6.3, respectively, are designed to tolerate model inaccuracies and ensuring system requirements, even when alternative models are used.

Table 5.4 presents the WMSE values computed using (5.34), and Figure 5.15 shows the 3D surfaces for the compared models. The corresponding projections in the $n_{\text{apc},j}$ -plane and h_j -plane are shown in Figure 5.16 top and bottom figures, respectively.

$$\text{WMSE} = \frac{1}{n_o} \sum_{i=1}^{n_o} \left(\frac{y_{\text{data},i} - f_1(n_{\text{apc},j}, h_j, \mathbf{p})}{\sigma_i} \right)^2 \quad (5.34)$$

Figure 5.15: 3D illustrations of (a) the first-order polynomial; (b) the third-order polynomial; (c) the exponential; (d) the logarithmic model.

Figure 5.16: Projection of (a)-(b) the first-order polynomial; (c)-(d) the third-order polynomial; (e)-(f) the exponential; (g)-(h) the logarithmic model, in the $n_{apc,j}$ -plane and in the h_j -plane respectively.

These results help illustrate how different models capture the relationship between the number of agents, the prediction horizon, and the resulting application complexity, guiding the presented strategy for predicting computational demands and allocating appropriate edge resources.

Furthermore, to analyze the robustness of the selected model, Figure 5.17 shows a sensitivity analysis of the second-order polynomial regression using subsets of the collected data. The corresponding WMSE values for each subset are reported in columns 2–6 of Table 5.4, demonstrating the model’s consistency and generalizability across varying input domains.

5.7.2 System Complexity

The framework comprises two key computational components: (i) the offline resource model based on polynomial regression, and (ii) the online optimization-based synthesis of edge-deployed centralized controllers. The resource model is computed offline and does not affect the runtime complexity, as its evaluation at runtime has constant time complexity, $\mathcal{O}(1)$ per controller.

Figure 5.17: 3D illustrations of the second-order polynomial model for (a) $n_{apc,j} \in [1, 4]$; (b) $n_{apc,j} \in [1, 6]$; (c) $n_{apc,j} \in [4, 9]$; (d) $h_j \in [10, 20]$; (e) $h_j \in [20, 40]$; (f) full dataset.

The online resource allocation is formulated as a quadratic optimization problem with linear constraints and solved using the Gurobi optimization solver. The computational complexity of this step primarily depends on the number of controllers and the number of edge nodes. Since the number of edge nodes is constant and the number of controllers increases only when necessary (e.g., in cases of infeasibility), the system scales efficiently in practice. This makes the framework suitable for real-time operation, even as the number of agents or control requirements increase.

5.7.3 System Robustness

While this work aims to present a novel approach for optimizing the offloading and deployment of edge-based centralized controllers through dynamic computational resource allocation, and demonstrates its effectiveness through multiple experimental results, there are hardware limitations and technical aspects that should be considered.

Closed-loop control systems operating over a network are inherently affected by communication delays. The suggested approach accounts for these delays through multiple layers of mitigation. The state estimator corrects state drift caused by RTT delays in Section 3.3, while the control strategy ensures that the total RTT delay remains within the bounds to meet the stability requirements of the system, as described in (5.22a). This is feasible only if the variation in communication delays is bounded and the dynamic resource allocation strategy is able to compensate.

While the proposed delay-aware control mechanism cannot fully compensate for severe or abrupt network delays, it is well-suited for addressing slow-varying delays, which are commonly observed in real-world NCS. These slow variations typically arise from periodic background traffic fluctuations, temporary resource contention at the edge, or modest congestion patterns within shared wireless links, such as those seen in 5G UL scheduling or TDD schemes. By leveraging a sliding-window average of the RTT, the control law is capable of gradually adjusting computational resource allocations to maintain stability and responsiveness under these conditions. This makes it highly effective in practice for sustaining closed-loop control quality in dynamic but moderately time-varying network environments, which are often encountered in edge-enabled multi-agent deployments.

While the system adapts to varying delays using feedback-based resource reallocation, its performance may degrade under severe conditions such as high packet loss, persistent network congestion, or limited BW. In such cases, agents fall back to onboard operation to maintain stability and safety, as presented in Section 3.4. Extensive delays are assumed to occur only temporarily, during which agents rely on onboard mode and operate through PID controllers. Once the RTT delay again satisfies (5.22a), the system resumes edge-based centralized control. However, persistent or large-scale delays and BW constraints remain a limitation, and strategies such as dynamic 5G QoS [179] could be explored to address these challenges.

Communication range is closely tied to these delays. Agents must maintain a connection with the edge cluster to transmit odometry data and receive control commands. In indoor environments, this connection can be maintained through Wi-Fi or cellular protocols [52], while outdoor scenarios may rely on 5G or similar technologies. However, operations in remote areas without reliable network coverage present a significant limitation. In such cases, agents would be forced to operate entirely in onboard mode. When within communication range, it remains essential that the system continues to meet the delay constraint in (5.22a), regardless of network congestion or variability.

Battery life is another significant constraint in UAV operations. Although this approach does not directly address battery management, offloading computation to edge servers can help extend flight time by allowing the use of lighter onboard computers [180]. Nevertheless, battery limitations impose upper bounds on both mission duration. In scenarios with limited battery capacity, the energy cost of maintaining persistent communication with the edge must be balanced against the need for accurate and responsive control. Such extension could consider energy-aware scheduling and control strategies to further extend operational time and improve overall system efficiency.

Despite these limitations, the architecture is designed to degrade smoothly under adverse conditions, preserving safety through fallback strategies and resuming full operation as soon as system constraints permit. When communication quality deteriorates or edge resources become temporarily saturated, the system transitions gracefully from edge-offloaded control to onboard execution without abrupt performance loss. This seamless degradation ensures that agents remain operational and maintain stable behavior even during network disruptions or high-latency periods. Once the network recovers and stable connectivity is reestablished, the architecture automatically restores the edge-based control mode, allowing the system to regain optimal performance and coordination without requiring manual intervention.

5.8 Concluding Remarks

This chapter presented a comprehensive and novel framework for dynamic resource allocation in edge-offloaded centralized control systems, with a particular focus on aerial robotics MAS. As the most substantial contribution of the thesis, this chapter addressed the critical scalability and stability challenges inherent in CNMPC for large-scale MAS.

Building upon the architectural and control foundations introduced in earlier chapters, this work extended the edge-enabled CNMPC framework by incorporating adaptive, delay-aware, and resource-constrained deployment strategies. A key aspect of the approach is the tight integration of application-level requirements with the underlying edge infrastructure, enabling a closed-loop feedback between control performance and computational provisioning.

The chapter introduced a reactive scheduling mechanism that dynamically monitors the system workload and deploys or reconfigures CNMPC controllers across a k8s-based edge cluster. Through continuous observation of agent counts and mission demands, the scheduling mechanism ensured that the control architecture remained flexible, scalable, and resource-efficient.

To overcome the inherent trade-offs between prediction accuracy, computational load, and time-delay constraints, a dynamic resource-aware control strategy was developed. This includes: (i) an offline resource modeling pipeline using second-order polynomial regression to estimate the computational complexity of CNMPCs as a function of the number of agents and prediction horizon; (ii) a delay-compensating control law that adjusts computational resources based on observed RTT delays to maintain closed-loop stability, and (iii) a multi-constraint optimization formulation that determines the optimal allocation of controllers, agents, prediction horizons, and CPU shares, subject to application, system, and resource constraints.

The proposed methodology was extensively validated through experiments on a real-time cloud platform and simulated UAV missions, confirming its effectiveness in maintaining stable and performant operation under dynamically changing mission profiles. The experimental results demonstrated the scalability of the architecture up to dozens of agents, the responsiveness of the control law to communication delays, and the robustness of the optimization framework under varying system loads.

Moreover, the chapter addressed key challenges such as model selection, system complexity, and runtime robustness in networked robotic environments. The discussion section underscored the generalizability of the proposed approach beyond CNMPC, as the framework is inherently modular and capable of supporting other computationally intensive robotic applications with similar resource-adaptive requirements.

In conclusion, this chapter represents a significant advancement in the integration of control theory, edge computing, and cloud-native orchestration. By bridging the gap between real-time control and infrastructure-level resource management, it paves the way for scalable, delay-aware, and resource-optimized deployment of centralized control strategies in future large-scale multi-agent robotic systems. The techniques introduced herein contribute not only to control-aware scheduling but also to the broader vision of adaptive autonomy in cyber-physical systems. Importantly, the presented framework enables dynamic interaction between the control objectives and the underlying compute design, offering a foundation upon which future systems can autonomously adapt to changing mission demands and system constraints.

This combination between high-level decision-making and low-level execution marks a step forward toward resilient, intelligent, and infrastructure-aware robotic autonomy.

The next and final chapter synthesizes the contributions of this thesis, outlines key insights and lessons learned, and proposes promising directions for ongoing and future research. It revisits the research questions posed at the outset and reflects on how the developed architectures, control strategies, and resource-aware mechanisms collectively address the challenges of enabling real-time, scalable, and resilient robotic autonomy through edge computing. By combining the theoretical advancements and experimental validations presented across the previous chapters, the concluding chapter offers a comprehensive view of the thesis' impact and positions its outcomes within the broader context of smart robotics and cyber-physical systems.

6.1 Research Outcomes

This thesis explored the intersection of edge computing and control theory for robotic MAS, with a particular emphasis on dynamic resource allocation in time-critical, computationally intensive control loops. Through the design, implementation, and validation of novel architectures and algorithms, the research presented herein delivers a set of significant theoretical and practical outcomes across the domains of networked control systems, edge-cloud orchestration, and robotics.

Beginning with a thorough investigation of delay-aware control frameworks, the thesis proposed mechanisms to mitigate the effects of end-to-end latency by offloading key control functions to nearby edge servers. This was achieved through the integration of predictive state estimation, fallback control policies, and robust switching strategies, components that collectively ensured resilience and safety during network degradation. These architectures were validated through real-world experiments and simulations using both aerial and ground robots, demonstrating bounded tracking error and seamless transitions between offloaded and onboard controllers.

Building on this foundation, the thesis then introduced scalable edge-based architectures for centralized control of MAS. The use of centralized NMPC schemes enabled predictive coordination among agents, while edge offloading mitigated the otherwise prohibitive computational costs. The results showcased that, through strategic architectural design and communication-aware constraint modeling, it is possible to achieve real-time performance at scale, something previously limited by onboard hardware or rigid distributed schemes.

The final outcome of this work lies in the development of a dynamic resource-aware control framework. This framework introduced a feedback-driven mechanism for allocating computational resources based on control complexity and real-time delay. By modeling the resource demands of CNMPCs using second-order polynomial regression and embedding a delay-compensating control law, the proposed approach ensured that computational resources were allocated optimally, both to preserve closed-loop stability and to maximize performance.

Furthermore, a mixed-integer optimization formulation was proposed to determine not only resource allocation but also the number and configuration of deployed controllers, considering the system state and cluster capacity. The resulting architecture was shown to adapt seamlessly to changes in agent count, prediction horizon, and network load.

Collectively, these research outcomes present a unified and experimentally validated framework for deploying high-performance, scalable, and resilient control applications at the network edge. By tightly integrating control-theoretic rigor with modern orchestration technologies such as k8s, this thesis contributes a novel paradigm for the operation of future robotic MAS in real-world, resource-constrained environments.

6.2 Summary of Obtained Results

The work presented in this thesis has demonstrated several key results that advance the field of edge-enabled control for robotic MAS. These results span theoretical contributions, algorithmic innovations, and experimental validations, and together form a cohesive narrative supporting the feasibility and effectiveness of deploying centralized control schemes over resource-constrained and time-critical environments.

The first set of results focused on the challenge of time delay in edge-offloaded control architectures. Through a combination of predictive state estimation and fallback control modes, a resilient framework was developed to ensure safe operation even under high and variable latency conditions. The delay compensation module was shown to significantly reduce tracking errors by anticipating the effect of control latency and generating predictive state trajectories. Experimental validation using real UAV platforms demonstrated that the system maintained safe operation and control accuracy even when network conditions deteriorated, confirming the practical relevance of the proposed techniques.

Subsequently, CNMPC was extended to MAS operating over an edge infrastructure. A edge-offloaded CNMPC framework was developed and evaluated across scenarios involving both ground and aerial robots. Key results showed that the centralized controller could successfully generate safe and coordinated trajectories for multiple agents, while respecting inter-agent and obstacle avoidance constraints. Importantly, the offloading to edge servers enabled the use of long prediction horizons and complex constraints, which would be computationally infeasible on lightweight onboard processors. The system was experimentally validated in both hardware and simulated environments, confirming its ability to scale with the number of agents while maintaining real-time responsiveness.

The most significant results were obtained in the development of the dynamic resource-aware control framework. Here, the relationship between controller complexity, prediction horizon, number of agents, and computational demand was formally modeled using a second-order polynomial regression. This model enabled the accurate estimation of CPU resource needs, which was then integrated into an online feedback-based control law designed to maintain RTT latency within safe bounds. The control law dynamically allocated additional resources to controllers when delays approached the predefined thresholds, ensuring closed-loop stability.

Furthermore, the deployment of controllers was formulated as a mixed-integer linear optimization problem, taking into account cluster-wide resource constraints and application-specific requirements. The proposed scheduling and deployment mechanism was shown to adapt in real time to changing system conditions, including varying numbers of agents and dynamic resource availability. Experiments with up to 65 UAVs and a three-node k8s cluster demonstrated that the system could successfully allocate resources, reconfigure controller deployments, and maintain stable operation even under high computational load.

Altogether, the results of this thesis confirm that it is both feasible and advantageous to employ centralized control schemes for large-scale robotic MAS using edge computing. Through systematic modeling, real-time control, and intelligent scheduling, the presented framework delivers scalable, resilient, and high-performance control capabilities suitable for deployment in complex and dynamic environments.

6.3 Limitations & Lessons Learned

While the outcomes of this research demonstrate significant advances in edge-enabled control and dynamic resource allocation for MAS, several limitations were encountered throughout the work. These limitations provided valuable insights that guided the refinement of the proposed methodologies and revealed opportunities for future research and improvement.

A primary limitation arises from the dependency of the proposed architectures on network connectivity and communication reliability. Although extensive efforts were made to compensate for RTT delays and to ensure resilience through fallback actions, the performance of the edge-offloaded control schemes still depends on bounded network conditions. In scenarios with persistent congestion, or intermittent coverage, the quality of control inevitably degrades, forcing the system to revert to onboard operation. While this ensures safety, it also reduces performance. This observation highlights the need for tighter integration between network-layer QoS management and control-layer resource allocation, particularly in 5G infrastructures.

Moreover, this work primarily focused on streaming low-BW telemetry, such as odometry and control commands, which can be reliably transmitted in most wireless network configurations. However, ongoing and future research efforts based on the proposed framework, particularly those involving perception-driven applications, will likely require the transmission of significantly larger data streams, such as LiDAR point clouds, RGB-D camera feeds, or semantic maps. These data types impose much higher demands on the network level, and can lead to bottlenecks due to BW or throughput constraints. Under such conditions, additional mechanisms, such as data compression, priority-aware scheduling, or cross-layer optimization, may be necessary to ensure that real-time control performance is not compromised.

Another inherent limitation lies in the scalability of centralized NMPC schemes themselves. While the proposed framework enables the deployment of multiple CNMPC instances to overcome the computational limitations associated with a single centralized controller, each individual CNMPC is still constrained by the number of agents it can feasibly handle. These constraints arise from solver complexity, control horizon length, and the combinatorial explosion of collision avoidance constraints as agent density increases. As such, the framework relies on partitioning the global MAS into smaller subsets, each managed by its own CNMPC.

Although this partitioning approach preserves many of the advantages of centralized control within each subset, such as coordinated planning, constraint handling, and global optimization, it introduces new challenges at the system level. Specifically, the CNMPC instances must operate in parallel while maintaining consistency across agent boundaries. Without proper coordination, inter-group interactions may lead to conflicting plans, collisions at group interfaces, or degraded overall performance. Addressing this issue requires the introduction of higher-level synchronization strategies or inter-controller communication mechanisms.

In this regard, the current framework implicitly assumes that agent partitioning results in loosely coupled groups, and that cross-group conflicts are minimal. While this assumption holds in structured environments or with appropriate mission planning, it may not generalize to all MAS scenarios. To fully scale centralized control across large systems, future extensions should explore hybrid or hierarchical control architectures that blend centralized and distributed principles. For example, decentralized negotiation protocols, distributed constraint enforcement, or consensus-based coordination could be employed between CNMPCs to ensure cohesive system behavior while preserving the tractability of each control group.

Furthermore, although the proposed resource allocation and scheduling strategies successfully mitigated computational bottlenecks through horizontal and vertical scaling, the centralized NMPC formulation inherently becomes more complex as the number of agents increases. The offloading of computation to edge nodes significantly alleviates this challenge, yet real-time feasibility still requires trade-offs between prediction horizon, control frequency, and the total number of controlled agents. These trade-offs must be carefully managed to balance global optimization against computational latency.

From a modeling standpoint, the second-order polynomial regression used for computational complexity estimation provided excellent performance and interpretability within the evaluated range of system parameters. It successfully captured the relationship between the number of agents, prediction horizon, and the computational cost of the centralized NMPC. However, this model relies on the assumption of a relatively smooth nonlinear dependency between control parameters and resource usage. In practice, especially under extreme configurations, such as sudden increases in agent count, solver saturation, or high resource contention, this assumption may not hold, leading to reduced accuracy.

Moreover, the derived model is inherently tied to the characteristics of the infrastructure on which it was trained. Variations in hardware (e.g., CPU architecture, memory BW) or software (e.g., solver implementation, container orchestration configuration) specifications, can significantly influence both execution time and system behavior. As such, deploying the proposed framework on a different edge cluster or in a heterogeneous computing environment would likely require re-training or re-calibrating the complexity model. The parameters of the regression function, and potentially the form of the model itself, must therefore be tuned to reflect the specific hardware and software characteristics of the target system.

While the control law introduced in this work provides robustness against some modeling discrepancies by dynamically adjusting resource allocation based on real-time delay feedback, future extensions may benefit from integrating adaptive or learning-based models. These models could continuously refine their internal estimates in response to system behavior, improving generalization and performance across a wider range of operating conditions.

An additional limitation arises from the use of k8s as the orchestration layer. While it enables scalable and modular deployment of CNMPCs, it is not inherently optimized for hard real-time responsiveness. The delay between issuing a deployment or reconfiguration command and the CNMPC becoming operational depends on multiple factors, including pod scheduling latency, container startup time, and image availability across nodes. These orchestration delays may become critical during fast mission transitions, where quick controller activation is necessary to maintain safe and stable closed-loop behavior.

Furthermore, each CNMPC is a stateful application, requiring persistent information such as the internal solver state, constraint setup, and recent trajectory history to generate coherent predictions. During agent handovers, where one or more UAVs are reassigned from one controller to another, this state must be either reinitialized or transferred. Currently, the system does not support seamless state transfer between CNMPCs, and therefore, each reassignment entails a cold-start of the optimization problem for the new controller. This can temporarily degrade tracking performance, increase latency, or result in control discontinuities. Ensuring robust and low-latency stateful handovers remains a challenge, and future extensions may explore predictive synchronization, state checkpointing, or fast re-initialization techniques to mitigate these issues.

Finally, the experimental validation of the system, while extensive, was mainly conducted within controlled network environments and using simulated or laboratory-scale robotic platforms. Although these setups provided an effective testbed for verifying the theoretical concepts, real-world deployment in large-scale outdoor or industrial scenarios may introduce additional challenges such as unpredictable communication interference, limited BW availability, and hardware heterogeneity. Similarly, while the k8s-based orchestration provided an efficient and modular deployment framework, the reliance on specific container management configurations may limit portability across alternative orchestration environments.

6.4 Ongoing & Future Research Directions

This thesis sets the groundwork for scalable, delay-aware, and resource-optimized control in robotic MAS by proposing a comprehensive framework that spans control-theoretic modeling, edge-computing orchestration, and network-aware scheduling. However, the evolving demands of robotics and cyber-physical systems call for further extensions and refinements of this foundation. The ongoing research activities and emerging challenges discussed below offer promising directions to push the boundaries of edge-assisted autonomy.

One major area of ongoing work focuses on real-time point cloud transmission and mapping for MAS. In that end, lightweight point cloud compression for edge-assisted MAS SLAM and global environment mapping is crucial. In this context, a custom compression algorithm is being designed, with the goal of enabling real-time LiDAR data transmission from resource-constrained aerial robots to edge computing clusters. The compressed point cloud data streams must then be transmitted to an edge cluster for joint processing and global map generation. The algorithm is designed to preserve high reconstruction fidelity of the compressed 3D point clouds. Early results show that this method achieves a significant reduction in transmitted data volume, with minimal degradation in reconstruction accuracy, allowing real-time operation.

This line of work complements and extends the framework developed in this thesis, addressing a key limitation identified earlier, namely, that while the current architecture supports control and odometry-level streaming, future extensions must also support high-throughput perceptual data offloading for collaborative mapping, object recognition, and scene understanding. The combination of compression-aware data encoding on the robot side and dynamic resource allocation on the edge side opens the door to fully perception-enabled edge robotics, further improving autonomy, scalability, and MAS collaboration.

Furthermore, another ongoing research direction which involves offloading LiDAR-based perception applications, such LiDAR Inertial Odometry (LIO) in Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)-denied environments, addresses this bottleneck through the integration of Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput (L4S) protocols with point cloud compression algorithms (e.g., `Draco`). This work proposes a 5G-compatible offloading mechanism that allows robots to stream compressed LiDAR data in real time to an edge cluster for processing, enabling computational offloading without compromising map quality or transmission latency. This expands the offloading scope from lightweight control decisions to dense perceptual tasks and introduces new challenges in compression-accuracy trade-offs and bitrate control, which are actively being addressed through bitrate scheduling and adaptive streaming mechanisms.

Complementing the above is another line of research that integrates 5G dynamic QoS management with k8s-based application orchestration. This work introduces an architecture where both edge resources and network throughput are optimized using through k8s pod-level resource allocation and 5G QoS configuration. Early investigations apply this framework to heterogeneous applications, including CNMPC and vision-based DL models. The core challenge lies in coordinating computational and communication resources in a closed loop, such that application-level QoS requirements are satisfied across the system. This line of research aims to generalize and abstract the dynamic resource control mechanisms presented in this thesis to accommodate a wider range of robotic and AI workloads beyond control.

Another direction builds upon the CNMPC offloading framework to support global map sharing and cooperative navigation across multiple robots. In this work, robots collaboratively construct a global map at the edge, and sub-map windows are dynamically generated and streamed to robots in the field for real-time localization and planning. A k8s-native deployment architecture is used, relying on `MinIO` object storage instead of persistent volumes, which simplifies the runtime orchestration of map updates and localization services. This work aims to reduce robot-side computation while still enabling rich SLAM-based autonomy, particularly in multi-robot environments where dynamic map reuse and update consistency become critical. It also builds the bridge between MAS control and collaborative mapping.

In parallel, a fourth research direction investigates the use of network heatmaps for intelligent mission planning and data offloading. Preliminary results have been obtained from subterranean deployments, where network performance characteristics (e.g., throughput, RTT, and packet loss) are geospatially mapped to build heatmaps. These maps are then used by the robot's planner to identify communication-aware trajectories, to balance coverage, safety, and reliable transmission to the edge. This work can introduce optimization formulations that will include not only traditional motion objectives (such as path smoothness or obstacle avoidance) but also communication-reliability constraints for adaptive data scheduling and offloading.

More broadly, several future research directions emerge from the limitations and challenges identified in Section 5.7. Firstly, further efforts are required to reduce orchestration overheads and improve the responsiveness of controller deployment in k8s-based clusters. Approaches such as stateful application migration, container warm-starting, and predictive scheduling may help reduce deployment latency and support faster agent handovers between CNMPCs. Secondly, while the resource modeling techniques in this thesis demonstrated strong predictive accuracy within tested domains, generalization to new hardware configurations or other classes of control applications (e.g., energy-aware or task-aware controllers) remains an open challenge. Incorporating lightweight machine learning models or transfer learning methods may further improve adaptability.

Finally, expanding the framework toward inter-controller coordination and hybrid centralized–distributed architectures presents a compelling direction. As noted, each CNMPC manages a bounded subset of agents, and while this preserves the tractability of centralized control, the overall MAS still requires coordination across these controller boundaries. Future work may explore lightweight protocols for inter-CNMPC consensus, inter-controller constraint sharing, or hierarchical coordination strategies, blending the benefits of centralization with scalable distributed control.

Together, these ongoing and prospective efforts aim to transition the proposed framework from a highly capable control-centric edge computing solution to a versatile, communication-aware, autonomy-enabling infrastructure, scalable across applications, adaptable to dynamic environments, and robust under real-world networking conditions.

6.5 Final Remark

Ultimately, this thesis contributes toward realizing the long-term vision of smart cities and Industry 4.0, where autonomous systems seamlessly interact with cloud-edge infrastructures to perform complex, collaborative tasks in real time. By tackling foundational challenges, such as network-induced delays, MAS coordination, and dynamic resource allocation, this work provides critical building blocks for the next generation of intelligent, resilient, and scalable robotic systems. Through the proposed architectures and methods, the thesis brings robotic autonomy one step closer to operating as an integral part of interconnected urban and industrial environments, fulfilling the promise of edge-enabled intelligence in modern cyber-physical ecosystems.

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